

SEPServer
Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report
Mission description and data comparison
Deliverable D2.2

	Name	Signature	Date
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Summary of the contents

SEPServer receives solar energetic particle data from many instruments on various spacecraft and missions. This document contains descriptions of those missions and comparisons of data from various instruments. The following sections are included:

- ✓ Overview of the missions involved
- ✓ Description of each single mission
- ✓ Comparative data quality assessment of instruments located close to each other at specific time periods
- ✓ Summary

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document summarizes the missions from which solar energetic particle (SEP) data have been delivered for SEPServer as described in the individual instrument Data Delivery Reports (DDRs).

This document consists of the following components:

- ✓ Overview of the missions involved
- ✓ Description of each single mission
- ✓ Comparative data quality assessment of instruments located close to each other at specific time periods
- ✓ Summary

1.2 Applicable documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
AD 1	Description of Work	EC-GA #262773, Annex I	10 Dec 2010
AD 2	SEPServer Data Delivery Plan	SEPSERVER-009-CAU-WP2	Issue 2, Rev. 3
AD 3	SEPServer Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: HELIOS E6 Instrument description and data quality	SEPSERVER-010-01-CAU-WP2	Issue 1, Rev. 1
AD 4	SEPServer Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: ULYSSES COSPIN Kiel Electron Telescope description and data quality	SEPSERVER-010-02-CAU-WP2	Issue 1, Rev. 0
AD 5	SEPServer Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: ULYSSES/COSPIN/LET Instrument description and data quality	SEPSERVER-010-03-NOA-WP2	Issue 1, Rev. 2
AD 6	SEPServer Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: ULYSSES/HISCALE	SEPSERVER-010-04-NOA-WP2	Issue 1, Rev. 1

	Instrument description and data quality		
AD 7	SEPServer Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: WIND 3DP Instrument description and data quality	SEPSERVER-010-05-UWUE-WP2	Issue 1, Rev. 0
AD 8	SEPServer Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: SOHO/EPHIN Instrument Description and Data Quality Report	SEPSERVER-010-06-CAU-WP2	Issue 1, Rev. 0
AD 9	SEPServer Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: SOHO/ERNE instrument description and data quality	SEPSERVER-010-07-UT-WP2	Issue 1, Rev. 1
AD 10	SEPServer Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: ACE/EPAM Instrument description and data quality	SEPSERVER-010-08-NOA-WP2	Issue 1, Rev. 1
AD 11	SEPServer Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: ACE/SIS Instrument description and data quality	SEPSERVER-010-09-NOA-WP2	Issue 1, Rev. 1
AD 12	SEPServer Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: STEREO/SEPT Instrument description and data quality	SEPSERVER-010-10-CAU-WP2	Issue 1, Rev. 0
AD 13	SEPServer Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: STEREO/LET Instrument description and data quality	SEPSERVER-010-11-NOA-WP2	Issue 1, Rev. 3

1.3 Reference documents

Ref.	Title	Document Reference
RD 1	The SOHO Mission: An Overview	Domingo, V., Fleck, B., and Poland, A.I.: Sol. Phys. 162, 1-37, 1995.
RD 2	Electron, Proton, and Alpha Monitor on the Advanced Composition Explorer spacecraft	Gold, R.E. et al.: Space Sci. Rev 86 541-562, 1998.
RD 3	The Solar Isotope Spectrometer for the	Stone, E. C. et al.: Space Sci. Rev. 86, 357-

	Advanced Composition Explorer	408, 1998.
RD 4	The Kiel University experiment for measuring cosmic radiation between 1.0 and 0.3 AU /E 6	Kunow, H. et al.: Raumfahrtforschung, 19, 253-258, 1975.
RD 5	COSTEP – Comprehensive Suprathermal and Energetic Particle Analyser	Müller-Mellin R. et al.: Sol. Phys., 162, 483-504, 1995.
RD 6	Energetic particle experiment ERNE	Torsti, J. et al.: Sol. Phys. 162, 505-531, 1995.
RD 7	Energetic and relativistic nuclei and electron experiment of the SOHO mission	Valtonen, E. et al.: Nucl. Instrum. and Meth. in Phys. Res. A391, 249-268, 1997.
RD 8	The Low-Energy Telescope (LET) and SEP Central Electronics for the STEREO Mission	Mewaldt, R. A. et al.: Space Sci. Rev. 136, 285-362, 2008.
RD 9	STEREO IMPACT Investigation Goals, Measurements, and Data Products Overview	Luhmann, J. G. et al.: Space Sci. Rev. 136, 117-184, 2008.
RD 10	The Solar Electron and Proton Telescope for the STEREO Mission.	Müller-Mellin, R. et al.: Spac. Sci. Rev. 136, 363-389, 2008.
RD 11	Corotating interaction regions	Heber, B. et al.: Adv. Space Res. 23, 567-579, 1998.
RD 12	The ULYSSES Cosmic Ray and Solar Particle Investigation	Simpson, J. A. et al.: Astron. Astrophys. Suppl. 92, 365-399, 1992.
RD 13	Heliosphere Instrument for Spectra, Composition and Anisotropy at Low Energies	Lanzerotti, L.J. et al.: Astron. Astrophys. Suppl. 92, 349-363, 1992.
RD 14	A Three- Dimensional Plasma and Energetic Particle Investigation for the WIND Spacecraft	Lin, R.P. et al.: Space Sci. Rev. 71, 125-153, 1995.
RD 15	The magnetic field investigation on the ULYSSES mission: Instrumentation and preliminary scientific results	Balogh, A. et al.: Astron. Astrophys. Suppl. 92, 221-236, 1992.
RD 16	The ULYSSES Mission	Wenzel, K.P. et al.: Astron. Astrophys. Suppl. 92, 207-219, 1992.

RD 17	Round-table discussion	Simpson, J.A. et al.: J. Geophys. Res. 64, 1691-1693, 1959.
RD 18	The STEREO Mission: An Introduction	Kaiser, M.L. et al.: Space Sci. Rev. 136, 5-16, 2008.
RD 19	Sun Earth Connection Coronal and Heliospheric Investigation (SECCHI)	Howard, R.A. et al.: Space Sci. Rev. 136, 67-115, 2008.
RD 20	The IMPACT Solar WIND Electron Analyzer (SWEA)	Sauvaud, J.-A. et al.: Space Sci. Rev. 136, 227-239, 2008.
RD 21	The STEREO IMPACT Suprathermal Electron (STE) Instrument	Lin, R.P. et al.: Space Sci. Rev. 136, 241-255, 2008.
RD 22	The STEREO/IMPACT Magnetic Field Experiment	Acuña, M.H. et al.: Space Sci. Rev. 136, 203-226, 2008.
RD 23	The STEREO IMPACT Boom	Ulrich, R. et al.: Space Sci. Rev. 136, 185-201, 2008.
RD 24	The Low-Energy Telescope (LET) and SEP Central Electronics for the STEREO Mission	Mewaldt, R.A. et al.: Space Sci. Rev. 136, 285-362, 2008.
RD 25	The High Energy Telescope for STEREO	von Rosenvinge, T.T. et al.: Space Sci. Rev. 136, 391-435, 2008.
RD 26	The Suprathermal Ion Telescope (SIT) for the IMPACT/SEP Investigation	Mason, G.M. et al.: Space Sci. Rev. 136, 257-284, 2008.
RD 27	The Plasma and Suprathermal Ion Composition (PLASTIC) Investigation on the STEREO Observatories	Galvin, A.B. et al.: Space Sci. Rev. 136, 437-486, 2008.
RD 28	S/WAVES: The Radio and Plasma Wave Investigation on the STEREO Mission	Bougeret, J.L. et al.: Space Sci. Rev. 136, 487-528, 2008.
RD 29	Comparison between ACE/EPAM and WIND/3DP	http://plasma2.ssl.berkeley.edu/~krucker/ace/epam_3dp.html

1.4 Abbreviations and acronyms

3DP	3-D Plasma
ACE	Advanced Composition Explorer
AT	Anisotropy Telescope
CCSDS	Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems
CDAWeb	Coordinated Data Analysis Web
CEPAC	COSTEP/ERNE particle analyser collaboration
COSPIN	Cosmic and Solar Particle INvestigation
COSTEP	COm-prehensive SupraThermal and Energetic Particle Analyser
DDP	Data Delivery Plan
DDR	Data Delivery Report
DE	Deflected Electrons
EPAM	Electron, Proton, and Alpha Monitor
EPHIN	Electron Proton Helium Instrument
ERNE	Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron
FGM	Flux Gate Magnetometer
GCI	Geocentric Inertial Coordinates
GSE	Geocentric Solar Ecliptic
GSFC	Goddard Space Flight Center
GSM	Geocentric Solar Magnetospheric
HISCALE	Heliosphere Instrument for Spectra, Composition and Anisotropy at Low Energies
HET	High Energy Telescope
HFT	High Flux Telescope
ISEE	International Sun Earth Explorer
IPM	InterPlanetary Medium
KET	Kiel Electron Telescope
LEFS	Low Energy Foil Spectrometers
LET	Low energy Telescope

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OBT	OnBoard Time
RTG	Radioisotope Thermoelectric Generator
RTN	Radial Tangential Normal
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SEPT	Solar Electron Proton Telescope
SIS	Solar Isotope Spectrometer
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
STEREO	Solar TERrestrial RELations Observatory
TAI	Temps Atomique International
VHM	Vector Helium Magnetometer

2 Overview of the missions involved

Significant developments in our understanding of solar energetic particles in the heliosphere are based on both theoretical understanding and observational evidence especially due to more-detailed near-Earth observations. ULYSSES has continued its studies of the latitudinal distribution of cosmic rays and other energetic charged particles for almost two full consecutive 11-year sunspot cycles, with the attendant important change in the magnetic field sign. The inner heliosphere is again in the focus of future exploration, and there is the potential for forming out of the current and proposed missions an Inner Heliosphere Observatory comparable to the Great Heliospheric Observatory for the outer heliosphere. Thus, in anticipation of this network, it is a perfect time to develop techniques and strategies for combining the different energetic particle measurements, which currently span the time period from the early 1970's to recent space instrumentation, to address scientific questions concerning energetic particle acceleration, injection, and propagation in the inner heliosphere environment.

Table 1 Satellites from which SEP data have been provided for SEPServer. The color of the "Mission" indicates the location; green at L1 or similar distance, purple inside 1 AU, and black between 1 and 5.3 AU. The superscript indicates if the measurements allow the derivation of pitch angle distributions from a spinning (1) or not spinning platform (2) or not (0).

Mission	1970-1979	1980-1989	1990-1999	2000-2013
HELIOS A/B ¹	1974-1982 1976-1980			
ULYSSES ¹			1990 – 2009	
SOHO ²				1995 -
WIND ¹				1994 -
ACE ¹				1997-
STEREO ²				2006-

Table 1 lists the relevant measurements that are the basis of our SEPServer study. Some of these observations are taken (partially) close to 1 AU (ACE, WIND, SOHO, and

STEREO), within 1 AU (HELIOS) or beyond 1 AU (ULYSSES). Each of the measurements involved cover certain particle composition and energy ranges, may allow the determination of particle pitch angle distribution or spatial gradients of the particle phase space density.

3 Description of missions involved

3.1 HELIOS

The HELIOS program has been the biggest scientific German-American space research program so far. The program was based on a contract between the American National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and the German Federal Ministry of Research and Technology concluded on 10th July 1969. In the course of this program, two space probes, HELIOS-1 on December 10, 1974 and HELIOS-2 on January 15, 1976, were launched into a heliocentric orbit. Each one had ten scientific experiments on board. The two spacecraft and seven of the scientific experiments had been developed and built in the Federal Republic of Germany. NASA supplied the two launch vehicles, both Titan III E/Centaur/TE-364-4, three experiments as well as test and launch support. The German Space Operations Center (GSOC) and the NASA Deep Space Network (DSN) were joined to a common ground operations system.

The responsibility for operating the space probes was located at the control center for space vehicles of the German Aerospace Center (DFVLR). On the German side, the project was managed by the German Aerospace Center, department for project funding (former GFW), the space probes were developed and produced by an industrial consortium with the Munich firm Messerschmitt-Bölkow-Blohm (MBB) as prime contractor.

3.1.1 HELIOS Orbit

The main scientific aim of the HELIOS mission was the exploration of the physical phenomena in the inner solar system and, by means of a smaller distance to the sun, a more precise observation of events in the atmosphere of the sun. Two practically identical

space probes were sent into highly eccentric, elliptic orbits around the sun: Figure 1 shows the orbits of HELIOS-1 and HELIOS-2 in the sidereal coordinate system. For comparison Figure 2 shows the same orbits in a system with a fixed earth-sun axis. The orbital period around the sun was 190 days for HELIOS-1 and 185 days for HELIOS-2. The distance to the sun at the point closest to the sun was 0.3095 AU for HELIOS-1 and 0.290 AU for HELIOS-2. The points most distant to the sun are at approximately 0.98 AU (1 AU is the astronomical unit, the average sun-earth distance of 1.5×10^8 km).

Figure 1 The orbits of HELIOS-1 and HELIOS-2 in the sidereal coordinate system. The solar-ecliptic latitude of the spacecraft in relation to every point of the trajectory can be determined on the basis of the latitude markers along the inner circle. All the points of the orbit right of the sun's equator nodal line are south of the sun's equator; all the points left of this line are north of the sun's equator. Note that the launch date (Dec 10, 1975) for HELIOS 1 is wrong, it should read Dec 10, 1974.

Figure 2 The orbits of HELIOS-1 and HELIOS-2 in relation to the axis earth-sun for the years 1974 to 1980.

3.1.2 Scientific aim of the HELIOS mission and its experiments

German scientists have been studying the sun and the interplanetary space close to the sun for decades. Especially Prof. L. Biermann's theories about the solar wind from 1951 should be mentioned in this regard. The project HELIOS to investigate the sun and the inner solar system directly tied in with these theories. But it was also a direct and logical continuation of the exploration of the entire solar system commenced in 1967. Various Mariner- and Venera missions as well as the Pioneer-Venus mission investigated the interplanetary space as far as to the planet Venus. Mariner X advanced to Mercury in the inner solar system. Other Mariner-, Mars-, Pioneer- and Viking-spacecraft explored the outer solar system far beyond Jupiter. So the probes HELIOS-1 and HELIOS-2 were a significant part of the worldwide research focus 'solar system'. They proceeded further into the inner solar system than any spaceflight object had ever done before or after.

There were ten scientific instruments on board for studying the physical characteristics of the interplanetary medium near the sun and for a 'closer' remote observation of the solar atmosphere. They were optimally adapted to each other and complemented each other well. The instruments on-board can be divided into three categories with the following measuring tasks:

1. Five experiments for studying interplanetary plasma and fields:
 - a. Investigation of electrons, protons and alpha particles, measurement of their energy spectrum and their three-dimensional distribution
 - b. Measurement of three components of the magnetic field up to 5 Hz
 - c. Measurement of oscillating magnetic fields up to 2 kHz
 - d. Measurement of oscillations of the electric field and waves up to 3 MHz.

2. Three experiments for studying the cosmic radiation:
 - a. Measurement of mass and energy spectra of the cosmic particle radiation [RD 4]
 - b. Determining their angular distribution
 - c. Observation of the solar X-ray activity
 - d. Registration of galactic and extragalactic gamma ray bursts (only for HELIOS-2)

3. Two experiments for studying micrometeoroids and dust
 - a. Measurement of the intensity and the polarization of the zodiacal light under the angles of 16°, 31° and 90° w.r.t. the orbit.
 - b. Determining the intensity of dust particles in interplanetary space.
 - c. Determining mass, speed and composition of micrometeoroids.

In addition, the exact orbit measurement plus duration, Doppler shift, phase rotation and range of the telemetry signal were used for conducting so-called passive experiments. The aim of this study was an improved measurement of parameters of Einstein's Theory of Relativity and probing of the solar corona.

For SEPServer, data from the Kiel E6 experiment have been provided.

3.1.3 The HELIOS spacecraft

The outer shape of the HELIOS space probe was determined by the necessity of an energy supply via solar cells, which could cope with a solar heat input that changed by a

factor of 12 along the trajectory. The enormous insolation at perihelion and the requirements of the subsystems and the experiments to stay constantly within a relatively narrow temperature interval from -10°C to $+20^{\circ}\text{C}$ posed a major challenge to the thermal control system.

The probe consisted of a 16-sided centerbody housing the subsystems of the spacecraft and the majority of the experiments. Attached to the central body were two conical solar arrays for the generation of electrical power. Thereby, the probe obtained a configuration in the shape of a spool. Figure 3 shows a schematic drawing of the space probe. The magnetometer experiments were attached to the side arms that could be folded out. Each side arm was a double-hinged boom which was folded during launch. Also at the side of the centerbody, but shifted by 90° from the side arms, the extensible antennas were located. They had a tip-to-tip length of 32 m and were used for measuring plasma and radio waves. Above the central body, the antenna systems stuck out over the solar cell panels. The high-gain antenna had to be despun so that at all times it pointed towards the earth during flight because the entire spacecraft rotated by one revolution per second around its own axis. In flight, the aerial mast points north (HELIOS-1) or south (HELIOS-2). Therefore the reflector of the directional antenna needs to be controlled by a despun motor so that the maximum transmission power was always emitted earthwards. Underneath the central body, covered by the solar array, the adapter was positioned for connecting the spacecraft to the upper propulsion stage.

Figure 3 Schematic Drawing of the HELIOS-Space Probe.

3.2 ULYSSES

The primary purpose of the ULYSSES mission was to explore the inner heliosphere of the Sun away from the ecliptic plane. This mission was unique in that the spacecraft traveled over the solar poles, exploring regions of the sun in a manner not previously attempted. ULYSSES spacecraft, a joint NASA and European Space Agency mission, was launched in October 6, 1990. Table 2 summarizes the major milestones achieved by that mission.

Table 2 ULYSSES list of milestones

Milestone	Date
ULYSSES Launch	6 Oct. 1990
Jupiter Fly-by	Feb. 1992
1 st South Polar Pass (solar minimum, $A>0$)	Jun. – Nov. 1994
1 st North Polar Pass	Jun. – Sep. 1995
End of prime mission, extended mission starts	Oct. 1995
2 nd South Polar Pass (solar maximum)	Sep. 2000 – Jan. 2001
2 nd North Polar Pass	Sep. – Dec. 2001
Jupiter distant encounter	Jun. 2004
ESA's SPC approves mission extension until March 2009	14 Nov. 2007
3 rd South Polar Pass (solar minimum, $A<0$)	Nov. 2006 – Apr. 2007
3 rd North Polar Pass	Nov. 2007 – Mar. 2008
X-band transmitter failure	15 Jan. 2008
S-band downlink at 1024 bps, real time and tape recorder data transmitted to 70 m ground stations	15 Jan. – 31 May 2008
S-band downlink at 512 bps, only real time data transmitted to ground stations (data gaps result)	Jun. 2008 – Jun. 2009
ULYSSES commanded to switch off its transmitter. End of mission	30 Jun. 2009

3.2.1 ULYSSES trajectory

To reach high solar latitudes, the spacecraft was aimed close to Jupiter so that Jupiter's large gravitational field would accelerate ULYSSES out of the ecliptic plane to high latitudes. The encounter with Jupiter occurred on February 8, 1992, and since then ULYSSES travelled to higher heliospheric latitudes investigating for the first time the 3D Heliosphere. ULYSSES was originally scheduled to be a five year mission, with the first south polar pass occurring in June-October 1994 and the north polar pass occurring June-September 1995 (see Figure 4). The orbit of Jupiter determined the aphelion distance; the perihelion was chosen to be ~ 1.3 AU for thermal reasons. The orbital period was ~ 6.4 years, i.e. roughly half a solar cycle. When the spacecraft's instrumentation was finally switched off in mid 2009, it completed three full orbits.

Figure 4 The in-ecliptic trajectory and orbit of ULYSSES around the Sun. The Jupiter flyby occurred in Feb. 1992 and about 1.5 years later, in summer 1994, the spacecraft passed the Sun's south pole and crossed the ecliptic plane in March 1995.

3.2.2 Scientific aim of the ULYSSES mission and its experiments

Although, the idea of exploring the heliosphere at high solar latitudes is as old as the age of space exploration itself [RD 17], it was not before the mid-seventies when work began on a mission to explore the solar poles. This mission was initially designed as a twin spacecraft mission named "International Solar Polar Mission" (ISPM) and was re-named to ULYSSES after several changes in the design of the mission and the budget allowance and was finally launched as a single spacecraft mission in October 1990. A detailed description can be found in [RD 16]. The primary aims of the mission were the following:

- ✓ To study the three-dimensional properties of the interplanetary magnetic field and the solar wind, including studies of the composition of the solar wind to understand its origin at different latitudes and the investigation of waves, shocks, discontinuities and the interaction of different solar wind streams.
- ✓ To investigate galactic cosmic rays (including Jovian electrons), and solar energetic particles.
- ✓ To improve the understanding of interplanetary dust in the solar system.

3.2.3 ULYSSES instrumentation

To achieve the goals of the mission described above, ULYSSES was equipped with 9 instruments displayed in Figure 5. Only those from which data are provided for SEP Server are:

VHM/FGM The magnetometer aboard ULYSSES, described in detail in [RD 15] consists of two separate instruments. The Vector Helium Instrument (VHM) was based on the magnetometers already flown on the Pioneer 10/11 and ISEE3 spacecraft and exploited the observation that the effectiveness of optical pumping is affected by the presence of an ambient magnetic field. The Fluxgate Magnetometer (FGM) consisted of three single axis ring-core fluxgate sensors. The combination of these instruments allowed measurements of the interplanetary magnetic field and the magnetic field of Jupiter with high precision. For interplanetary spacecraft missions it is common to use the RTN-

coordinate system¹ for the representation of the magnetic field vector. The R component is along the connection from the Sun to the spacecraft. The T component is the result of the cross product of the solar rotation axis and the R. The N component is the cross product of R and T. VHM/FGM magnetic field data for SEPServer are downloaded from CDAWEB.

COSPIN The Cosmic Ray and Solar Particle Investigation (COSPIN) instrument group consisted of the Kiel Electron Telescope (KET), the High Energy Telescope (HET), the High Flux Telescope (HFT), the Low Energy Telescope (LET) and the Anisotropy Telescope (AT) as described in [RD 12]. The purpose of COSPIN was the measurement of high energetic particles in a wide range of energy in the interplanetary medium. The KET and LET have been described in more detail in [AD 4] and [AD 5], respectively.

HISCALE The Heliosphere Instrument for Spectra, Composition, and Anisotropy at Low Energies (HI-SCALE) instrument onboard the ULYSSES spacecraft has been described in [RD 13]. The instrument is described further in [AD 6].

Figure 5 Sketch of the ULYSSES spacecraft including the locations of scientific payload. The dish antenna on top of the spacecraft's body provides up- and downlink communication between the ground control and ULYSSES. The power source, a RTG (radioisotope thermoelectric generator), is located on the right upper side of the sketch.

3.3 WIND

The *WIND* spacecraft was launched on November 1, 1994. The dry weight of the spacecraft is 875 kilograms, with an additional 368 kilograms of hydrazine propellant for orbit and attitude control. The nominal mission life was three years. During this time, *WIND* was placed initially into a highly elliptical orbit (apogee $> \sim 60 R_E$, with the Earth radius $R_E = 6370$ km), followed by a lunar swingby orbit in which the apogee was increased to $\sim 250 R_E$, sending *WIND* into a 7-month outer loop that reached the Lagrangian point L1. The perigee remained above $4.5 R_E$. A further lunar flyby in October 1997 sent the spacecraft in a halo orbit around the L1 point. This flyby marked the completion of the nominal mission phase and the beginning of the extended mission. The extended mission has comprised various orbital phases and concepts, including halo orbits at L1 and L2, high-inclination orbits, deep-magnetotail excursions, and distant prograde orbits (with excursions of up to $320 R_E$ in the Y_{GSE} direction). Since May 2004, *WIND* has remained in a halo orbit around the L1 point (for details, see <http://wind.nasa.gov/orbit.php>).

Figure 6 Sketch of the WIND spacecraft.

3.3.1 Instruments

WIND is a spin-stabilized (20 rpm) cylinder-shaped spacecraft measuring 2.4 m in diameter and 1.8 m in height (see Figure 6), with the spin axis pointing towards the Ecliptic South. It carries 8 instruments: the Solar WIND Experiment (SWE) to measure solar wind electrons and ions, the Solar WIND and Suprathermal Ion Composition Studies (SMS) experiment to determine the abundance, velocity, spectra, temperature and thermal speeds of solar wind ions, the Three-Dimensional Plasma & Energetic Particles (3DP) experiment [RD 14] to measure electrons and ions from the solar wind plasma to low energy cosmic rays, the Energetic Particle Acceleration, Composition and Transport (EPACT) experiment to measure high-energy ions in the solar wind, the Magnetic Fields Instrument (MFI) to measure the intensity, direction and fluctuations in the interplanetary magnetic field, the Plasma and Radio Waves (WAVES) experiment to measure radio waves and other wave modes of the plasma over a wide frequency range, and the Transient Gamma Ray Burst Detector (KONUS) to study gamma-ray bursts.

For SEP Server, particle data have been provided from the 3DP experiment. In addition, electromagnetic data are provided from the WAVES experiment (see Data Delivery Report of EM data).

3.3.2 Mission goals and objectives

The primary science objectives of the *WIND* mission are:

- Provide complete plasma, energetic particle and magnetic field data for solar wind, magnetospheric and ionospheric studies.
- The detailed exploration of the interplanetary particle population in the suprathermal energy range.
- The study of particle acceleration at the Sun, in the interplanetary medium, and upstream from the Earth.
- The study of the transport of suprathermal particles in the interplanetary medium.
- The study of basic plasma processes occurring in the interplanetary medium, such as wave-particle interactions, the production of radio emission by beam-plasma processes (Type III bursts), shock waves, and solar wind heat flux.

-
- The measurement of the particle and plasma input to and output from the Earth's magnetosphere
 - Provide baseline, 1 AU, ecliptic plane observations for inner and outer heliospheric missions.

3.4 SOHO

The Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO), is a project of international cooperation between ESA and NASA to study the Sun, from its deep core to the outer corona, the solar wind and energetic particles [RD 1]. Current information on the mission can be found at <http://sohowww.nascom.nasa.gov/>.

SOHO was launched on 2 December 1995. SOHO was transferred into a halo orbit around the First Lagrangian Point (L1) of the Sun-Earth system, where the combined gravity of the Earth and Sun keeps SOHO in an orbit locked to the Earth-Sun line. The L1 point is approximately 1.5 million kilometres away from Earth in the direction of the Sun.

Therefore, SOHO has an uninterrupted view of the Sun from outside of the Earth's magnetosphere. The halo orbit of SOHO is illustrated in Figure 7. SOHO orbit data are available at <http://sohowww.nascom.nasa.gov/data/ancillary/orbit/predictive/>. The Orbit data describe the position and motion of the spacecraft, and are available in several coordinate systems including geocentric inertial (GCI) coordinates for the J2000 system, geocentric solar ecliptic (GSE), geocentric solar magnetospheric (GSM) coordinates, and Heliocentric Ecliptic coordinate system.

Figure 7 SOHO orbit schematic illustrating the orbit variation in X, Y, and Z as function of time.

SOHO is a three-axis stabilised spacecraft constantly pointing to the centre of the Sun. At the beginning of the mission the nominal roll angle was zero. However, after the failure of the high-gain antenna drive mechanism the high-gain antenna has been parked in a fixed position since the summer of 2003. In order to maximize the time that data can be sent to Earth through the high gain antenna SOHO has to turn upside down during half of its halo orbit. In other words, the nominal roll switches between 0 and 180 degrees every 3 months. The roll attitude is listed in:

http://sohowww.nascom.nasa.gov/data/ancillary/attitude/roll/nominal_roll_attitude.dat.

Up until October 29, 2010, if the roll angle of SOHO was zero, the spacecraft +Z axis was aligned with the North Pole of the Sun ("right side up"). If the roll angle was 180, spacecraft -Z axis was aligned with the North Pole of the Sun ("upside down"). After October 29, 2010, the reference for the nominal roll attitude of the spacecraft no longer is the solar North Pole, but the Ecliptic North Pole. Therefore, the roll angle with respect of the solar rotation axis goes from -7.25 degrees in June to 7.25 degrees in December.

When SOHO is in the "middle" parts of its orbit, it is not possible to point the spacecraft to the Sun while also pointing the high-gain antenna towards Earth. These parts of the orbit are called SOHO "keyhole periods", and they occur twice per orbit (since summer 2003).

SOHO's each halo orbit around L1 takes about half a year, so keyholes affect SOHO operations roughly every 3 months. The SOHO keyhole periods are listed in <http://soho.nascom.nasa.gov/soc/keyholes.txt>.

SOHO carries 12 instruments, 8 remote sensing and 4 *in-situ* instruments. The energetic particle instruments on-board SOHO are COSTEP and ERNE, together forming the COSTEP-ERNE Particle Analyzer Collaboration (CEPAC). Data from the COSTEP/EPHIN [AD 8] and ERNE [AD 9] have been provided for SEPServer; see also [RD 5, RD 6, RD 7]. The SOHO payload module is shown in Figure 8 with the COSTEP/EPHIN and ERNE instruments.

The SOHO On-Board Time (OBT) uses the CCSDS format, level 1 (TAI reference, 1958 January 1 epoch). The SOHO OBT is an unsegmented time code with a basic time equal to 1 second and a value representing the number of seconds from 1 January 1958 based on International Atomic Time. E.g., the data provided for SEPServer by SOHO/ERNE is time-referenced to the SOHO OBT [AD 9].

SOHO is operated from NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC). Ground control is provided via NASA's Deep Space Network antennae. The data from GSFC is sent directly to the institutes responsible for the instruments through internet.

Figure 8 SOHO payload module with COSTEP/EPHIN and ERNE.

3.5 ACE

The Advanced Composition Explorer (ACE) was launched in August 1997 with the primary task of monitoring the elemental, isotopic, and ionic charge-state composition of energetic particles in the nearby interplanetary medium (IPM). These particles originate from three major sources: the Sun, the nearby interstellar medium, and other galactic sources. ACE

carries a collection of different instruments designed to measure particle energies ranging from ~ 100 eV/nuc to ~ 500 MeV/nuc. ACE will remain within the ecliptic plane at the L1 point, about 0.99 AU from the Sun. ACE was placed in a halo orbit around the L1 point; see **Figure 9** This keeps ACE along a direct line between the Earth and Sun even though ACE is about 0.01 AU closer. Being in this location allows ACE to monitor the status of the solar wind and relay data back to Earth with about an hour lead time. The L1 point is not a stable point of equilibrium and orbit corrections must be performed approximately once every five days.

Figure 9 ACE trajectory.

Mission goals and objectives

Most of the goals and objectives for ACE involve compositional and origin studies of the various particle populations that are found in the near IPM. These goals are as follows [RD 3]:

- Determine the solar isotopic abundances through direct sampling of solar material,
- Determine the elemental and isotopic composition of the solar corona, interplanetary pick-up ions, and anomalous cosmic rays,
- Explain the formation processes for the solar corona and the acceleration of the

solar wind, and

- Characterize the mechanisms of energetic particle acceleration and transport in the heliosphere.

The Advanced Composition Explorer was launched on August 25, 1997, by a Delta II rocket from Cape Canaveral Air Force Station. In similar fashion to ULYSSES, ACE is spin-stabilized, rotating at a rate of 5 rpm. ACE, however, only has about half the mass of ULYSSES, 156 kg. The significant difference in weight is primarily the result of the power systems employed by ACE. ACE will remain at the first Lagrange point, L1, at a distance of 0.99 AU. This permits ACE the luxury of using solar panels for power generation whereas ULYSSES is reliant upon RTGs. There are nine different instruments on the ACE spacecraft. For SEPServer, solar energetic particle data have been provided from EPAM and SIS. In addition, supplementary magnetic field and solar wind data have been provided from MAG and SWEAPAM. EPAM and SIS instruments and their data are described in detail in [AD 10] [AD 11], respectively.

The ACE spacecraft was designed to provide at least 90% duty cycle over a 2 to 5 year period. As of the writing of this document, ACE is in its 16th year of operation and still appears to be functioning adequately. There are some troubles with a couple of the detectors on the EPAM instrument [RD 2], which are detailed in [AD 10], but the ability to achieve the main mission objectives stated in the previously mentioned remains intact.

3.6 STEREO

STEREO is the third mission in NASA's Solar Terrestrial Probes program (STP). It employs two nearly identical space-based observatories - one ahead of Earth in its orbit (STEREO-A: STA), the other trailing behind (STEREO-B: STB) (see [Figure 10](#)) providing the first-ever stereoscopic measurements of the Sun with the goal to study the nature of coronal mass ejections (CMEs) (see Section 3.6.1). STEREO mission represents a revolutionary addition to Heliophysics research as it provides measurements from a rich package of upgraded sensors (see Section 3.6.2). It also travels to new vantage points (see Section 3.6.3) providing for the first time coherent analysis and interpretation of CMEs/ICMEs and SEPs under the multi-spacecraft approach (see Section 3.6.4).

Figure 10 An artist's conception of the STEREO mission. Two nearly identical spacecraft situated well off the Earth–Sun line, making simultaneous measurements of the Sun (taken from [RD 18]).

3.6.1 Mission goals and objectives

The principal mission objective for STEREO is to understand the origin and consequences of CMEs, the most energetic eruptions on the Sun and the cause of the most severe nonrecurrent geomagnetic storms at Earth. These have been presented in detail in [RD 18]. Specific science objectives are to:

- Understand the causes and mechanisms of CME initiation.
- Characterize the propagation of CMEs through the heliosphere.
- Discover the mechanisms and sites of solar energetic particle acceleration in the low corona and the interplanetary medium.
- Develop a three-dimensional, time-dependent model of the magnetic topology,

temperature, density and velocity structure of the ambient solar wind.

3.6.2 Scientific payload of the two STEREO spacecraft

The scientific payload of the two STEREO spacecraft consists of four measurement packages, each of which has several components totaling at least 18 individual sensors (**Figure 11**). Together, this suite of instruments will characterize the CME plasma from the solar corona to Earth's orbit. In what follows we provide a brief introduction of these instruments as those were presented in [RD20]

- **Sun–Earth Connection Coronal and Heliospheric Investigation (SECCHI).** SECCHI encompasses a suite of remote sensing instruments including two white-light coronagraphs, an extreme ultraviolet imager and two white-light heliospheric imagers all designed to study the three-dimensional evolution of CMEs from the Sun's surface through the corona and interplanetary medium to their eventual impact at Earth. A comprehensive description of the SECCHI suite of instruments is given by [RD 19].
- **In situ Measurements of PArticles and CME Transients (IMPACT)** measures the interplanetary magnetic field, thermal and suprathermal solar wind electrons, and energetic electrons and ions. IMPACT is a suite of seven instruments, three of which—the solar wind electron analyzer (SWEA), the suprathermal electron instrument (STE) and the magnetic field experiment (MAG)—are located on a six-meter deployable boom deployed anti-sunward. The remaining IMPACT instruments—the low energy telescope (LET), the high-energy telescope (HET), the suprathermal ion telescope (SIT) and the solar electron and proton telescope (SEPT)—are all located on the main body of the spacecraft and are dedicated to measuring solar energetic particles (SEPs). The IMPACT suite is described in a series of papers: [RD 9] provides an overview, SWEA is described in [RD 20], STE in [RD 21], MAG in [RD 22] and [RD 23] describes the boom itself. The LET instrument and the computer system that controls all the SEP instruments, known

as SEP central, are described in [RD 24]. The HET instrument is described in [RD 25], the SIT in [RD 26] and the SEPT in [RD 10].

- **PLAsma and SupraThermal Ion Composition (PLASTIC)**, provides in situ plasma characteristics of protons, alpha particles and heavy ions. It supplies key diagnostic measurements of the mass and charge state composition of heavy ions and characterizes the CME plasma from ambient coronal plasma. The PLASTIC instrument is described in [RD 27].
- **STEREO/WAVES (S/WAVES)** is an interplanetary radio burst tracker that observes the generation and evolution of traveling radio disturbances from the Sun to the orbit of Earth. As its primary sensors, S/WAVES uses three mutually orthogonal monopole antenna elements, each six meters in length. The three monopoles were deployed antisunward so that they remain out of the fields of view of Sun-facing instruments. The S/WAVES instrument is described in [RD 28].

For SEPSErver, sectorized electron and ion data have been provided from IMPACT/SEPT [AD 12] and sectorized proton and helium data from IMPACT/LET [AD 13]. These data have been provided from both STEREO/A and STEREO/B spacecraft.

Figure 11 An artist's conception of the Behind spacecraft with the locations of the instruments shown. The SECCHI instruments point at the Sun and the IMPACT boom and S/WAVES antennas are on the opposite end. There are very slight differences between the Ahead and Behind spacecraft, mainly due to the fact that the spacecraft fly upside down relative to one another so that their high-gain antenna is always on the Earth-facing side of the spacecraft. This means that some of the particle instruments which need to point into the solar wind magnetic field direction have different placements on the two spacecraft (taken from [RD 18]).

3.6.3 STEREO's orbit

The twin STEREO spacecraft were launched on October 26, 2006, at 00:52 UT from Kennedy Space Center aboard a Delta 7925 launch vehicle. After a series of highly eccentric Earth orbits with apogees beyond the Moon, each spacecraft used close flybys of the Moon to escape into orbits about the Sun near 1 AU. Once in heliospheric orbit, one

spacecraft trails Earth while the other leads (**Figure 12**). As viewed from the Sun, the two spacecraft separate at approximately 44 to 45 degrees per year.

Figure 12 STEREO's orbit [taken from RD 18].

3.6.4 The multi-spacecraft approach

[RD20] explains in great detail the multi-spacecraft approach that is greatly facilitated via the STEREO mission. The strength and orientation of the interplanetary magnetic field at the two different STEREO spacecraft, combined with the suprathermal electron measurements will help to determine whether the local magnetic fields of the interplanetary CME (i.e. ICME), are rooted at the Sun at one or both ends or disconnected. Such magnetic topology information tells us about the coronal origins of the CME/ICME

and also about the role of processes such as reconnection at the Sun and in the IP medium. Higher energy electron, and also ion, detectors provide information on whether the local field connects to a flaring active region. Detection of SEP events at the two locations, with high time resolution and directional information over the energy range from 10s of keV to ~100 MeV, allow remote sensing of the CME-initiated shock location and strength as it travels into the heliosphere. SEP ion composition measurements make it possible to distinguish between electron and heavy ion-rich flare-accelerated particles and solar wind particles accelerated at the interplanetary shock. The lowest energy SEP ions also provide information on the ambient suprathermal ion “seed” populations that may feed the higher energy SEP production at the CME related shocks. With the radio and plasma waves investigation, opportunities exist for in situ plasma microphysics diagnostics on local shock structures and waves, as well as comparisons of radio remote sensing and SEP remote sensing of coronal shocks. The in situ data integration with images and ground based images and magnetograph observations through Sun-to-Earth modeling enables a STEREO era of regular cradle-to-grave analyses of the CME phenomenon. In particular, details of the conditions on the Sun that lead to specific 1 AU consequences can be investigated, and used to refine observational strategies for space weather missions such as the Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO) and for formulating updated science questions for Solar Orbiter and Solar Probe.

Figure 13 Illustration of the interaction of a flux rope-like interplanetary coronal mass ejection with the ambient solar wind. The inset shows how the instruments of the IMPACT investigation are configured to make in situ measurements of the structures and particle populations at each spacecraft location (taken from [RD 9]).

4 Comparative data quality assessment of instruments located close to each other at specific time periods

4.1 Comparative data quality assessment for instrumentation close to Earth

Comparisons of the data delivered to SEPServer are undertaken for selected sample of events. In some cases not only the intensity time profiles but higher order data products such as energy spectra or pitch angle distributions of different instruments are compared with each other. Of special interest to the project are the data sets close to Earth and at a distance of about 1 AU because simulations have been undertaken for these distances (see Delivery Report of simulations and inversion methods). The following events were selected for the comparison between ACE SIS, ACE EPAM, WIND 3DP, SOHO/ERNE, and SOHO EPHIN:

1. 13 November 1997, event number 4 of the SOHO/ERNE event list. The time profiles displayed in Figure 14 were obtained from the SEPServer server interface and show the corresponding data from WIND 3DP, ACE EPAM, SOHO/ERNE and SOHO EPHIN for selected energy channels.
2. 27 May 1999, event number 17 of the SOHO/ERNE event list. The time profiles displayed in Figure 18 are from the SEPServer server interface and show the corresponding data from WIND 3DP, ACE EPAM, SOHO/ERNE and SOHO EPHIN for selected energy channels.
3. 01 November 2004, event number 96 of the SOHO/ERNE event list. The time profiles displayed in Figure 22 are from the SEPServer server interface and show the corresponding data from WIND 3DP, ACE EPAM, SOHO/ERNE and SOHO EPHIN for selected energy channels.
4. 14 July, 2005, event number 105 of the SOHO/ERNE event list. The time profiles displayed in Figure 26 are from the SEPServer server interface and show the corresponding data from WIND 3DP, ACE EPAM, SOHO/ERNE and SOHO EPHIN

for selected energy channels.

Sections 4.1.1 4.1.4 below contain figures of the selected events:

1. The first figure in each section contains (from top to bottom) the intensity time profiles of WIND 3DP protons between 1.4 MeV and 7.1 MeV in three energy channels, ACE/EPAM ion intensities between 1.1 MeV and 4.8 MeV in two energy channels, SOHO/EPHIN proton intensities between 4.3 and 41 MeV in three energy channels, and SOHO/ERNE proton intensities in the energy range between 1.8 MeV to 40 MeV in four energy channels. Note, that the intensities are given per MeV with the exception of WIND 3DP which is given per eV. In order to compare WIND 3DP with the other measurements, the WIND 3DP intensities have to be multiplied by a factor of 10^{+6} . The purpose of the figure is to illustrate the general characteristics of the event as seen by the different instruments. Note that these plots show how the SEPServer server database can be used by the community.
2. The second figure in each section displays the orbital information of the three spacecraft if available from <http://sscweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/>. The purpose of the figure is to give an overall impression of the relative locations of the spacecraft and of their locations with respect to the Earth's magnetosphere and bow shock, which also serve as defining the rough scale of the figure.
3. The third and fourth figures display the proton and helium energy spectra for selected time periods
 - a. 13.11.1997 from the event onset (22:26 UT) till 14.11.1997 02:00.
 - b. 27.5.1999 from onset (11:16 UT) till 18:00 UT.
 - c. 1.11.2004 from onset (05:15 UT) till 18:00 UT.
 - d. 14.7.2005 00:00 UT - 24:00 UT.

Comparing the energy spectra of the four periods we find differences of several tens of percent between the various instruments. In order to investigate these differences in more detail, we analyze in section 4.1.5 the intensity time profiles of the July 2005 event for SOHO/EPHIN and SOHO/ERNE. As discussed there, the conclusion of the analysis is that the intensities from these two instruments do agree with each other within a factor of 50%.

4.1.1 November 13, 1997 solar energetic particle event

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Figure 14: Intensity time profiles for selected proton channels from the SOHO/EPHIN, WIND 3DP, ACE EPAM, and SOHO/ERNE for the November 13, 1997 event (generated by SEPServer).

Figure 15 Spacecraft locations of ACE (blue symbol), SOHO (purple symbol) and WIND (green symbol) during November 13 and 14, 1997 (from <http://sscweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/>)

Figure 16 Energy spectra of protons in the energy range of a few tens of keV to above 100 MeV for the November 13, 1997 event.

Figure 17 Energy spectra of Helium from a few MeV/nucleon to above 100 MeV/nucleon for the November 13, 1997 event

The energy spectra of protons for the rising phase of the November 13, 1997 event (from 22:26 UT November 13 till 02:00 UT November 14) measured by ACE/EPAM, SOHO/ERNE and SOHO/EPHIN are shown in Figure 16. The agreement is good at the lowest energies covered by these instruments, while at higher energies there are differences of 60 to 90 %.

The corresponding energy spectra for ^4He measured by SOHO/ERNE, SOHO/EPHIN and ACE/SIS are shown in Figure 17. For helium the agreement is reasonable for all three instruments in the energy range where a comparison can be made. At energies between 60-80 MeV/nucleon the shape of the energy spectrum changes, which is probably caused by galactic cosmic rays. However, the fast drop of the helium intensity in Figure 17 at the two highest energies measured by ERNE is probably an instrumental effect. This is further discussed in [AD 9]. Here it is only noted that the highest energy proton and helium intensities measured by ERNE should be treated with caution.

4.1.2 May 27, 1999 solar energetic particle event

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Figure 18 Intensity time profiles of different proton channels from the WIND 3DP, ACE/EPAM, SOHO EPHIN and SOHO ERNE instrument for the May 27, 1999 solar energetic particle event (generated by SEPServer).

Figure 19 Spacecraft locations of ACE (blue symbol), SOHO (purple symbol) and WIND (green symbol) during the May 27, 1999 solar energetic particle event (from <http://sscweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/>)

Figure 20 Energy spectra of protons in the energy range from a few tens of keV to more than 100 MeV.

Figure 21 Helium energy spectra from SOHO/ERNE, SOHO/EPHIN and ACE/SIS are compared to each other

The energy spectra of protons for the May 27, 1999 event (from 11:16 UT till 18:00 UT) measured by ACE/EPAM, SOHO/ERNE and SOHO/EPHIN are shown in Figure 20. The agreement is relatively good over the entire common energy range of ACE/EPAM, ERNE and EPHIN.

The corresponding energy spectra for ^4He measured by SOHO/ERNE, SOHO/EPHIN and ACE/SIS are shown in Figure 21. The agreement between ERNE and EPHIN is good, while the intensities of ACE/SIS seem to be generally roughly by a factor of 1.5 to 1.7 lower compared to ERNE and EPHIN.

4.1.3 November 1, 2004 solar energetic particle event

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Figure 22 Intensity time profiles of different proton channels from the WIND 3DP, ACE/EPAM, SOHO EPHIN and SOHO ERNE instrument for the November 1, 2004 solar energetic particle event (generated by SEPServer).

Figure 23 Spacecraft locations of ACE (blue symbol) and SOHO (purple symbol) during the November 1, 2004 solar energetic particle event (from <http://sscweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/>)

Figure 24 Energy spectra of protons in the energy range of a few tens of keV to above 100 MeV for the November 1, 2004 event.

Figure 25 Energy spectra of Helium in the energy range of a few MeV/nucleon to above 100 MeV/nucleon for the November 1, 2004 event measured by SOHO/ERNE, SOHO/EPHIN and ACE SIS.

The energy spectra of protons for the November 1, 2004 event (05:15 UT till 18:00 UT) measured by SOHO/ERNE and SOHO/EPHIN are shown in Figure 24. The agreement is relatively good over the entire common energy range of ERNE and EPHIN.

The corresponding energy spectra for ^4He measured by SOHO/ERNE, SOHO/EPHIN and ACE/SIS are shown in Figure 25. The agreement between all instruments is reasonable. The reality of the very fast fall of the proton and helium spectra of ERNE at highest energies must be treated with some care as mentioned in Section 4.1.1.

4.1.4 July 13/14, 2005 solar energetic particle event

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Figure 26 Intensity time profiles of different proton channels from the WIND 3DP, ACE/EPAM, SOHO EPHIN and SOHO ERNE instrument for the July 13/July 14, 2005 solar energetic particle event (generated by SEPServer).

Figure 27 Spacecraft locations of ACE (blue symbol), SOHO (purple symbol) and WIND (green symbol) during the July 2005 solar energetic particle event (<http://sscweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/>)

Figure 28 Energy spectra of protons in the energy range of a few tens of keV to above 100 MeV for the July 14, 2005 event.

Figure 29 Energy spectra of helium in the energy range of a few MeV/nucleon to above 100 MeV/nucleon for the July 14, 2005 event.

The energy spectra of protons for the November 1, 2004 event (05:15 UT till 18:00 UT) measured by SOHO/ERNE and SOHO/EPHIN are shown in Figure 28. The agreement is perfect over the entire common energy range of ERNE and EPHIN.

The corresponding energy spectra for ^4He measured by SOHO/ERNE, SOHO/EPHIN and ACE/SIS are shown in Figure 29. The agreement between all instruments is very good.

4.1.5 Detailed Comparison of SOHO/EPHIN and SOHO/ERNE data

In Figure 30 we compare the on the left panel the hourly averaged intensities of uncorrected (green curve) and corrected (red curve) SOHO EPHIN and ERNE (black curve) 4.3 to 7.8 MeV protons during the July 13, 2005 solar energetic particle event. While the uncorrected EPHIN data sets are contaminated strongly by electrons during the onset of the event the profile of the corrected proton intensities is in reasonable agreement with the time profile of the ERNE intensities. However we find that EPHIN gives lower intensities than ERNE. During the time of significant PHA corrections strong deviations

exist, which can be attributed to the low statistics of the PHA words. In order to quantify the difference between the two sensors we calculated the relative difference $(I_{\text{EPHIN}} - I_{\text{ERNE}})/(I_{\text{EPHIN}} + I_{\text{ERNE}}) * 50$ as shown in the right panel of Figure 30. From the figure it is evident that EPHIN determines an intensity that is about 30% smaller than ERNE. Also, although not shown here similar differences can be obtained for other energy channels. We conservatively conclude that ERNE and EPHIN agree within an uncertainty of less than 50%.

Figure 30 Comparison of hourly averaged intensities of 4.3 to 7.8 MeV protons as measured by the SOHO/ERNE (black curve) and the uncorrected (green curve) and corrected (red curve) of SOHO/EPHIN intensities during the July 13, 2005 event. The right panel shows the relative difference indicating that the intensities measured by both instruments differ by ~ 30%.

4.2 Comparison of ACE and WIND electron measurements

4.2.1 The February 18, 2000 event

Figure 31 displays from top to bottom the intensity time profiles of different electron energy channels of the WIND 3DP, ACE/EPAM LEFS and ACE/EPAM LEMS DE instruments. A solar energetic particle event was registered around 9:30 h of the day. The relative position of the spacecraft are shown in Figure 32. In order to compare the two ACE/EPAM instruments with the WIND 3DP sensor Figure 33 shows the energy spectra for different electron channels in the time period from ~9:30 h to 12:00 h for the sectors pointing to pitch angle 0 (from [RD 29]). The very good agreement of these measurements is obvious from the figure. We conclude that similarly to SOHO/ERNE and SOHO/EPHIN all three

instruments measure the same intensities within an uncertainty of less than 50%.
 However, in the following section it will be shown that the preevent background is of large importance.

©SEPServer

Figure 31 Intensity time profiles of different electron energy channels as measured by ACE/EPAM LEMS DE, ACE/EPAM LEFS and WIND 3DP on February 18, 2000 (generated by SEPServer).

Figure 32 Relative position of the ACE (blue symbol) and the WIND (green symbol) on February 18, 2000.

Figure 33 Electron energy spectra during the February 18, 2000 solar energetic particle event. Note the energy scale is given in eV. For details see text (from [RD 29]).

4.2.2 The January 2007 events

Figure 34 STEREO, ACE, SOHO, and WIND positions in January 2007

In January 2007 STEREO A and B, ACE, WIND and SOHO observed a number of solar energetic particle events. The spacecraft locations at that time for STEREO A, ACE, SOHO, and WIND are displayed in Figure 34. Figure 35 shows the intensity time profiles of 105 to 165 keV electrons measured by STEREO A (red curve) and B (blue curve) SEPT, and of 103 - 175 keV electrons measured by ACE EPAM LEFS (pink curve) and LEMS DE (green curve) for the energetic particle events on January 23 and 24. Both SEPT measurements agree with each other very well. It can be seen that the background intensities of SEPT are nearly two orders of magnitude lower than those of ACE EPAM LEFS and ACE EPAM LEMS DE. However, also the maximum intensity is lower for STEREO SEPT and ACE EPAM LEFS compared to ACE LEMS DE. In order to investigate the influence of the background, the pre-event background on Day 22 2007 was subtracted from all measurements. The resulting profiles are shown in Figure 36. Note that in Figure 36 the STEREO A and B as well as the ACE EPAM LEFS measurements have been multiplied by a factor of 1.3 in order to achieve a good agreement between the SEPT and ACE LEMS DE data sets.

STEREO SEPT LEVEL2 DATA - 10min - omni / ACE EPAM
Jan 22, 2007 00:00:00 - Jan 26, 2007 00:00:00

Figure 35 Intensity time profiles of energetic electrons as measured by STEREO A and B SEPT as well as by ACE EPAM LEFS 60 and DE during the January 2007 events.

STEREO SEPT LEVEL2 DATA – 10min – omni / ACE EPAM
 Jan 23, 2007 12:00:00 – Jan 24, 2007 12:00:00

Figure 36 Stereo A SEPT, STEREO B SEPT and ACE EPAM energetic electron intensity time profiles after subtracting the pre event background as measured on January 22.

Figure 37 SOHO/EPHIN electron observations during the January 2007 events.

In comparison to Figure 35 Figure 37 displays the SOHO EPHIN intensities measured between 250 to 700 keV. Although not directly comparable, the SOHO intensities are lower than the one measured by ACE and STEREO as expected.

4.2.3 The May 2007 events

Figure 38 Spacecraft position of STEREO A and B, ACE, WIND and SOHO in May 2007

In what follows we compare ACE/EPAM, STEREO A and STEREO B SEPT as well as SOHO/ERNE, SOHO/EPHIN, STEREO A and B LET with each other.

4.2.3.1 Electron observations

Figure 39 Comparison of STEREO A SEPT, STEREO B SEPT, ACE EPAM LEFS and ACE EPAM LEMS DE electron measurements.

A second period of solar electron events was observed in May 2007. The intensity time profiles of energetic electrons are displayed in Figure 39. As for the January 2007 period the figure clearly shows the necessity to correct the profiles for the prevent background. The result of this procedure is displayed in Figure 40. In contrast to the time period in January no agreement between the two ACE channels can be found. We conclude that ACE and STEREO SEPT are measuring the same intensities within an uncertainty of less than 50%.

Figure 40 Same data as in Figure 39 but corrected for the prevent background and ACE LEFS and STEREO A and B multiplied by 1.3.

4.2.3.2 Proton measurements

SOHO/ERNE, SOHO/EPHIN and STEREO A and B LET also registered this event in their proton and helium channels. Figure 41 and Figure 42 display the energy spectra during the event. From those figures it is evident that the four instruments agree very well with each other. The upper limit for the differences in the intensities is found to be of the order of 30%. During this very small SEP event, the bumps in the proton and helium energy spectra of ERNE are very prominent in Figure 41 and Figure 42. The bump in the proton spectrum may partly be due to the background caused by penetrating galactic cosmic rays. For more details see [AD 9].

Figure 41 Proton energy spectra during the May 19, 2007 event.

Figure 42 Helium energy spectra during the May 19, 2007 event.

4.3 Comparison of STEREO/SEPT, STEREO/LET, ACE/EPAM, SOHO/ERNE and SOHO/EPHIN ions during the January 2007 CIR event.

Recurrent energetic particle events are caused by Corotating Interaction Regions (see e.g. [RD 11]) and represent energetic particle events observed in correlation with the forward and reverse wave (shock) of a fast and recurrent solar wind stream interacting with the ambient slow solar wind. At the end of January 2007 such an event was observed by all four spacecraft close to Earth. Figure 43 displays the intensity time profiles of 2.2 – 6.5 MeV protons measured aboard the STEREO spacecraft. Note that the spikes seen in the STEREO B time profile are caused by upstream events from the Earth magnetosphere. Although that time period is unique to calibrate all instruments at 1 AU to each other, not all instruments are measuring in the same energy range. Figure 44 summarizes the energy spectra measured from January 29, 18:00h to January 29, 24:00 h UT. From that figure we find a good agreement between all instruments.

Figure 43 Intensity time profile of 2.2 – 6.5 MeV protons during a Corotating Interaction ion event in January/February 2007

Figure 44 Energy spectra of protons during the January 2007 recurrent energetic particle event.

4.4 SOHO/ERNE, ACE/SIS, and ACE/CRIS heavy ion data

A comparison was carried out for the energy spectra of carbon and oxygen measured by SOHO and ACE for four time periods. To cover a wider energy range, also data from ACE/CRIS was used for comparison although ACE/CRIS data are not provided for SEP Server. The time periods selected were November 12-17, 1997, May 26-31, 1999, October 31-November 5, 2004, and July 13-18, 2005. These time periods cover the solar energetic particle events discussed in Sections 4.1.1 to 4.1.4, but longer time periods were used to increase the statistics, which still in some cases remained poor. The intensities were lowest for the November 1997 time period and highest for the July 2005 period. Representative results are presented in Figure 45 - Figure 48. For the November 1997 and October 2004 time periods the energy spectra for carbon are shown. The oxygen spectra are from the time periods May 1999 and July 2005. For each of the species and time period for which the results are not presented, the spectra have similar behaviour.

Figure 45. Carbon spectra measured by SOHO/ERNE and ACE/SIS and ACE/CRIS in November 1997.

Figure 46. Oxygen spectra measured by SOHO/ERNE and ACE/SIS and ACE/CRIS in May 1999.

Figure 47. Carbon spectra measured by SOHO/ERNE and ACE/SIS and ACE/CRIS in October-November 2004.

Figure 48. Oxygen spectra measured by SOHO/ERNE and ACE/SIS and ACE/CRIS in July 2005.

For all time periods investigated the carbon and oxygen spectra of ERNE, SIS, and CRIS match each other reasonably well, although at some energies there are also significant differences. There seems to be a trend that the higher the statistics, the better the agreement between various instruments. Generally the carbon intensities measured by ERNE roughly at energies 70-100 MeV/nucleon are higher than those of CRIS, while the last energy point of ERNE is lower. As for the proton and helium spectra (see Section 4.1.1 and Section 4.1.3), the reason for the low intensity at the highest energy may be an overestimation of the geometric factor of the instrument [AD 9]. For oxygen there is a clear trend that the intensities measured by ERNE at ~30 MeV/nucleon (the first energy channel of ERNE/HED) and at ~160 MeV/nucleon (the last energy channel of ERNE/HED) are lower than those of ACE/CRIS. The user has to be aware of these discrepancies.

5 Summary

We have briefly described in this document the missions and instruments from which solar energetic particle data and supplementary data of interplanetary magnetic field and solar wind have been provided for SEP Server. Each of the instruments, their functional

characteristics, data quality, and known caveats are described in more detail in separate documents [AD 3] – [AD 13].

A significant part of this document is the comparison of data from various instruments. While the comparison of the measurements is done in this document, the explanations for the reasons of possible significant discrepancies between instruments, when the discrepancies are thought to be due to the characteristics of a specific instrument, are included in the corresponding instrument Data Delivery Report.

Proton and helium observations in four solar energetic particle events by various instruments close to 1 AU were compared in Section 4.1. The selection included different sizes of events. Intensity-time profiles of protons for WIND/3DP, ACE/EPAM, SOHO/EPHIN and SOHO/ERNE were presented to demonstrate that all four instruments were able to record the events. The energy spectra of protons from ACE/EPAM, SOHO/EPHIN and SOHO/ERNE covered an energy range of more than three orders of magnitude (~ 70 keV - >100 MeV), while the energy spectra of helium from ACE/SIS, SOHO/EPHIN and SOHO/ERNE extended over roughly two orders of magnitude (~ 1 MeV/nucleon – 100 MeV/nucleon). In all cases the agreement between different instruments was reasonably good taking into account the slightly different locations of the spacecraft. However, a rapid fall of the proton and helium spectra measured by SOHO/ERNE was observed at the highest energies ($\gtrsim 80$ MeV/nucleon), which cannot be readily explained.

A detailed comparison of SOHO/EPHIN and SOHO/ERNE low-energy (4.3-7.8 MeV) proton intensities during the July 13, 2005 SEP event revealed an electron contamination in the SOHO/EPHIN proton data at the onset of the event. The SOHO/ERNE detectors have considerably higher detection thresholds than SOHO/EPHIN and are therefore not affected by electrons. A correction method was developed to remove the contamination from SOHO/EPHIN intensities and an agreement within an uncertainty of less than 50% was found for these two instruments.

The agreement of the proton and helium spectra of SOHO/EPHIN, SOHO/ERNE, and STEREO A and B LET was found to be very good during the small SEP event of May 19, 2007 (Section 4.2.3.2). Similarly, for the recurrent energetic particle event of January 2007 the protons measurements of STEREO/SEPT, STEREO/LET, ACE/EPAM, SOHO/EPHIN, and SOHO/ERNE were in good agreement (Section 4.3). In both of these low-intensity (at high energies) events the galactic cosmic ray background and the rapid fall of intensities at the highest energies measured by SOHO/ERNE are very prominent due to absence of high-energy solar particles.

Electron measurements of ACE/EPAM and WIND/3DP were compared for the SEP event of February 18, 2000, and those of STEREO A and B/SEPT and ACE/EPAM for the SEP events of January and May 2007 in Section 4.2. While the agreement of the electron energy spectra of WIND/3DP and ACE/EPAM was found to be very good, it was shown that the pre-event background was of great importance and has to be subtracted from the measurements.

Heavy ion measurements of ACE/SIS and SOHO/ERNE were compared in Section 4.4. In addition, ACE/CRIS heavy ion data were included at high energies, although ACE/CRIS data have not been delivered for SEPServer. The same events as used for proton and helium spectral comparisons were used. For all time periods investigated the overall carbon and oxygen spectra of SOHO/ERNE, ACE/SIS, and ACE/CRIS match each other reasonably well. However, both carbon and oxygen intensities at the highest energy channels of SOHO/ERNE were lower than those of ACE/CRIS indicating a similar behavior of rapid fall of the energy spectra as found for protons and helium.

Various instrument characteristics possibly affecting the data quality of specific instruments are discussed in more detail in the individual Data Delivery Reports [AD 3] – [AD 13].

**In the following are included the
Data Delivery Reports
of
each individual instrument
listed as AD3 – AD13 in Section 1.2 of this document.**

SEPServer

Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report HELIOS E6 Instrument description and data quality

	Name	Signature	Date
Prepared by	B. Heber		31.8.2013
Checked by	A. Papaioannou		31.8.2013
Approved by	R. Vainio		

DISTRIBUTION

Name	Organisation

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Summary and Recommendation

This document contains the Data Delivery Report (DDR) of the HELIOS E6 Experiment for the SEPServer database server.

The DDR can be subdivided into the following components:

1. Description of the E6 instrumentation
2. Data delivered
3. Data caveats and quality assessment for the E6 instrument data set

The Experiment E6 aboard the HELIOS spacecraft measures electrons in the energy range from a few hundred of keV to several MeV as well as ions from a few MeV/Nucleon to a few hundred MeV/Nucleon in different energy channels. Utilizing the (dE/dx – C) method such energy coverage could be achieved with a stack of five silicon detectors and one Saphirre detector. Since the first detector has a width of 0.1 mm only, minimum-ionizing particles cannot be registered, leading to misidentification of electrons and protons. The data delivered to SEPServer have not been corrected for this effect, thus the user should always compare intensity and anisotropy time profiles of both electron and proton channel with the same range in the detector stack. There are several flags given in the data set that reflect the status of the electronics (temperature effects as well as pre counter overflows). To be sure that the data are of high quality these flags should be nominal. If not the user is recommended to contact the investigator via the SEPServer page. A major issue of the HELIOS data is the highly variable accumulation period of the instrument frame. The user should be warned against other sources of data than the SEPServer page, because a fixed accumulation period can only be achieved by several assumptions. The data provided here are generated from the raw data without such assumptions.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document contains the Data Delivery Report (DDR) of the HELIOS E6 Experiment for the SEPServer database server.

The DDR can be subdivided into the following components:

1. Description of the E6 instrumentation
2. Data delivered
3. Data caveats and quality assessment for the E6 instrument data set

Each class of requirements will be detailed in a section of the document.

1.2 Applicable documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
AD1	Description of Work	EC-GA #262773, Annex I	10 Dec 2010
AD2	SEP Server SEP Data Delivery Plan	SEPSERVER-009-CAU-WP2	02 Oct 2012
AD3	SEP Server Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: Spacecraft descriptions and data comparison	SEPSERVER-010-00-CAU-WP2	31.Aug.2013

1.3 Reference documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
Kunow et al. (1975)	The Kiel University experiment E6 for measuring cosmic radiation between 1.0 and 0.3 AU	H. Kunow, et al.: Raumfahrtforschung, 19:253-258, Oct. 1975.	
Kunow et al. (1977)	Cosmic ray measurements on-board HELIOS 1 from December 1974 to September 1975: Quiet time spectra, radial gradients, and solar events	H. Kunow, et al.: Journal of Geophysics Zeitschrift für Geophysik, 42:615-631, 1977.	
Kunow et al. (1972)	Das Kieler Experiment zur Untersuchung der kosmischen Strahlung an Bord der Sonden HELIOS	H. Kunow et al.: Atomkernenergie 20, 193, 1972.	
Kunow et al. (1974)	HELIOS Experiment 6 (description in tables)	H. Kunow et al.: BMFT-FB-W 74-6, 113, 1974.	
Schulze et al. (1974)	The Influence of Finite Injection Periods on Anisotropies during Solar Particle Events	B.-M. Schulze et al.: BMFT-FB-W 74-8, 143, 1974.	
Reinhard and Wibberenz (1974)	Propagation of Solar Flare Protons in the Corona	R. Reinhard and G. Wibberenz: Solar Physics 36, 473-494, 1974.	
Brunstein (1964)	Measurement of Low-Energy Cosmic Ray Protons	K.A. Brunstein: Phys. Rev. 133, B 1520-1525, 1964.	

McDonald and Ludwig (1964)	Measurement of Low-Energy Primary Cosmic Ray Protons on IMP-1 Satellite	F.B. McDonald and G.H. Ludwig: Phys. Rev. Let. 13, 783-785, 1964.
Stone (1975)	Methods for the Determination of Z and M Using dE/dx, Cerenkov and Total Energy Measurements	E.C. Stone, in: Research Goals for Cosmic Ray Astrophysics in the 1980's. ESRO SP-109, 63-70, 1975.
Rossi (1956)	High Energy Particles	B. Rossi: Prentice Hall, Englewood Cliffs NJ, 1952.
Linsley (1955)	Measurements of Multiply Charged Cosmic Rays by a New Technique	J. Linsley: Phys. Rev. 97, 1292-1302, 1955.
Reinhard (1970)	Voruntersuchungen für ein Teilchenexperiment an Bord der Sonden HELIOS	R. Reinhard: Diplomarbeit, Universität Kiel, 1970.
Jepsen (1978)	Ansprechverhalten des Experiments 6 an Bord von HELIOS A und B auf Protonen der kosmischen Strahlung mit Energien größer als 51 MeV	U. Jepsen: Diplomarbeit, Universität Kiel, 1978.
Coleman et al., (1968)	Effects of Damage by 0.8 – 5.0 MeV Protons in Silicon Surface Barrier Detectors	J.A. Coleman et al.: IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci., NS-15 No.3, 363-372, 1968.
Iwers (1975)	Energieeichung und Bestimmung des Auflösungsvermögens des HELIOS-Experiments 6 am	B. Iwers: Diplomarbeit, Universität Kiel, 1976.

<p>Witte (1978)</p>	<p>hamburger Isochron Zyklotron UNTERSUCHUNG DES Langzeitverhaltens der Kieler Messinstrumente an Bord der Raumsonden HELIOS 1 und HELIOS 2</p>	<p>M. Witte: 2. Report IFKKI 78/1, Universität Kiel, 1978.</p>
<p>Green (1971)</p>	<p>Die adaptive Messwerterfassung bei einem Experiment zur Messung der kosmischen Strahlung an Bord der interplanetaren Sonde HELIOS</p>	<p>G. Green: Dissertation, Universität Kiel, 1971.</p>
<p>Steinbuch (1962)</p>	<p>Taschenbuch der Nachrichtenverarbeitung</p>	<p>K. Steinbuch: Berlin, 1962.</p>
<p>Green et al., (1970)</p>	<p>An Adaptive Data Compression Method for a Cosmic Ray Experiment on Board a Space Probe</p>	<p>G. Green et al.: Nucl. Instr. Meth. 86, 213-216, 1970.</p>

1.4 Abbreviations and acronyms

ADC	Analog-to-Digital Converter
DC	Direct Current
DDR	Data Delivery Report
DFVLR	Deutsche Forschungs- und Versuchsanstalt für Luft- und Raumfahrt
E6	Experiment No. 6
EDR	Experiment Data Record
GSOC	German Space Operations Center
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
CSA	Charge sensitive amplifier
HV	High Voltage
FET	Field-Effect Transistor
PHA	Pulse height analysis

2 HELIOS A/B E6 Instrument Description

The HELIOS A/B experiment, addressed to measure cosmic rays in the inner solar system, has been developed between 1967 and 1974 at the Institute for Pure and Applied Nuclear Physics. Thus, continuous studies of the solar and galactic radiation from the ground to the interplanetary space, using balloons, rockets and satellites, was possible. Information about acceleration processes on the Sun and in interplanetary space, as well as transport processes of particles in the interplanetary space were collected by measuring energy spectra, intensity-time profiles and anisotropies of electrons, protons and heavy atomic nuclei in the inner solar system. With the help of these data, the existing models on acceleration, propagation and modulation could, and still can, either be validated and improved.

2.1 Scientific goal

With the HELIOS experiment No. 6 (E6) high-energy charged particles of the cosmic radiation were measured, in particular atomic nuclei with energies above 1.3 MeV/Nucleon and electrons above 0.3 MeV (Kunow et al., 1972, Kunow et. al., 1974). Although many citations are outdated here, they have been kept in order to understand the development of the E6 experiment as it was produced in the 1960's and 1970's. For recent reviews please refer to the DDR on particle propagation [?? To be given by WP 4]:

- ✓ Galactic cosmic rays are produced far beyond our solar system and enter the interplanetary space against the barrier of the solar magnetic field, which is carried outwards with the solar wind. The shielding effect of the solar system depends on the solar activity and varies with energy and type of the particles. The galactic cosmic radiation mainly consists of protons with the peak of the energy spectrum around several hundred MeV, albeit nearly all chemical elements are present.
- ✓ The solar cosmic radiation is primarily produced during big flares and coronal mass ejections (CMEs). Electrons and atomic nuclei of the coronal plasma are being strongly accelerated and spread out in the corona over a large part of the Sun's surface

depending on the ambient magnetic field structures. The particles leave the solar atmosphere along the magnetic field lines, which reach out into the interplanetary space (Schulze et al., 1974; Reinhard et al., 1974, Reames, 2013). The intensities of the solar cosmic radiation can exceed the galactic intensity in significant amounts. But there are also very small events whose structures and connections to solar processes can be studied particularly well when approaching the Sun (Kunow et al., 1977a).

- ✓ Jovian electrons are also being observed in interplanetary space. They leak out of Jupiter's radiation belt and fill out large parts of interplanetary space.
- ✓ Interplanetary (heliospheric) particles are particles (protons, some heavier atomic nuclei) which already exist in interplanetary space (the heliosphere) and are accelerated by interplanetary (heliospheric) shocks, corotating interaction regions or other mechanisms.

For the study of the described phenomena, the measuring instrument on board of the probes provided intensity-time-profiles and angular distributions for different energies as well as energy spectra for each particle species. The measured energy spectra as function of the spacecrafts position also allows to determine spatial gradients. The ability to distinguish between different species in addition allows to measure the chemical, for helium even the isotopic composition.

2.2 Instrument Description

The energy range of the E6 extends from 3.3 MeV/Nucleon to > 1000 MeV/Nucleon for nuclei and from approximately 0.3 to 8 MeV for electrons. The on-board data processing system evaluated the measured pulses created during the particle transition and carried out a highly effective redundancy reduction before formatting the data and passing it on for transmission to Earth.

The detector telescope consisted of five solid-state detectors, one Sapphire-Cerenkov-detector and one anti-coincidence plastic scintillator (Figure 1). The opening cone of 55° thereby was the same for all energy ranges. But the geometrical factor, the product of solid

angle and detector surface, is lower by a factor of five for particles below 48 MeV/Nucleon because for these particles the response of the detectors 1 and 2, which are of a smaller diameter, is demanded. The detector system will be thoroughly described in section 2.5.

Figure 1 Sketch of the detector telescope of the HELIOS experiment E6

The on-board data-processing system initially had the task of amplifying, shaping and measuring the pulses emitted by the detectors. The digital data processing selected those events, which are of physical interest, and counts them. Moreover, a few events were selected for which the information from the detector signals was analyzed with high precision. The counting rate information and detailed information on the signal amplitude (pulse height words) were then compiled into an experiment-data-frame (formatted), after a very effective data reduction on board, which allowed an automatic adaptation to a large

dynamic range of the incident particle flux. The functions of the analogous and digital data processing will be discussed more precisely in section 2.7.

2.3 Principles of Measurement

The registration of charged particles in the sensor material is based on their ability to ionize matter and to generate Cerenkov light.

The ionization was detected in two ways:

1. In the semiconductor detector, holes and electrons, which were released from the atoms of the medium by the primary ionization, were dragged towards the electrodes by an electric field applied to the detector. The energy deposit in the detector caused by ionization can be quantitatively determined after an appropriate charge integration and subsequent amplification.
2. As an effect of the ionization, a light emission was stimulated in the scintillation counter by the primary charged particle. This was observed with a photomultiplier. The resulting current pulse was then amplified and measured to determine the energy deposit.

In the Cerenkov detector, particles with a speed above the speed of light in the Cerenkov material generate a light pulse (Cerenkov effect). The resulting light is detected by a photomultiplier, as in the case of the scintillation counter.

The function of the measuring instrument, depicted in Figure 1 was to determine energy, charge and mass of each individual charged particle that penetrates the sensor within the opening angle. Sections 2.3.1 and 2.3.2 basically explain the measuring principles.

2.3.1 $dE / dx - E -$ Technique

The $dE / dx - E -$ method for the determination of energy, charge and mass is used for particles which stopped in one of the five semiconductor-detectors, a method developed by Brunnstein (1964), McDonald and Ludwig (1964) and Stone, (1975). The principle of this method shall be explained by means of Figure 2.

Figure 2 Exemplary particle trajectory in a dE/dx -E-telescope

A charged particle with the energy E_0 penetrates the thin first detector D1 and stops in the thick detector D2. In the first detector, with a thickness of Δx , the particle loses the energy ΔE due to ionization given by:

$$\Delta E \approx \frac{dE_0}{dx} \cdot \Delta x \quad (1)$$

E' is deposited in the second detector. The entire kinetic energy E_0 results from the sum $\Delta E + E'$, the energy losses in both detectors. From the Bethe-Bloch-relation (e.g. Rossi, 1956), the energy loss in both detectors can be determined for a known detector-material and for particles of a known species. For non-relativistic heavy particles the equation reduces to:

$$\frac{dE_0}{dx} \propto \frac{Z^2}{V^2} \quad (2)$$

with Z and V the charge and velocity of the particle. If $\Delta E = dE / dx \cdot \Delta x \ll E'$ (meaning very small against the remaining energy), one can approximately replace E' with the incidence energy E_0 . For non-relativistic particles of mass M is:

$$E_0 = \frac{1}{2}MV^2 \quad (3)$$

From (2) and (3) then follows

$$\Delta E \cdot E_0 \propto Z^2 \cdot M \quad (4)$$

This constitutes a typical quantity for a particle-species. Since Z and M can only take on discrete values, the relation (4) offers a possibility to separate various particles and, in addition to the energy, to determine mass and charge.

2.3.2 The dE/dx-Cerenkov-method

Charged particles, which completely penetrate the semiconductor detectors, can be studied with the help of the Cerenkov detector C, which is placed underneath the semiconductor detectors. The use of a different detector is necessary since with energy-loss measurements alone, the energy determination is only possible in a narrow energy range above the maximum energy for stopping particles. Linsley (1955) was the first to introduce the dE/dx-Cerenkov method, while McDonald (1956) was the first to describe the necessary instrument. The principle is explained by means of Figure 3. A fast particle penetrates a semiconductor detector D and a Cerenkov detector C with a speed of $\beta > \beta_m$, with $\beta_m = c/n$ being the speed of light in the Cerenkov detector where n is the refraction index of the Cerenkov material. The energy loss in the semiconductor detector was already presented above.

Figure 3 Sketch of a particle trajectory in a dE/dx-C-telescope

The number of emitted quanta ΔN per travel distance Δx is:

$$\frac{\Delta N}{\Delta x} = K \cdot Z^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta^2 \cdot n^2} \right) \quad (7)$$

Plotting the “energy-loss by the Cerenkov effect”, ΔN , against the energy-loss by ionization, ΔE , in a first approximation results in straight lines with negative slopes depending on the speed of the particles, which can clearly be separated for different atomic numbers. So, the dE / dx – Cherenkov – method allows an identification of the penetrating particles in terms of charge and an energy-determination for energies above a minimum-energy. ΔN can be approximated by:

$$\Delta N = -AZ^2 - B\Delta E \quad (8)$$

with A and B being constants. As with the dE / dx – E – method, the resolution in the presented experiment is improved by using two energy-loss-measurements.

2.4 Design Criteria for the Sensor System

The instrument was designed to measure electrons, protons and heavier atomic nuclei up to oxygen for solar and galactic cosmic radiation. A separation of the isotopes of hydrogen and helium is possible with the resolution required for the charge separation. The separation of electrons, protons and heavier nuclei should be possible by means of simple electronic thresholds. An anti-coincidence-detector was necessary for the determination of angular distributions as well as for the reduction of the background by laterally incident particles. For the study of solar energetic particle events, during which intensities, which are so high, frequently emerge, that a saturation of the instruments has to be feared, the lower energy ranges between 1 and 50 MeV/Nucleon are measured with a smaller geometry factor than the energy range above 50 MeV/Nucleon.

A pure semiconductor-detector-telescope is not suitable for the study of galactic cosmic radiation because of the minor change of energy loss and the restrictedly accessible active layer thickness. That is why an additional Cerenkov-detector was included in the telescope, which delivered distinctively different pulse amplitudes in the energy range above 200 MeV/Nucleon up to approximately 1 GeV/Nucleon.

An additional criterion for the design of the detector system was the necessity to work in near-Sun environment even in the case of very high insolation and strongly varying temperatures.

2.5 Description of the Detector Telescope

The detector system consisted of five semiconductor detectors of increasing thickness as shown in Figure 4. The figure also displays the areas and thicknesses of the detectors. Detectors 1 and 2 are silicon-surface-barrier detectors by Philips, Eindhoven. They were used for the determination of the lowest energy channels, for the definition of the geometry factor for energy ranges below 51 MeV/Nucleon as well as for the discrimination between electrons and nuclei. Since detector 1 could not respond to relativistic particles due to a thickness of 100 μm , a trigger threshold of 150 keV and the fact that electrons above 300 keV are already relativistic particles, the discrimination between electrons and nuclei is that detector 1 must not be triggered for electrons. To avoid false identifications by these discrimination conditions, detectors 1 and 2 have been placed as close as possible on top

Abb. 2.3.-1.: Schematische Darstellung des Detektorsystems

Figure 4 Schematic depiction of the detector system

of each other.

Detectors 3 - 5 are 3 mm thick lithium drifted silicon-detectors with an active area of 1250 mm². The thickness grading from 0.1 over 1 to 3 mm allowed a division of the energy range for nuclei between 1.3 and 51 MeV/N in smaller intervals, which at least roughly exhibit comparable count rates during solar events.

Charged particles, which penetrated detector 5 and the aluminum absorber below of 0.5 mm thickness, were detected in the Sapphire-Cerenkov-detector. The Cerenkov-threshold for this material ($n=1.8$) is at $E_S = 210$ MeV/Nucleon. But the Sapphire-Cerenkov-detector is not a pure Cerenkov-detector. It also delivered scintillation light, so that there was another leftover energy measurement available for particles in the energy range 51 MeV/Nucleon to 80 MeV/Nucleon (see also Section 2.3.2; the dE/dx -E-method). Between 80 MeV/Nucleon and 210 MeV/Nucleon, the sapphire crystal delivered scintillation light proportional to the ionization energy loss of penetrating particles. Reinhard (1970) studied these effects. The light output of the Cerenkov-detector as a function of the particle energy is graphically depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Light yield of the Sapphire-Cerenkov-detector as a function of energy

Therewith it is possible to divide the energy range of 51 – 400 MeV/Nucleon into smaller energy intervals for the determination of a spectrum (Jepsen, 1978). Above 400 MeV/Nucleon, only integral measurements are possible.

The Cerenkov-detector, with a thickness of 10 mm and a diameter of 7.5 cm, consisted of synthetic sapphire that was implemented as a window of a photomultiplier of type C 31012 by the company RCA. Since the Cerenkov-light is emitted directionally, due to the bidirectional symmetry of the opening cone it was possible to receive different pulse heights depending on the arrival direction of a particle. The signal of a high-energy particle which penetrates the telescope 'from behind' was weakened so much by the necessary multiple reflection and the self-absorption that it could mimic a low-energy particle penetrating from the 'front'. To avoid false identifications of the measured data by particles penetrating from 'behind', the surfaces of the sapphire, which was turned towards the semiconductor-detectors, was coated with light-absorbing black paint. Thus, the amplitude of the Cerenkov-signal of particles, which penetrated the telescope from 'behind' was reduced to approximately 15 % and could be distinguished from regularly measured data. Simultaneously, the light generated by ionization was reduced by approximately 50 %, independently of the direction of incidence (Reinhard, 1970).

In addition an anti-coincidence scintillator made of Nuplex 4 surrounded the detector-telescope in order to reduce the background of faulty events and to define the opening cone. The anti-coincidence ring had an average responsiveness of 200 keV and was read out by a photomultiplier of the company RCA, type C 7151 Q. The half opening cone of the telescope was 27.5°. For thermal reasons, and to achieve light tightness, additional absorbers were integrated in the ray path:

A quartz reflector of 16- μm thicknesses, which was coated with silver and aluminum on the backside, has been used as entrance foil. Since the quartz reflector has a residual transparency of approximately 1 %, an opaque nickel foil of 0.75 μm had to be installed in the ray path directly in front of detector 1. Additional light protection was achieved by mounting detector 1 with the aluminum side in the direction of the entrance and further

evaporating it with $120 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ aluminum and $40 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ nickel. As a result of this, a good protection from radiation damage was obtained (Coleman et al., 1968). The Cerenkov detector, whose photomultiplier can register extremely weak light signals, was decoupled optically from the remaining detector system by an aluminum absorber of 0.5 mm thickness. The absorber materials in the ray path determined the minimal verification energy for the different particles in the telescope (e.g. Iwers, 1975). Protons with an energy of 1.3 MeV for HELIOS A and 1.7 MeV for HELIOS B were found to be the lower trigger threshold. Table 1 summarizes the energy windows and the geometry factors the detectors used for a pulse height analysis as well as the number of sectors for HELIOS A and HELIOS B as function of the particle species. The acronyms have the following meanings: P stands for protons, A stands for alpha particles and particles with $Z > 2$, E stands for electrons. The subsequent number roughly indicates the lower boundary of the energy interval in MeV and MeV/Nucleon, respectively.

Table 1 Energy-intervals and geometry factors for the particle channels of E6 on HELIOS A and B.

Abbreviation	E (MeV) HELIOS A	E (MeV) HELIOS B	Geom. Factor ($\text{cm}^2 \text{sr}$) HELIOS A	Geom. Factor ($\text{cm}^2 \text{sr}$) HELIOS B	Detector s with PHA	Number of sectors
P1	1.3 – 3.8	1.7 – 3.7	0.48	0.43	-	8
P4	3.8 – 12.8	3.7 – 12.7	0.48	0.43	1, 2	8
P13	12.8 – 26.8	12.7 – 27.4	0.48	0.43	1, 1, 3	8
P27	26.8 – 36.6	27.4 – 37.3	0.48	0.43	2, 3, 4	8
P37	36.6 – 50.7	37.3 – 51.0	0.48	0.43	3, 4, 5	1
P51	> 50.7	> 51.0	2.23	2.23	4, 5, C	8
A2	1.7 – 3.7	2.0 – 3.6	0.48	0.43	-	8

A4	3.7 – 12.7	3.6 – 12.6	0.48	0.43	1, 2	8
A13	12.7 – 26.6	12.6 – 27.2	0.48	0.43	1, 2, 3	8
A27	26.6 – 36.5	27.2 – 37.2	0.48	0.43	2, 3, 4	1
A37	36.5 – 48.1	37.2 – 48.3	0.48	0.43	3, 4, 5	1
A48	> 48.1	> 48.3	2.23	2.23	4, 5, C	1
E0.3	≥ 0.3	≥ 0.3	0.49	0.46	-	8
E0.8	≥ 0.8	≥ 0.8	0.49	0.46	2, 3	8
E2	≥ 2.0	≥ 2.0	0.49	0.46	2, 3, 4	1
E3	≥ 3.0	≥ 3.0	0.49	0.46	3, 4, 5*	1

* only HELIOS A

2.6 Selection of the Detectors

Both the semiconductor detectors and the photomultipliers underwent very extensive tests, especially performance tests at constant room temperature, before they were assembled in the flight units. This included: mechanical examination of thicknesses and areas, optical examination of the surfaces, recording of the current-voltage as well as the voltage-capacity characteristics. The resolving power was measured with test pulses and different radioactive sources during irradiation through the front and backside for different voltages and for different time constants. Thereby, an optimal operating point for each detector was determined and a preliminary quality specified. All the detectors, which met the requirements in the performance tests, were afterwards long-term tested in thermal vacuum (pressure $\approx 10^{-8}$ Torr, temperatures T: -40° to $+35^{\circ}$) for at least 4 – 8 weeks. This way a resolution (full width half maximum) better than 30 keV at 20°C and of better than 45 keV in the channels 3 – 5 was reached. The photomultipliers were extensively examined in

terms of their amplifier-voltage characteristics, quantum efficiency, uniformity of the photocathode and stability.

2.7 Sensor Mechanics and thermal Arrangements

The sensor box (Figure 10) contained the sensor-system as well as the required voltage supplies for semiconductor detectors and photomultipliers and one charge-sensitive preamplifier for each semiconductor detector and for each photomultiplier. The individual elements were attached to a baseplate as blocks, which ensure a good thermal contact to the spacecraft. In order to reduce the heat input, the entrance window featured a quartz reflector and a collimator that was covered with second-surface mirror material. Good heat contacts were established with heat-sink pastes to ensure good heat dissipation from the detectors to the baseplate. The baseplate has had a contact area of approximately 20 cm² with the spacecraft, which was, for electric insulation, equipped with beryllium-oxide plates and heat-sink paste with a very small thermal resistance.

Figure 6 Block diagram of the HELIOS-experiment No. 6

2.7.1 System Description

The analogue electronics has the task of processing the charge pulses, which are produced in the detectors, in a way that all events are counted, classified by event type and randomly submitted to a detailed pulse height analysis.

Figure 6 shows the block diagram of the instrument. The analogue electronics is depicted in the upper part. The signals emitted by the seven detectors were further processed in identically designed channels; corresponding dimensioning of the electronic components was made to adjust to the different energy ranges.

The electronics of each channel consists of a charge sensitive amplifier (CSA), a pulse shaper, a linear amplifier and a discriminator. Additionally, three analogue-to-digital converters, each with one 4-channel multiplexer (linear gates), were built in. For testing the electronics during flight there was an inflight test generator, with which all signal paths could be stimulated.

The analogue electronics described here was distributed on both experiment boxes, i.e. sensor box E6A and electronics box E6B, the signal interface is between CSA and the pulse shaper. Hence the sensor unit contained CSA, the inflight test generator and the high-voltage supply for the detectors. This arrangement had the following advantages:

1. The connecting cables between detectors and CSA inputs were short, thus minimizing the capacitive noise component the analogue signals which were to be transferred from box to box can be amplified to a sufficiently high level with appropriately dimensioned amplifiers
2. The high voltages did not have to be carried over long, pluggable wirings, thus the inflight test pulses were carried over short wires to the CSAs
3. The control signals were digital

The connection between CSAs and pulse shapers consisted of seven coaxial cables, which were led through a seven pole CANNON-D connector with coaxial inserts. The rest of the analogue electronics was located in the electronics box on a total of 10

daughterboards, pluggable wired over a motherboard.

2.7.2 Supply Voltages

The energy range which is to be linearly processed was defined with $q_{\max}/q_{\min} = 5000$ for all detectors. As for the respective analogue voltage for q_{\min} , we regarded 1 mV as realizable so that the signal range of the electronics, which was to be linearly processed, was between 0 and 5 V. Therefore, for the low-voltage power supply we required the following voltage rails: for the CSAs +20 V, for linear circuits +10 V and -5 V, and for the digital interfaces +5 V.

2.7.3 Signal Flux

The entire linear signal processing worked with unipolar positive pulses. The individual electronic assemblies from CSAs onwards were DC-coupled except for the x70 linear amplifiers. The linear voltage ranged from 1 mV to 4900 mV, which was to be processed, and was divided into two ranges of equal dynamics after the pulse shape, namely range 1 with 1 mV to 70 mV and range 2 with 70 mV to 4900 mV. The division happened in the linear amplifier complex (compare Figure 7a). The voltage range of 1 mV to 70 mV was transformed through amplification to the values of the upper range with 70 mV to 4900 mV. Due to this, the following devices (discriminators, linear delay lines) were adjusted to the relatively high-ohmic pulse shaper.

Because of the double track processing of the signals, the number of circuits increased, but the significantly smaller dynamic range led to lower demands for the devices and therefore a smaller total expense.

Originally it was planned to carry out the division into two ranges immediately after the pulse shaper. In this case, only an amplification factor of 1 is necessary for the upper channel.

In the course of the development it became obvious that in channel 1, which covers the lowest energy ranges, the longterm stability of the amplifier was not guaranteed due to the required high conversion factor in the CSA ($C15 < 1 \text{ pF}$).

Figure 7 Signal flux diagram for the linear data processing

So in the flight models the conversion factors in the CSA were reduced by a factor of 5, while retaining the overall amplification factor, but increased by a factor of 5 in the amplification part for the upper range. The signal for the lower part was branched off in this channel only after the 5-fold-amplifier (compare Figure 7 b). The linear data processing was made according to the schematic diagram (a) for nearly all channels. Only for channel 1 a setup according to schematic diagram (b) had to be chosen to increase the stability.

2.7.4 Circuit Description

2.7.4.1 Charge-Sensitive Amplifiers

Joined to the five semiconductor detectors and the two photomultipliers is a CSA.

The task of the CSAs is to make voltage-jumps from the current pulses of the semiconductor detectors and the photomultipliers in an amplitude range, which is both unified and well suited in amplitude for the following processing.

Their transmission factors is adjusted to the different charge ranges of the current pulse of interest. These ranges are listed next to the charge accumulation time t_s in Table 2.

Table 2 Dynamic ranges of the input signals

Detectors	t_s /nsec	q_{min} /pAsec	q_{max} /pAsec	q_{max}/q_{min}
HLD 1	50	0.004	20	5000
HLD 2	50	0.01	50	5000
HLD 3, 4, 5	400	0.02	100	5000
Cerenkov	20	0.03	150	5000
Anticonicidence	20	0.03	150	5000

The transmission factor is given by:

$$w = \Delta u / \Delta q = 2 \text{ mV}/q_{min} \quad (9)$$

Accordingly, the voltage jumps at the CSA-outputs are in a range of 2 mV to 10 V. They are positive and fall off with a time constant of $\tau = 35 \mu\text{s}$. Figure 8 shows the circuit diagram of the CSA for channel 1 while Figure 9 shows the component diagram.

The supply voltage for the detectors was led over the CSA-board (pin 1), where there was also the load resistor R03 located. Both, high voltage and signal were carried over the connecting cable between CSA and detectors. The capacitor C01 separated the high voltage from the CSA input. The components R12, C12, D11 and D12 constituted a voltage protection for the CSA. This setup was used for all detectors, i.e. channels 1 through 5.

The photomultipliers in channels A and C got their high voltage through separate HV-converters. In this case, the components were installed together with the photomultipliers, so the CSA boards were populated differently.

The resistor R02 lied as a shunt in the return of the detector. The voltage drop caused by the detector current delivered the housekeeping information "detector current".

The amplifier itself was built as a multi-stage amplifier with a FET-input stage. The circuit elements C15, 16, 17 and R15, 16, 17 determined the conversion factor and the decay time constant τ .

Being sensitive input stages, the CSAs are a main source of the electronically induced noise. By carefully choosing the input field effect transistors, the equivalent null noise was kept below $0.53 \cdot 10^{-15}$ As, equivalent to absorbed particle energies of 6 keV. (This value applied for overall channel 1 from CSA to ADC with a pulse rise time of approximately 350 ns at the ADC).

In channel 1 and 2, the FETs T1 and T7 got wired in parallel, which certainly increased the null noise, but the capacitive noise components due to the input capacitance (detector, cable, etc.) got smaller. Thus in total a better performace was achieved.

Figure 8 Circuit diagram of the charge-sensitive amplifier based on the example of channel 1

For channels 3 to 7, only T1 got equipped. The output stage of the CSA (T6, T5) was built in such a way that the following pulse shaper could be operated with $Z = 500 \Omega$. The d-c voltage part (offset) got separated by C22, since point 10 lies on positive potential thanks to the unipolar current supply of +20V.

Pin 8 was the test input for the inflight test generator. The amplification factor for this test signal could be adjusted with C04.

All seven CSA boards were designed identically. The assembly was carried out by the pile, whereupon specially constructed milling parts constituted both the exterior wall of the overall CSA box and the shielding walls between the CSAs. The connections of the CSAs were soldered.

The connections between the CSA outputs and pulse shapers in the electronics box consisted of seven coaxial cables, which led through a common CANNON-D connector with coaxial inserts. Those cables were not terminated with the wave resistance.

Figure 9 Component diagram of the charge-sensitive amplifier (channel 1)

The temporal resolution has been derived from the capabilities of the threshold discriminators, i.e. which minimal intervals between two events incident on the detector could be resolved as being separate events. Since the pulse lengths of the discriminators depended on amplitudes and further, since two discriminators have had to be watched due to the division of the energy range into two voltage ranges per channel, Table 3 can be used as an estimate for the resolution of a discriminator in the lower range, e.g. D10. Hence the linear signal processing could resolve

at q_{\min} approx. 600 kHz
 at q_{\max} approx. 24 kHz

Table 3 Time constants of the analog electronics

Input (mV)	Pulse length at discriminator output (μs)
3	1.4
10	2.0
100	7.0
500	22.0
1000	29.0
5000	41.0

The entire linear signal processing was built with a total of 18 boards of eight different types. The weight portion of the analogue electronics amounted to approximately 1 kg. The power demand of the entire analogue electronics was in the order of 1.5 W; the share of the circuits in the electronics box accounted for 1 W. The entire analogue electronics was fully functional in a temperature range from -40° C to +70° C.

3 Technical Data and Specific Features

3.1 Technical Interface

The interface of the HELIOS-experiment No. 6 to the probe is basically determined in the interface document No. IS 306.106 B and C. The most important technical data are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4 Characteristic numbers of the HELIOS E6 analog electronics

Mass	7.15 kg
Power input	4.49 W
Number of commands	12
Number of analog monitor channels	16
Number of digital monitor channels on board (8 bit)	8

3.2 Technological Specific Features

The instrument consists of two separate units, the sensor box and the electronics box (compare: Figure 10). The sensor box contained the detector telescope, the high-voltage supplies for the operation of photomultipliers and semiconductor detectors, the preamplifiers and the test generator. Further analogue and digital electronics were located in the electronics box. This included a 4-kbit core memory, which was needed for the collection of counting rates and pulse height words as well as output buffers for the data retrieval by the space probes.

Figure 10 Sensor and Electronic box of the HELIOS E6 Experiment

Although the instrument was located in the thermally well-isolated central body, special precautionary measures were required for the adherence to the maximal detector temperatures of $+30^{\circ}$ C. The aperture of the telescope was sealed by a $16\ \mu\text{m}$ thick spheric quartz foil that was evaporated with silver and gold on the backside. Thereby, a 'second surface mirror' was created with a ratio of absorption to emission of 0.05. Since the quartz mirror was not completely light tight, the semiconductor detectors have had to be protected from the sun by an additional nickel foil of $0.75\ \mu\text{m}$.

0.7 mm thick slices of BeO (Thermalox 995) and a surface coupling with heat-sink paste Dow Corning C-6-1102 were used for the conduction of the solar heat input to the mounting platform of the space probe while simultaneously meeting the requirement of being electrically insulated.

3.3 Course of the Mission

The instruments withstood the extreme strain of the precision-launch on the 10.12.1974 and the 15.01.1976 without any damage. Not until 38 hours after the launch was the instrument supplied with power to avoid arcing in the high voltage power supply in the

critical pressure range between 10^2 and 10^{-11} Torr. The automatic switch-on sequence immediately responded and commanded the instrument into the nominal configuration, as the check of the real-time data showed a few seconds later. The full functionality of the on-board electronics was controlled with the help of a built-in test-pulse generator. The uninterrupted flight control by the housekeeping-measurement posts of the instruments showed the desired low leakage current of the individual detectors and the expected high voltage level on the photomultipliers. Even the sensor part, which was especially temperature-sensitive, warmed up from -26°C at 1 AU to only $+24^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the first perihelion and therefore remained in the allowed range with a margin of 6°C to the critical upper temperature limit. In the meantime, the temperatures rose further with every subsequent perihelion-transition, so that by the end of the mission detector 1 exceeded the upper limit of $+30^{\circ}\text{C}$. Nevertheless, the detectors only showed very minor noise because of a substantially smaller degradation than expected (Witte, 1978). This means that the detectors absolutely fulfilled the requirements even when the temperatures were above 30°C . The evaluation of the mission data of both probes confirmed the very good, low-noise performance of the detectors, the high stability of the analog electronics as well as the flawless performance of the digital electronics. Although both spacecraft were built for a lifetime of about 18 month, they returned data for eleven and six years, respectively.

4 HELIOS A/B E6 Data sets

4.1 Data Frame

The on-board data acquisition and data processing of measuring data of the detector telescope was adjusted to the periodic operating cycle of the space probe telemetry system. Since the instrument could generally produce more data than the probes could transfer, it was important to utilize the capacity available by choosing and coding the measurements skillfully. It had to be taken into account that the total telemetry capacity fluctuated quite strongly (between 8 and 4095 bit/s) depending on transmission conditions,.

It proved to be convenient to use a relatively long experiment-data frame of 624 bits because frame synchronization and identification claim a smaller part of the bit rate than shorter frames. Each three successive frames 0, 1 and 2 constituted a complete experiment data cycle. They differ from each other in which one third of the overall 96 counter is contained. Each frame also contains a number of pulse height words, which deliver much more detailed information on each particle than the counters. The device adjusted to different particle intensities as well as to different data-transfer rates by choosing the part of the pulse height words: the larger sample of pulse height words was transferred the more the intensities decreased or the transfer bit rate increased (Green, 1971). In the sense of a bit-level-encoding, the frames were compiled as follows:

1 ... 9

Frame 0:

synchronization word 111010010, at the same time label for Experiment 6. The sync-words were chosen in a way that allows for a Hamming-distance as large as possible when it, including its neighboring bits, is shifted against itself (Steinbuch 1962).

Frame 1:

8 bit experiment-status register + 1 parity bit, together coded in a way

that makes them coincide with the synchronization word in the normal operating status of the instrument.

Frame 2:

sequence number modulo 512 of the experiment-data cycle, incremented at frame 0 but only shown here, two frames later.

10 ... 12	Number of the sector with which the last count rate read-in period ended.
13 ... 16	(18 – N), N = number of pulse height words transferred in this frame
17 ... 32	Duration of the count rate read-in period in eighth-sector passages.
32 ... (N+1)*32	N pulse height words of 32 bit length
(N+1)*32+1 ... 608	32 counter readings in compressed form (statistically insignificant digits suppressed following a square root compression procedure (Green et al., 1970))
609 ... 610	identification of the data frame (0, 1, 2)
611 ... 612	ditto (redundancy)
613 ... 616	as 13 ... 16 (redundancy)
617	1 bit indication of pre-counter overflows during the last count-rate-read-in period
618 ... 620	as 10 ... 12 (redundancy)
621 ... 624	as 13 ... 16 (redundancy)

The counter readings are accommodated in the bits of the data frames in the following order:

Bit mod 32	Frame 0	Frame 1	Frame 2
1 ... 8	A2	P1	P51

9 ... 16	A4	P13	P4
17 ... 24	A13	E03	n.s.d.
25 ... 32	P27	E08	n.s.d.

(n.s.d. = non sectorized data)

Within each frame, all 32 counter readings are brought to the length of the highest counter reading involved by prefixed zeros. Dependant on this length is the number of the pulse height words transferred in the frame. It fluctuates between a minimum of six and a maximum of 16. For this, the first 16 pulse height words recorded in each read-in period were stored on-board. After this, the instrument transitioned into a priority operation mode by overwriting the first six words by a maximum of six further words. These words, chosen deliberately from the particularly different coincidence types, could therefore be transmitted in any case. Every single pulse height word was composed as follows:

Bit	Content
1 – 6	coincidence type
7 - 13	pulse height 1 on a log. scale
14 – 20	pulse height 2 on a log. scale
21 – 27	pulse height 3 on a log. scale
28 – 30	Sector of view direction
31	0: normal operation mode 1: priority operation mode
32	Parity bit (odd)

Depending on the telemetry bit-rate, the HELIOS probes could send an Experiment 6 data frame every 4.5 to 864 seconds. The time resolution of the instrument was therefore

between 13.5 and 2592 seconds. During times where no ground station was available for the data reception, or when it was to be expected that the transmission conditions did temporarily not allow reception, the data were stored on-board until telemetry was established again. Depending on the prospective duration of the disruption, the read-in bit rate could be chosen in a way that, given the capacity of the core memory of about 500 kbit, the optimal time resolution was achieved. In case of particularly long intermissions, e.g. during a blackout (when HELIOS was located in a certain angle range behind the sun) the storage capacity did not suffice for a complete coverage, even with the smallest bit rate. In this case, continuous reading-in could be interrupted, thus only every n-th space-probe main frame was stored with the goal of achieving a data coverage as evenly as possible.

4.2 Data-Profile

The space-probe telemetry system was able to compile the measured data in six different formats in which the share of the Experiment 6 varied between 0 and 9.7% of the total amount of data. Figure 12 depicts the HELIOS-E6 bit-rate profile for the first 500 days of the HELIOS mission. The data profile looks qualitatively alike for the further course of the mission of HELIOS A (2500 mission-days on 13.10.1981) as well as for HELIOS B (1514 mission-days). Thereby, the blackout phases got shorter, due to the continuous change of the HELIOS trajectories, but from 1980 additional data gaps appeared because the Experiment 6 had to be turned off in the aphelion of the orbit, owing to the degeneration of the solar cells. The daily amount of data transmitted to the Earth decreased because ground-antennas with less transmission capacity were used more often after the expiration of the prime mission. This did not generate data gaps but reduced the time-resolution. In the long-term average, two megabytes per day were received for Experiment 6. They were provided by the German Satellite Operations Center (GSOC) of the DFVLR with additional data on orbit, attitude, commands, data-quality and housekeeping-data and sent to the experimenter. Magnetic tapes (9-track/800 bpi) were used as data distribution medium. By October 1981, 827 experiment-data-record-tapes (EDR) of HELIOS A, which covered the time frame from 10.12.1974 to 2.7.1981, and 651 EDR-tapes of HELIOS B for the time frame from 16.1.1976 to 8.3.1980 were stored at the Christian-Albrechts-University of Kiel.

Abb. 1.7-1: HELIOS-E6-Bitratenprofil

Figure 11 HELIOS-E6-Bitrate-Profile

4.3 Notes on HELIOS-1/2 E6 Data Delivery and Quality Assessment

The file format of the HELIOS data is ASCII. The electron and ion intensity data for the solar cycles 20 and 21 cover the time period from December 11, 1974 to February 7, 1986, and from January 16, 1976 to March 8, 1980, for HELIOS A and B, respectively. In principle the time coverage was continuous, but did include several data gaps at irregular times and of varying length. The data gaps were not marked or filled in any way, the data are simply missing. The basic time resolution (accumulation time) of the measurements varied is due to the bit rate coverage (see Figure 11) highly variable. Time stamps mark the start and end of the averaging interval (rounded to the second) and are given by year, day of year, hour of day, minute of hour, and second of minute.

The data format and contents are defined in Tables 1 and 2 of the Data Delivery Plan [AD2]. The total size of the dataset delivered is about 1.5 GB. The different data groups have been pre-processed into single files before being ingested into the SEPServer, and magnetic field information was added. The preferred access method to the SEPServer has changed from a web browser interface to compressed archives for retrieving the desired data.

4.3.1 Data coverage and varying accumulation periods

While Figure 11 shows the bit-rate profile of the mission, Figure 12 exemplary displays the accumulation times for HELIOS A during the course of 1976. It becomes evident that strong variations between 10 sec and 45 min can occur. Thus the analysis of the data with respect to timing needs to take into account different statistical conditions.

Figure 12 Variation of the accumulation time for HELIOS A and year 1976

4.3.2 Counter overflow and deadtime corrections

The E6 instrument was capable of measuring incident particles with high precision. However, the on-board ADC conversion of the signal amplitude was time consuming and introduced an unacceptable dead time in a high radiation environment. Therefore, only a sample of events are precisely pulse height analyzed while most of them were only counted in 96 counters with a coarse energy and species classification. The counter depth is $2^{20} - 1$. Counting incurred a smaller deadtime, which was even further reduced by incorporating a set of 25 pre-counter flip-flops which were polled between 75 and 1600 microseconds adjusted for the expected particle flux. In rare cases, this sampling period was not sufficient, and the counting result would be erroneous. In order to signal such a situation, a pre-counter overflow bit was transmitted in a telemetry frame. If this bit was set, any one of the 32 counting rates of this frame could be affected. Ambiguous counting results should be discarded from scientific data evaluation.

Using the known time constants of the analog electronics, the measured fluxes can be

corrected for dead time as indicated in Tables 1 and 2 of the SEP (AD2).

4.3.3 Temperature effect

Although of minor importance for the analysis of solar energetic particle events, a temperature dependence of the analog electronics may alter the signal amplification and hence the on-board particle identification. This effect has not been taken into account.

4.3.4 Cross talk

During the course of the mission it became clear that the determination of reliable absolute particle fluxes - especially electron fluxes - in the various energy ranges was problematic due to the following reasons:

1. Because of an apparent non-uniform sensitive area of D1 there was a finite probability for protons to pass D1 without triggering it (Figure 4). This led to a severe contamination of the electron channels during times with greatly enhanced proton fluxes with respect to the electron flux.
2. Due to the lack of electron calibration measurements the energy ranges of the electron channels were not well known, and
3. Scattering effects (cf. Lupton and Stone, 1972) led to different effective opening angles for electrons compared to what one would expect from purely geometrical arguments. The contamination of the proton channels by electrons, which trigger D1 due to straggling, was also possible. This effect was most noticeable during the onset of solar particle events when electrons arrive earlier because of their higher velocities.

In principle, the contamination can be corrected by using the sample of pulse height analysed data to sort out the falsely identified particles. However, pulse height analysed (PHA) data are available only for two electron channels, and due to the limited telemetry capacity of the spacecraft only for a few solar particle events with sufficient statistics. Therefore, reliable response functions for the HELIOS electron and proton coincidence

channels, which take into account among others the effects described above, need to be developed.

SEPServer

Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report

Ulysses COSPIN Kiel Electron Telescope description and data quality

	Name	Signature	Date
Prepared by	B. Heber		5.9.2013
Checked by	E. Valtonen		5.9.2013
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DISTRIBUTION

Name	Organisation

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21.11.2012	0.1			First draft
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Summary and Recommendations

This document contains the Solar Energetic Particle Instrument Document and Data Quality Report for the SEP Server database. Herein the following sections are included:

1. Description of the instrumentation
2. Caveats of the instrument
3. Data quality assessment of the data set

The Kiel Electron Telescope (KET) is part of Cosmic Ray and Energetic Particle Investigation (COSPIN) aboard the Ulysses spacecraft. It was designed to measure electrons, protons and helium from a few MeV to several GeV/Nucleon. Several tests have been performed before the launch. The energy source for Ulysses is a Radioisotope Thermoelectric Generator.

Here we summarize the results of the on ground calibration using the different RTGs on the KET measurements, showing that a major impact on the count rate of low energy protons and electrons exists. Thus, we recommend getting in contact with the PI of the instrument before analysing the variation of the background distribution of galactic cosmic rays. Other sources of background or misidentification of particles, that can be corrected for, by using more detailed information are also summarized. These correction, however, have not been applied. Statistically significant results are only obtained when averaging over several hours. The impact of this effect is most pronounced for the Helium measurements in the energy range of 120 to 190 MeV/Nucleon. Therefore, the user is recommended to get in contact with the PI before analysing these data.

Since the first space born measurements of energetic particles it is known that dead time corrections, a correction for the time the sensor needs to analyse the data, have to be applied. These corrections have been investigated and applied to the data. However, when the effect is getting large such corrections may not lead to reliable results. Thus, the user is recommended to check the lifetime of the instrument, as given to the SEP Server database. Intensities are calculated from the "raw" measurements by applying geometrical factors.

A better way of getting to the physical quantities would be an inversion of the data using a model of the instrument. The first step of achieving such a goal is to simulate the instrument. Such simulations have been performed and are summarized in the report. Furthermore, the geometrical factors are calculated from these simulations and afterwards used to calculate the intensities given in the SEP Server database. For moderate solar energetic particle events the data were shown to give reliable intensities for protons within 50 % (see AD3).

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document contains the **Data Delivery Report** for the Ulysses COSPIN Kiel Electron Telescope (DDRKET) for the SEP Server database server.

The DDRKET roughly breaks down into the following components:

- (a) Description of the Ulysses COSPIN/KET instrumentation
- (b) Caveats of instrument
- (c) Data quality assessment for the instrument data set.

Each class of requirements will be detailed in a section of the document.

1.2 Applicable documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
AD1	Description of Work	EC-GA #262773, Annex I	10 Dec 2010
AD2	Data Delivery Plan	SEPSERVER-009-CAU-WP2	02 Oct 2012
AD3	SEP Server Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: Spacecraft descriptions and data comparison	SEPSERVER-010-CAU-WP2-Spacecraft	

1.3 Reference documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
Brun et al. (1987)	GEANT3. CERN DATA HANDLING DIVISON, 1987. (DD/EE/84-1).		
Clem et al. (2002)	Cosmic Electron Gradients in the Inner Heliosphere	Clem et al.: Geophysical Research Letters, 29, 23, 11-1, 2002	
Ferrando et al. (1996)	Latitude variations of ~7 MeV and >300 MeV cosmic ray electron fluxes in the heliosphere: ULYSSES COSPIN/KET results and implications.	Ferrando et al.: Astron. & Astroph., 316:528-537, 1996.	
Heber (1997)	Modulation galaktischer kosmischer Protonen und alpha-Teilchen in der inneren dreidimensionalen Heliosphäre: Messungen des Kiel Electron Telescopes an Bord der Raumsonde Ulysses	Heber: PhD thesis, University of Kiel, 1997	
Heber et al. (1999)	Determination of 7-30 MeV electron intensities: Ulysses COSPIN/KET results	Heber et al.: Proc. 16th International Cosmic Ray Conference, 7, 186, 1999	
Heber et al. (2001)	On the determination of the γ -ray contribution in the 3-10 MeV KET electron channel along the Ulysses trajectory	Heber et al.: Proc. 27th International Cosmic Ray Conference, 2255, 2001	
Heber et al. (2005)	On the determination of energy spectra of MeV electrons by the Ulysses COSPIN/KET.	Heber, et al.: Advances in Space Research, 35:605-610, 2005.	
Iwers	Calibration of a Space - Born Electron	Iwers: AEG AG, 1989	

(1989)	Telescope – Report on the calibrations performed with the SIM 3 experiment of the COSPIN instrument for the ULYSSES mission		
Rastoin (1995)	Les électrons de Jupiter et de la Galaxie dans l'héliosphère d'après l'expérience KET à bord de la sonde spatiale ULYSSE	Rastoin: PhD thesis, Saclay, 1995	
Sierks (1988)	Auswertungen der Eichmessungen des Kieler Elektronen-Teleskops zur Erstellung von Energiespektren an Bord der Raumsonde ULYSSES (International Solar Polar Mission)	Sierks: Master's thesis, University of Kiel, 1988	
Simpson et al. (1992)	'The ULYSSES Cosmic Ray and Solar Particle Investigation',	Simpson et al.: Astronomy and Astrophysics Supplement Series (ISSN 0365-0138), vol. 92, no. 2, p. 365-399, 1992	
Sullivan (1971)	Geometrical Factor and directional Response of single and multi-element Particle Telescopes	Sullivan: Nucl. Instr. and Meth., 95:5–11, 1971	

1.4 Abbreviations and acronyms

ADC	Analog-to-Digital Converter
AT	Anisotropy Telescope
CERN	Centre Européen de Recherches Nucléaires
COSPIN	Cosmic and Solar Particle Investigation
DDR	Data Delivery Report
FM	Fligth Model
FS	Flight Spare
GEANT	Detector Description and Simulation Tool
HET	High Energy Telescope
HFT	High Flux Telescope
KET	Kiel Electron Telescope
KSC	Kennedy Space Center
LEFS	Low Energy Foil Spectrometer
LET	Low Energy Telescope
PHA	Puls Height Analysis
RTG	Radioisotope Thermoelectric Generator
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle

2 Ulysses COSPIN/KET

The Kiel Electron Telescope (KET) is part of the Ulysses COsmic ray and Solar Particle INvestigation (COSPIN) experiment, which has been described in detail by Simpson et al. [1992]. The instrument is designed to measure electron, proton and α -particle fluxes in several energy windows ranging from a few MeV/n up to and above a few GeV/n. The Ulysses COSPIN/KET instrument has been described in Simpson et al. (1992) and Ferrando et al. (1996).

2.1 The Kiel Electron Telescope Sensor

Figure 1 shows the location of the different scientific instruments on-board Ulysses. The antenna is pointing towards the Earth and corresponds to the axis of rotation. KET is located within the COSPIN instrument group on-board the spacecraft as shown in Figure 2. The different sensor units of the COSPIN consortium are: KET (3), Low Energy Telescope (LET) and Anisotropy Telescope (AT) (both 1), High Energy Telescope (HET) (2) and the High Flux Telescope (HFT) (4). Figure 3 displays the KET flight spare model sensor unit and electronics box. For comparison a five German mark coin is shown to demonstrate the size of the instrument.

Figure 1: Sketch of the Ulysses spaceprobe and the location of the different instrumentation.

Figure 2: Location of the Kiel Electron Telescope (3) within the COSPIN detector suite. Annotated by 1 are the Anisotropy Telescope and the Low Energy Telescope, 2 the High Energy Telescope and 4 the High Flux Telescope (from Simpson et al., 1992).

Figure 3: Flight spare model sensor unit of the Ulysses Kiel Electron Telescope (KET) with electronics box.

KET measures protons and helium in the energy range from 6 MeV/nucleon to above 2 GeV/nucleon and electrons in the energy range from 3 MeV to a few GeV [Simpson et al. 1992] using two silicon detectors, an aerogel Cerenkov detector and PbF_2 -calorimeter. Figure 4 shows a schematic sketch of the KET sensor system.

Figure 4: Cross section of the Kiel Electron Telescope

D1 and D2 are 0.5 mm thick semiconductor detectors, C1 is an aerogel Cerenkov-detector and A a plastic anticoincidence scintillator. C2 is a lead fluoride Cerenkov-detector, S1 and S2 are plastic scintillators. Functionally, the detector system consists of two parts: an entrance telescope and a calorimeter, surrounded by a guard counter A.

- The entrance telescope is composed of a silica-aerogel Cerenkov-detector C1 inserted between semiconductor detectors D1 and D2. Together with the guard

counter A, this combination determines the geometry, selects particles with velocity $\beta > 0.938$ and determines the particle charge.

- The calorimeter consists of a 2.5 radiation length lead-fluoride (PbF_2) crystal used as Cerenkov-detector (C2) and a scintillator S2. In C2 an electromagnetic shower can develop. The number of electrons leaving the PbF_2 -crystal is counted in S2.

Thus a number of count rate channels can be defined for scientific analysis. These channels are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 Kiel Electron Telescope energy channel definition (from Simpson et al., 1992)

Name	Logic	Primary Particle Type	Energy Range (MeV/(n))	Geometric Factor (cm ² -sr)	Avg. Time Resolution (s)	Sectors	PHA
K1 (P1)	D11 <u>D12 C10 D20 C20 S20 A0</u>	proton	2.7-5.4	6.5	128	--	--
K21-28 (P4)	D12 <u>D13 C10 D20 C20 S20 A0</u>	proton	5.4-23.1	6.5	128	8	--
K3 (P32)	D11 D20 <u>D12 C10 C20 S20 A0</u>	proton	34.1-125	0.72	128	--	P1
K34 (P116)	D10 D20 S20 <u>D12 C10 C20 A0</u>	proton	125-320	1.2	128	--	P1
K12 (P190)	D10 D20 C20 S20 <u>D11 C10 D21 C21 A0</u>	proton	320-2100	1.7	128	--	P0
K10 (P4000)	D10 C10 D20 C20 S20 <u>D11 C11 D21 C21 A0</u>	proton	>2100	1.7	128	--	P0
K2 (A4)	D13 <u>C10 D20 C20 S20 A0</u>	He	6.0-20.4	6.5	128	--	--
K33 (A32)	D12 D21 <u>D13 C10 C20 S20 A0</u>	He	34.2-125	0.72	128	--	P1
K29 (A116)	D12 D21 S20 <u>D13 C10 C20 A0</u>	He	125-320	1.0	128	--	P1
K31 (A190)	D11 D21 C20 S20 <u>D12 C10 A0</u>	He	320-2100	1.4	128	--	P0
K30 (A4000)	D11 C10 D21 C20 S20 <u>D12 C11 A0</u>	He	>2100	1.4	128	--	P1
K13-20 (E4)	D10 C10 D20 <u>D11 C11 D21 C20 S20 A0</u>	electron	2.5-7	0.26	128	8	P1
K11 (E12)	D10 C10 D20 C20 <u>D11 C11 D21 S20 A0</u>	electron	7-170	0.40	128	--	P3
K32 (E300)	D10 C10 D20 C21 S20 <u>D11 C11 D21 (A0+A1)</u>	electron	>170	0.38	128	--	P2

2.2 Monte Carlo simulation of the KET

Sullivan [1971] describes the determination of the response functions of particle telescopes along with several exact formulae for multi-element telescopes. However, the determination of the response function of rather complex telescopes like the KET instrument makes a Monte Carlo simulation necessary. We assume that the differential coincidence-counting rate of a particle telescope can be expressed as:

$$dC_{i,k} = dE R_i^k(E) J_k(E) (\text{counts/s})$$

where $dC_{i,k}$ is the differential coincidence counting rate in channel i , $J_k(E)$ the flux of

particle species k with kinetic energy E , and $R_i^k(E)$ the response function for particle species k in channel i , to be determined by the simulation. To get the counting rate C_i for the channel i we have to integrate over E and sum up for all particle species. In general, the response function may depend on many variables like the angular distribution of the incident particle flux, the location where a particle penetrates a detector etc. Here we assume that $R(E)$ is a function only of kinetic energy, valid for particle fluxes which are almost isotropic over the effective opening angle, and that the simulation properly averages over all other dependencies.

The Monte Carlo simulation was performed with the CERN Library Program GEANT 3 [Brun et al., 1987]. Particles were followed down to a low energy cutoff (for electrons and gamma-rays at 50 keV, for protons at 300 keV). Once reaching this cutoff, the particles were considered to be stopped and to have deposited all of their kinetic energy in the traversed material. The geometry of the detectors, mountings, foils, and the relevant structure material as well as the energy resolution of the readout electronics were accounted for in the simulation.

Figure 5: Model of the KET-detector stack in the GEANT simulation.

-
- **KET geometry:** The model of the KET sensor unit in the simulation is shown in Figure 5. Shown are three possible tracks of 120 MeV protons. Two of these tracks are triggering the channel P32 and one of them is counted in P116.
 - **Energy loss distribution:** In addition to the count rates in all coincidence channels, the energy losses in D1 and D2 as well as the number of photons in C1, C2 and S2 are transmitted. Particle instruments are calibrated by using a particle beam provided by an accelerator [Sierks, 1988]. In space, particles of different species, incident directions and energies are observed nearly simultaneously. Such an environment cannot be simulated at an accelerator but can be simulated using an appropriate computer model. As an example Figure 6 (left) shows the simulated energy distribution of isotropic protons and α -particles in the semiconductor detectors D1 and D2 triggering the P32 and A32 coincidence channels. The D1-D2 PHA distribution (energy loss) has been calculated by using a uniform proton and α energy spectrum and an isotropic distribution. Solid lines in figures Figure 6 (left) show the mean energy losses. Marked on these lines are the expected energy losses for protons and α -particles with energies of 35, 40, 50, 70 and 120 MeV/n. The horizontal and vertical dotted lines display the electronic thresholds. In comparison, Figure 6 (right) shows a PHA distribution measured in space in January 1991. The entries below the dotted line could be identified as background. As is discussed in detail in Heber [1997], the proton and α -tracks in that matrix are well described by the GEANT Monte Carlo simulation.

Figure 6: Simulated (left) and measured (right) energy-loss in the two semiconductor detectors for the coincidence channels P32 and A32. The logic of these channels is that only the two semiconductor detectors register a signal above an electronic threshold. The nominal energy range for this channel is 34 - 125 MeV/nucleon. In contrast to the simulation an unexpected background is visible in the lower left corner of the measured distribution.

Calculations were done in order to determine the response function of the instrument. The input to the model was an isotropic particle distribution over 1.5 times the opening angle (see Figure 4) of the instrument equally distributed in energy from 1 MeV/nuc to 10 GeV/nuc.

Figure 7: Response function for the proton and alpha channel in the energy range from 38 to 125 MeV/nuc. The boxes give the expected response function (Heber, 1997).

Figure 8: Response function for the proton and alpha channel in the energy range from 125 to 250 MeV/nuc. The boxes (P) give the expected response function (Heber, 1997). In contrast to the response functions shown in Figure 7 the energy channels respond also to particles penetrating the instrument from the back (R). V and S denotes the response for nominal penetration and the sum of both, respectively.

Table 2. KET energy channels and response factors

Particle	Energy range (MeV/n)	Response factor (cm ² sr MeV)
KET P1 protons		
Protons	2.7 – 5.4	17.6
Protons	23.1-34.1	71.5
Helium	2.3-2.7	2.6
KET P4 protons		
Protons	5.4 – 23..1	115
Helium	2.7 – 6	15
Helium	20.4-34.2	89.7
KET P32 protons		
Protons	34-125	70
KET P116 protons		
Protons (F)	125-250	152
Protons (B)	160-260	
Helium	130-190	-
KET P190 Protons		
Protons (F)	250-2000	3300
Protons (B)	260-2000	
KET P4000 Protons		
Protons	>2000	TBD
KET A4 Helium		
Helium	5.4-23.1	115
Heavy Ions	TBD	TBD
KET A32 Helium		
Helium (F)	34-125	70
KET A116 Helium		
Helium (F)	125 - 155	88
Helium B	155 – 225	

KET A190 Helium		
Helium (F)	250 – 2100	3200
Helium (B)	260 -- 2100	
KET A4000 Helium		
Helium	> 2100	1 ¹
KET E4 Electrons		
Electrons	4 - 9	1 ¹
KET E12 Electrons		
Electrons	9 – 500	1 ¹
KET E300 Electrons		
Electrons	>500	1 ¹
Protons	>2000	1 ¹

2.2.1 Background contribution

When comparing Figure 6 (left) and (right) with each other, it is obvious that other particles contribute to the flight measurements. In order to minimize the contribution of this background, criteria were introduced in the energy loss distributions of the two semiconductor detectors. Figure 7 from P32 and A32 as well as P116 and A116 are shown in figure Figure 7 (left) and (right), respectively.

¹ These channels are given in count rates only

Figure 7: Correction masks for P32 and A32 (left) and P116 and A116 (right).

2.2.2 Response factor

The response functions $R_i^{Sim}(E)$ for isotropic protons and α -particles are displayed in Figure 8. The rectangular boxes indicate the response functions expected when using the Sullivan [1971] approach. For the low energy channels (P1, P4, and A4) this method is a good approximation. For the complex channels P32 to P4000, A32 to A4000, and E4 to E300 this approximation is not valid and one has to rely on the result of the Monte Carlo simulation. Since the shape of the response function is not rectangular anymore, the response factor, the integral R_i over all energies of the response function, has to be used for each coincidence i . The intensity I is obtained when dividing the measured count rates C_i by R_i .

Figure 8: Response function of different KET coincidence channels, as defined in Table 1.

3 Data Corrections

3.1 Particle identification and corresponding corrections

In the previous section the particle identification in the different proton channels has been discussed. Applying these corrections relies on a statistically significant subset of data for which a particle identification can be performed. Because only 20 particles can be analysed per data frame, we do not apply these changes on the high time resolution data.

3.2 Deadtime correction

When a large particle flux is entering the telescope, an instrumental feature called “deadtime” can occur, which inhibits the instrument in processing all of the incoming particles, due to processing time being longer than the time between the occurrences of subsequent events. The crucial parts of the instrument regarding this effect are the electronics, which handle the data acquisition for every detector. Different steps in the processing chain of detector signals can be responsible for the electronics being unable to process the next upcoming event (Spieler, 2005):

- ✓ Time to acquire a signal, based on the slope of the amplifier signal peaking over time and the subsequent settling of the amplifier signal back to the baseline
- ✓ Time to convert the signal in the ADC, which depends on the signal peak
- ✓ Time to store the data in memory, which depends on the memory speed and bandwidth

Effects of deadtime can be ignored in cases where the time between Poisson-distributed incoming pulses (like in extra-terrestrial particle distributions) is sufficiently larger than the combined time of these processing steps, since the case of two events occurring in the time window of instrument deadtime is very rare. Generally, for a telescope designed to study interplanetary particles, this is true for solar quiet times, which show much decreased particle fluxes compared to solar events. However, it is important to estimate the deadtime when generating particle spectra for solar events, since otherwise the particle fluxes will be underestimated.

In the case of the KET the correction due to instrument deadtime had not been used until this work. For low flux conditions the predominant dead time is that of the anticoincidence counter $A_{0/1}$. For quiet times, with an estimated $A_{0/1}$ count rate of more than 5000 counts/s, this sets the expected deadtime in the range of about 1% up to 2%. During high flux conditions the determining factor of deadtime are the pulse shapers of the other detectors involved. The calculations were done based on KET single count rates for every data frame. The results are saved in form of instrument livetimes in column 8 of Table 4 and Table 5. For the purpose of calculating particle spectra each particle is weighed with its livetime value. In case of high flux events the weighing of spectrum data with the livetimes will result in increased particle intensities. As an example deadtime corrected and uncorrected intensity time profiles are displayed in Figure 9, clearly showing the effect.

Figure 9 Raw (black curve) and livetime corrected (green curve) intensity-time profiles of 4 to 25 MeV protons during the March 1991 event. The red curve shows the livetime of the instrument (as a fraction of total accumulation time) during this very active period.

3.3 Background contribution due to the Radioisotope Thermoelectric Generator (RTG)

Before launch of the spacecraft several test at KSC have been performed. This section summarizes the results.

After the Integrated System Test at KSC, an RTG compatibility test was performed with KET-Flight Modell mounted onboard the S/C platform in flight configuration. The RTG was attached to the S/C in final flight position. The KET instrument was commanded into its nominal operational mode. The results are provided in Table 3 together with observations of similar tests performed in the years 1985 and 1986. The two columns with results from Mound Laboratories test runs serve to demonstrate, that there are only marginal differences between KET-FM and –Flight Spare with the exception of threshold C20 of the lead-flouride Cherenkov detector, which gives a counting rate by about a factor of 2 higher for the FM as compared to the FS.

The two columns with results from KSC test runs differ not only by time (1986 and 1990) and the associated change in RTG activity, but also by the switching from KET-FS to KET-FM as our preferred flight unit.

The last column shows the ratio of the counting rates taken 1990 and 1986. It is clear that there is an increase with time by about a factor of 2. It may even be more than a factor of 2, considering the fact, that back in 1986 the RTG could not be mounted in its final flight position because of problems with a thread in the RTG mounting flange. Consequently the RTG was facing KET in a position in which the self-absorption of the source was reduced.

The only significant deviation from the factor of 2 increases is recorded in channel C20, which is explained by the model switching (see above).

Table 3 contains three panels showing in the upper panel single detector readings above the lowest threshold, in the middle panel KET proton channels, and in the lower panel KET electron channels. Entries for channels, which did not show any counts, were left blank rather than giving upper limits to increase the readability. The KET helium channels are not shown, as they are not affected by the RTG.

The data from June 22, 1990 are taken between 10:34 and 11:42. They cover 67 minutes corresponding to 16.5 COSPIN superformats. Counting statistics for single detector readings above the lowest threshold are better than 0.3%.

Table 3 Response of KET to RTG Model F3

Rate	Channel	RTG Mound (Mar. 1985)		RTG KSC		Ratio
				Feb 86	Jun 90	
		KET-FS	KET-FM	KET-FS	KET-FM	90/86
		Counts/sec	Counts/sec	Counts/sec	Counts/sec	
K4	D10	25	22.8	44.5	73.0	1.64
K5	D20	9.9	10.5	22.8	39.4	1.73
K6	C10	128.5	129.6	226.0	403.2	1.78
K7	C20	68.2	142.7	91.3	397.7	4.36
K9	S20	358.0	496.0	603.0	1271.7	2.11
K8	A0/1	1134.0	955	1889.0	3117.1	1.65
K1	P1	0.6	0.6	1.4	3.2	2.29
K21-28	P4	2.4E-3	8.8E-4	-	7.3E-4	-
K3	P32	1.1E-4	1.8E-4	-	1.2E-4	-
K34	P116	-	-	-	-	-
K12	P190	-	1.8E-4	-	-	-
K10	P4000	3.8E-5	9.2E-5	-	2.4E-4	-
K13-20	E4	9.0E-3	7.3E-3	4.0E-3	3.2E-3	0.8
K11	E12	7.0E-4	1.5E-3	-	2.4E-4	-
K32	E300	-	-	-	-	-

As can be seen in the June 1990 data, some higher energy channels registered counts, which did not show up in 1986 (P4, P32, and E12), at a low counting rate though. From a scientific point of view, only the channels P1 and E4 are adversely affected by the RTG as the RTG background is of the order of the expected cosmic ray quiet flux in these KET particle channels. Thus they will only deliver meaningful results during solar flare events and closer to Jupiter. All channels will suffer from an RTG-induced deadtime of 0.5% as compared to 0.003% without RTG. The main contribution to the dead time increase stems from the scintillation guard counter with its large field of view. Use of Cerenkov detectors and multifold coincidences guarantees the low susceptibility of the KET coincidence rates.

Since there is some variability in the RTG values the following values 1., 8.05e-4, 1.8e-4, 0.0, 0.9e-4, 1.6e-4, 5.2e-3, 1.9e-4, and 0.0 counts/s were used for the channel P1, P4, P32, P116, P190, P4000, E4, E12, and E300, respectively. The activity of the RTG is expected to vary with time. However, it is impossible to correct for this, since the details of the RTG composition are not known to us.,

4 Ulysses COSPIN/KET Data Sets

The electron, proton and helium intensity and count rate data for the solar cycles 23-24 cover the time period May 8, 1996 – May 31, 2009. The time coverage is in principle continuous, but does include several data gap at irregular times and of varying length. The data gaps are not marked or filled in any way, but the data are simply missing. The basic time resolution (accumulation time) of the measurements is variable due to the variable data transmission rate of Ulysses. They vary between ~121 s and ~267 s. The start of the accumulation time is given by year, Day Of Year, Hour of Day, Minute of hour, Second of Minute and Millisecond of seconds. The data format and contents are defined in Table 4 and Table 5 taken from AD2.

Table 4 KET data format for the solar cycle 23 and 24 electron, proton and helium data

Column	Physical Quantity	Format	Units	Dependent Quantity	Range of dependent quantity	Value range	Dropout Value	Comments
1	Year	I5	N/A			see format	-707	Time block (start time of the record)
2	Day of year	I5	N/A			see format	-707	Time block (start time of the record)
3	Hour of day	I5	N/A			see format	-707	Time block (start time of the record)
4	Minute of hour	I5	N/A			see format	-707	Time block (start time of the record)
5	Second of minute	I5	N/A			see format	-707	Time block (start time of the record)
6	Millisecond of second	I5	N/A			see format	-707	Time block (start time of the record)

								the record)
7	Accumulation time	I10	N/A			see format	-707	Milliseconds
8	Lifetime	F12.3	N/A			see format	-707	Fraction of the accumulation time
9	Protons P1	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{sr}^{-1} \text{MeV}^{-1} \text{nucleon}^{-1}$	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s MeV})$
10	Protons P1	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Counts
11	Protons P4	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{sr}^{-1} \text{MeV}^{-1} \text{nucleon}^{-1}$	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s MeV})$
12	Protons P4	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Counts
13	Protons P32	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{sr}^{-1} \text{MeV}^{-1} \text{nucleon}^{-1}$	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s MeV})$
14	Protons P32	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Counts
15	Protons P116	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{sr}^{-1} \text{MeV}^{-1} \text{nucleon}^{-1}$	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s MeV})$
16	Protons P116	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Counts
17	Protons P190	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{sr}^{-1} \text{MeV}^{-1} \text{nucleon}^{-1}$	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s MeV})$

18	Protons P190	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Counts
19	Protons P4000	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ sr^{-1}	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s}$ MeV)
20	Protons P4000	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Counts
21	Helium A4	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ sr^{-1} MeV ⁻¹ nucleon ⁻¹	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Helium Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s}$ MeV)
22	Helium A4	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Helium, Counts
23	Helium A32	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ sr^{-1} MeV ⁻¹ nucleon ⁻¹	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Helium Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s}$ MeV)
24	Helium A32	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Helium, Counts
25	Helium A116	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ sr^{-1} MeV ⁻¹ nucleon ⁻¹	see Table 2	see Table 2		-707	KET Helium Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s}$ MeV)
26	Helium A116	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Helium, Counts
27	Helium A190	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ sr^{-1} MeV ⁻¹ nucleon ⁻¹	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Helium Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s}$ MeV)
28	Helium A190	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Helium, Counts
29	Helium A4000	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ sr^{-1}	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Helium Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s}$

								MeV)
30	Helium A4000	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Helium, Counts
31	Electrons E4	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ sr^{-1} MeV^{-1} nucleon^{-1}	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s}$ $\text{MeV})$
32	Electrons E4	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Counts
33	Electrons E12	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ sr^{-1} MeV^{-1} nucleon^{-1}	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s}$ $\text{MeV})$
34	Electrons E12	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Counts
35	Electrons E300	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ sr^{-1}	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s}$ $\text{MeV})$
36	Electrons E300	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Counts

Table 5 KET sectorized data format for the solar cycle 23 and 24 electron, proton and helium data

Column	Physical Quantity	Format	Units	Dependent Quantity	Range of dependent quantity	Value range	Dropout Value	Comments
1	Year	I5	N/A			see format	-707	Time block (start time of the record)
2	Day of year	I5	N/A			see format	-707	Time block (start time of the record)
3	Hour of day	I5	N/A			see format	-707	Time block (start time of

								the record)
4	Minute of hour	I5	N/A			see format	-707	Time block (start time of the record)
5	Second of minute	I5	N/A			see format	-707	Time block (start time of the record)
6	Millisecond of second	I5	N/A			see format	-707	Time block (start time of the record)
7	Accumulation time	I10	N/A			see format	-707	Milliseconds
8	Lifetime	F12.3	N/A			see format	-707	Fraction of the accumulation time
9	Protons P4 (Sector 0)	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{sr}^{-1} \text{MeV}^{-1} \text{nucleon}^{-1}$	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s MeV})$
10	Protons P4 (Sector 0)	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Counts
11	Protons P4 (Sector 1)	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{sr}^{-1} \text{MeV}^{-1} \text{nucleon}^{-1}$	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s MeV})$
12	Protons P4 (Sector 1)	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Counts
13	Protons P4 (Sector 2)	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{sr}^{-1} \text{MeV}^{-1} \text{nucleon}^{-1}$	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s MeV})$
14	Protons P4 (Sector 2)	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Counts
15	Protons P4 (Sector 3)	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{sr}^{-1}$	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Intensity in

			MeV ⁻¹ nucleon ⁻¹					1/(cm ² sr s MeV)
16	Protons P4 (Sector 3)	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Counts
17	Protons P4 (Sector 4)	E12.3	cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ sr ⁻¹ MeV ⁻¹ nucleon ⁻¹	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Intensity in 1/(cm ² sr s MeV)
18	Protons P4 (Sector 4)	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Counts
19	Protons P4 (Sector 5)	E12.3	cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ sr ⁻¹ MeV ⁻¹ nucleon ⁻¹	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Intensity in 1/(cm ² sr s MeV)
20	Protons P4 (Sector 5)	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Counts
21	Protons P4 (Sector 6)	E12.3	cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ sr ⁻¹ MeV ⁻¹ nucleon ⁻¹	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Intensity in 1/(cm ² sr s MeV)
22	Protons P4 (Sector 6)	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Counts
23	Protons P4 (Sector 7)	E12.3	cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ sr ⁻¹ MeV ⁻¹ nucleon ⁻¹	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Intensity in 1/(cm ² sr s MeV)
24	Protons P4 (Sector 7)	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET protons, Counts
25	Electrons E4 (Sector 0)	E12.3	cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ sr ⁻¹ MeV ⁻¹ nucleon ⁻¹	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Intensity in 1/(cm ² sr s MeV)
26	Electrons E4 (Sector 0)	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Counts
27	Electrons E4	E12.3	cm ⁻² s ⁻¹	see Table	see Table	see	-707	KET Electron

	(Sector 1)		sr ⁻¹ MeV ⁻¹ nucleon ⁻	2	2	format		Intensity in 1/(cm ² sr s MeV)
28	Electrons E4 (Sector 1)	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Counts
29	Electrons E4 (Sector 2)	E12.3	cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ sr ⁻¹ MeV ⁻¹ nucleon ⁻	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Intensity in 1/(cm ² sr s MeV)
30	Electrons E4 (Sector 2)	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Counts
31	Electrons E4 (Sector 3)	E12.3	cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ sr ⁻¹ MeV ⁻¹ nucleon ⁻	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Intensity in 1/(cm ² sr s MeV)
32	Electrons E4 (Sector 3)	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Counts
33	Electrons E4 (Sector 4)	E12.3	cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ sr ⁻¹ MeV ⁻¹ nucleon ⁻	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Intensity in 1/(cm ² sr s MeV)
34	Electrons E4 (Sector 4)	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Counts
35	Electrons E4 (Sector 5)	E12.3	cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ sr ⁻¹ MeV ⁻¹ nucleon ⁻	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Intensity in 1/(cm ² sr s MeV)
36	Electrons E4 (Sector 5)	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Counts
37	Electrons E4 (Sector 6)	E12.3	cm ⁻² s ⁻¹ sr ⁻¹ MeV ⁻¹ nucleon ⁻	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Intensity in 1/(cm ² sr s MeV)
38	Electrons E4 (Sector 6)	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Counts

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39	Electrons E4 (Sector 7)	E12.3	$\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ sr^{-1} MeV^{-1} nucleon ⁻¹	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Intensity in $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{sr s}$ MeV)
40	Electrons E4 (Sector 7)	F12.3	counts	see Table 2	see Table 2	see format	-707	KET Electron Counts

5 Ulysses COSPIN/KET Data Delivered and Quality Assessment

The electron, proton and helium intensity and count rate data for the solar cycles 23-24 cover the time period May 8, 1996 – May 31, 2009. The time coverage is in principle continuous, but does include several data gap at irregular times and of varying length. The data gaps are not marked or filled in any way, but the data are simply missing. The basic time resolution (accumulation time) of the measurements is variable due to the variable data transmission rate of Ulysses. They vary between ~121 s and ~267 s. The start of the accumulation time is given by year, Day Of Year, Hour of Day, Minute of hour, Second of Minute and Millisecond of seconds.

5.1 Remarks on different energy channels

- P1, P4 and A4 are single detector counters and measure therefore protons, alpha and heavier ions in other energy ranges than the channels were designed for. I.e. for hard or even inverted proton energy spectra these contributions are essential.
- The measured energy loss matrix of P32 shows unexpected entries. A correction for this entries needs a detailed analysis that can only performed on longer integration intervals.
- P116 and A116: Determination of reliable intensities of P116 and A116 needs correction on longer accumulation periods (several hours) since both species contribute to a certain amount to both channels.
- P190: Due to a ~10 % inefficiency of the aerogel Cherenkov detector particles to be measured in P4000 (i.e. protons with energies above 2 GeV) contribute to the P190 channel. This contribution is taken care of by subtracting 10% of the P4000 channel.
- A190: A small contribution to the A190 channel of protons with energies of about 200 MeV is possible. A correction on the basis of short accumulation times is not

possible and has therefore been omitted.

- P4000 and E300 are measuring singly charged minimum ionizing particles. The separation between these two channels is a threshold in the lead-fluoride Cherenkov detector. Thus both electrons with energies above 170 MeV and protons with energies above 2 GeV contribute to these channels. Since protons are much more abundant a reliable determination of the electron intensities need a detailed correction on longer accumulation periods (see also Clem et al., 2002).
- E4 and E12 are contaminated by gamma rays from the RTG and by gamma rays from the π^0 -decay. These π^0 are generated by the interaction of nuclei with the spacecraft body.
- Time periods when KET is saturated or is working in a "non nominal mode" have been omitted, e.g.:
 - March event 1991
 - Jovian encounter

5.2 Summary of major improvements

SEPServer provides for the first time

1. Ulysses COSPIN/KET data corrected for:
 1. Contamination from neutrons and gamma rays from the RTG
 2. Dead time correction
2. Ulysses COSPIN/KET intensities using the geometric factors derived from a GEANT 3 simulation
3. Most comprehensive description of the data set
4. Sectorized intensities for 4 to 25 MeV protons.

SEP Server

Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report Ulysses/COSPIN/LET Instrument description and data quality

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DISTRIBUTION

Name	Organisation

CHANGE LOG

Date	Issue	Rev.	Pages	Reason for change
21.11.2012	0.1			First draft
	1.	0		Consolidation of team inputs
24.05.2013	1.	1	Several pages	Included caveats
04.06.2013	1.	2	P10	Included editing changes proposed by EV
01.08.2013	1.	3	Several pages	Included changes proposed by BH
02.10.2013	1.	4	Several pages	Included changes proposed by RV

Summary

This document contains the Solar Energetic Particle Instrument Document and Data Quality Report for the SEPServer database server. Herein the following four sections are included:

1. Description the Ulysses/COSPIN/LET instrumentation
2. Data sets delivered
3. Caveats and data quality assessment.

In Section 2 a detailed description on the Ulysses/COSPIN/LET instrumentation is provided. It includes details on the characteristics of LET together with the basic scientific objectives of the instrument. Section 3 refers to the datasets delivered to SEPServer in terms of the format of the files and contents that currently are available through the SEPServer database. Section 4 provides a summary of the known limitations of the LET data. The background issues from high energy protons, the “roll-over” effect and the known caveats are being reported. Finally, a summary of the dataset distributed by SEPServer is presented at the end of this document.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document contains the Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report (DDR) of the Cosmic Ray and Solar Particle Investigation (COSPIN) Low Energy Telescope (LET) for the SEP Server database server.

The DDR's roughly break down into the following components:

1. Description the Ulysses/COSPIN/LET instrumentation
2. Data sets delivered
3. Caveats and quality assessment.

Each class of requirements will be detailed in a section of the document.

1.2 Applicable documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue	
AD1	Description of Work	EC-GA #262773, Annex I	10	Dec 2010
AD2	Data Delivery Plan	SEPSERVER-009-CAU- WP2	02	Oct 2012

1.3 Reference documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
RD1	The ULYSSES Cosmic Ray and Solar	Simpson, J. A., Anglin, J.	

	Particle Investigation,	D., Balogh, A., et al.: Astron. Astrophys. Suppl. Series, 92(2), 365– 399, 1992	
RD2	Ulysses/COSPIN Low Energy Telescope Handbook Rev.1	http://www.rssd.esa.int/helio/archive/LET_Handbook_rev1.pdf	
RD3	Ulysses/COSPIN Low Energy Telescope website	http://www.rssd.esa.int/helio/archive/cospin_let.html	

1.4 Abbreviations and acronyms

COSPIN	Cosmic and Solar Particle INvestigation
DDR	Data Delivery Report
DDP	Data Delivery Plan
GCRs	Galactic Cosmic Rays
LET	Low energy Telescope
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
RTG	Radiothermal Generator Background
SEP Server	Data Services and Analysis Tools for Solar Energetic Particle Events and Related Electromagnetic Emissions
NOA	National Observatory of Athens

2 Ulysses/COSPIN/LET description

The Low Energy Telescope (LET) is part of the collaborative Cosmic Ray and Solar Particle Investigation (COSPIN) experiment designed to investigate the charged particle environment encountered during all phases of the Ulysses mission. The LET measures the flux, energy spectra and elemental composition of solar and heliospheric energetic particles and low energy cosmic ray nuclei from hydrogen up to iron, covering an energy range from ~ 1 to ~ 75 MeV/n. Isotope separation for light nuclei such as He is also achieved.

Figure 1 Cross-section of the COSPIN/LET sensor, showing the detectors and aperture foils [taken by RD2]

The detecting elements of the telescope are shown in cross-section in **Figure 1**. A photograph of the hardware is presented in **Figure 2**. Detectors D1 and D2 are surface-barrier devices with equal active area (6.0 cm^2), while D3 and D4 are 2 mm-thick lithium-drifted devices of 10.0 and 12.5 cm^2 active area, respectively. The detailed characteristics of the detectors mounted in the flight instrument are given in **Table 1**. D5, comprising a cylindrical plastic scintillator element viewed by a single photomultiplier tube, forms (together with D4) an anti-coincidence counter. The anti-coincidence shield is needed to reject particles that enter the telescope outside the nominal acceptance cone, or that penetrate part of the internal structure of the telescope, giving rise to spurious signals in one or more detectors. The telescope aperture is covered by two thin foils, an inner Ti foil ($\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$, 0.9 mg/cm^2) for electrical shielding, and an outer aluminised Kapton foil ($\sim 8 \mu\text{m}$, 1.0 mg/cm^2) for thermal protection.

Table 1 Characteristics of the detectors and aperture foils installed in the flight model LET. (Note that there is some uncertainty in precise thicknesses of the two foils).

Detector	Type		Thickness		Area (cm^2)
			(μm)	(mg/cm^2)	
D1	Si surface barrier	Ortec 600-30 S/N 22-235B	32.2	7.503	6.0
D2	Si surface barrier	Ortec 600-100 S/N 20-663C	95.9	22.345	6.0
D3	Li-drifted	LBL 1000-2000 S/N 4469	2054	478.6	10.0
D4	Li-drifted	LBL 1250-2000 S/N 4506	2000	466.0	12.5
D5	Plastic scintillator / PMT	RCA C70102E 4F4	-	-	-
Outer foil	Aluminised Kapton			~ 8	~ 1.0
Inner foil	Titanium			~ 2	~ 0.9

The scientific data obtained from the LET system are counting rates for 22 different particle species/energy-range combinations, 2 of which are further sub-divided into 8 angular viewing sectors in the spacecraft spin plane. At the highest available spacecraft bit-rate (1024 bps real-time telemetry), counts are accumulated over 32- or 128-sec intervals (telemetry-format synchronised) for the non-sectored channels, and over an integral number of spins for the 16 spin-synchronised sectored channels. Data from the LET are telemetered in the form of spin-averaged counting rate information for proton, alpha and heavy ion energy channels, together with pulse-height information on a sampled event-by-event basis for $Z > 2$ events. In order to facilitate the study of the spatial distribution of the particle flux, the counts in two of the proton channels are also accumulated in eight consecutive equatorial sectors of 45° , the telescope axis being perpendicular to the spacecraft spin axis. An overview of all 38 rate channels is given in **Table 2**.

Table 2 COSPIN Low Energy Telescope (LET) Data Channel Summary

COSPIN/LET RATE DATA		
Channel	Measurement	Geometrical factor (cm ² sr)
L1	protons (0.9-1.2 MeV)	9.1
L2	protons (1.2-3.0 MeV)	9.1
L3	protons (1.8-3.8 MeV)	0.58
L4_11	protons (1.8-3.8 MeV) / sectors 1 to 8	0.58
L12	protons (3.8-8.0 MeV)	0.58
L13_20	protons (3.8-8.0 MeV) / sectors 1 to 8	0.58
L21	protons (8.0-19.0 MeV)	0.58
L22	alphas (1.0-5.0 MeV/n)	9.1
L23	alphas (1.9-3.7 MeV/n)	0.58
L24	alphas (3.7-8.4 MeV/n)	0.58
L25	alphas (8.4-19.0 MeV/n)	0.58
L26	Li,Be,B (1.9-4.9 MeV/n)	0.58
L27	Li,Be,B (4.9-26 MeV/n)	0.58

L28	C,N,O (2.6-7.1 MeV/n)	0.58
L29	C,N,O (7.1-39.0 MeV/n)	0.58
L30	Z>=10 (3.0-9.0 MeV/n)	0.58
L31	10<=Z<=20 (9.0-50 MeV/n)	0.58
L32	Z>=20 (12.0-75.0 MeV/n)	0.58
L33	electrons (0.3-1.0 MeV)	-
L34_38	single detector counting rates	

Figure 2 Photograph of the LET telescope showing its mechanical configuration and the tube mounting [taken by RD2]

The specific scientific objectives for the COSPIN/LET instrument are as quoted as follows from [RD1]:

- I. From the measurement of charged particles of solar origin we shall study their energy spectra, elemental and isotopic composition and anisotropy during propagation to high heliospheric latitudes to determine:
 - a) The role of coronal magnetic fields for the storage and propagation of solar flare accelerated nuclei and electrons;
 - b) The origin of the enrichment of ^3He and Fe observed in some solar flares;
 - c) The importance of emission of energetic particles from regions other than solar flares.

- II. For the galactic cosmic ray investigations we shall:
 - a) Explore the likely reduction in solar modulation near solar minimum over the solar polar regions to deduce the interstellar galactic cosmic ray spectra at low energies both for nucleons and electrons, and to determine the abundances of electron-capture isotopes.
 - b) Investigate the propagation of nuclei compared to that of electrons in polar and equatorial regions during the period when nucleons are predicted to gradient drift from over the polar regions to the inner heliosphere. This would provide a test of the importance of the 22 year solar polar magnetic field reversal cycle for cosmic ray modulation.
 - c) Based on "b" above, search for evidence that the anomalous nuclear component may be accelerated at a terminal shock over the heliospheric polar regions;
 - d) Measure the elemental and isotopic abundances of the galactic cosmic rays from H to Ni down to a low energy threshold determined by either:
 - (i) residual modulation if significant transverse magnetic field irregularities exist at polar latitudes, or;
 - (ii) instrumental response thresholds if the field lines are open to the interstellar

- medium so that residual modulation is unimportant;
- e) From "d" above, attempt to derive the nucleosynthetic origin of the low energy interstellar cosmic radiation.
- III. With regard to the acceleration or modulation of charged particles in the interplanetary medium, COSPIN/LET will:
- a) Study the latitudinal extent and three-dimensional character of interplanetary shocks which accelerate charged particles and modulate (e.g., by Forbush decreases) the galactic cosmic rays and the anomalous nuclear component;
 - b) Establish the latitudinal gradients of nucleons and electrons during the solar magnetic cycle prevailing in 1992-1996;
 - c) Measure the distribution of Jovian electrons as probes of heliospheric magnetic fields at high latitudes.
- IV. During the Ulysses encounter with Jupiter (closest approach, 8 February 1992) COSPIN/LET studies will include:
- a) The first traversal of the dusk side of the Jovian magnetosphere;
 - b) A search for the mechanism producing the ~10 hour "clock" variation of the Jovian relativistic electron spectra both in the magnetosphere and in interplanetary space;
 - c) Measurements of the intensities, spectra, anisotropies, and composition of the trapped radiation.

2.1 LET mechanical construction

The LET telescope is mounted together with the associated analogue and digital electronics in the central section of the SIM-1 package, with the Data Processing Unit below and the Anisotropy Telescopes above (see **Figure 3** and **Figure 4**). The LET aperture is protected by a hinged cover that was deployed (opened) after launch, as

indicated in **Figure 4**.

Figure 3 Front view of SIM-1 package with LET in the center (upper figure); SIM-1 package with the Anisotropy Telescope (AT) and LET (middle) indicated (bottom panel) [taken by RD2]

Figure 4 Side view of SIM-1 package with LET in the center (dimensions in mm) [taken by RD2]

3 Data Delivery

Ulysses/COSPIN/LET measures protons in the energy range of 0.9-19 MeV, alphas in the energy range of 1-19 MeV/nuc, Li, Be, Bin the energy range of 1.9-26 MeV/nuc, C, N, O in the energy range 2.6-39 MeV/nuc and heavier elements $Z \geq 10$ in various energy ranges i.e. 3.0-75 MeV/nuc. Sectorized data (of 8 sectors covering the full sky) are being measured for protons within the energy ranges of 1.8-8.0 MeV. All channels have a geometrical factor $G=0.58 \text{ cm}^2\text{sr}$, apart from protons (0.9-1.2 MeV), protons (1.2 –3.0 MeV) and alphas (1.0-5.0 MeV/n) which all have a geometrical factor of: $G=9.1 \text{ cm}^2\text{sr}$ (see **Table 2**). 10-min averaged intensities of all the aforementioned species have been delivered to SEPServer.

4 Data Caveats

Known malfunction and caveats of the COSPIN/LET have been reported since almost the beginning of the Ulysses mission [RD3]. In what follows a summary of the known limitations and caveats of the COSPIN/LET data is presented (**Section 4.1**). A quantitative comparison among different instruments of COSPIN has already been performed in RD1 (Figure 7 of RD1), demonstrating the consistency of the COSPIN/LET dataset and a very good agreement with the other instruments. This direct test of the intercalibration of all COSPIN telescopes, with independent determinations of geometrical factors, efficiencies of detection, energy thresholds, etc, demonstrates remarkable consistency. A summary of the features of the dataset that is provided in SEPServer is presented in **Section 4.24.2**.

4.1 Summary of Limitation and Caveats of the COSPIN/LET data

I. Known limitations/caveats [RD2, RD3]:

- Rate channel L1 (which nominally responds to protons in the energy range 0.9-1.2 MeV) is derived from a single-detector measurement, and as such is sensitive to penetrating particles which lose part of their energy in the detector. The background contribution depends on the energy spectrum of the incident particle population, being negligible for (differential) energy spectral slopes of -3.5 or steeper, increasing to 80% of the total counts for a slope of -1.0 or harder.

-
- Rate channel L2 is derived from a single detector measurement, and the nominal energy response to protons (1.2-3.0 MeV) is approximate.
 - Please note that a software error in the LET data reduction algorithm provided incorrect LET sector channels (L4-L11 and L13-L20) for all COSPIN/LET rates data files submitted to the ESA and NASA archive prior to August 2012. Full resolution and 10 minute averaged rates data files issued since September 2012 have corrected proton fluxes for the sector channels.
 - Rate channel L21 (which nominally responds to protons in the energy range 9-19 MeV) is also sensitive to higher-energy particles which lose part of their energy in the telescope structure. As in the case of L1, the background contribution depends on the energy spectrum of the incident particle population, being negligible for (differential) energy spectral slopes of -2.0 or steeper, increasing to 80% of the total counts for a slope of +0.75 or harder.
 - Rate channel L22 is derived from a single detector measurement, and the nominal energy response to alpha particles (1.0-5.0 MeV/n) is approximate.
 - Rate channel L25 (which nominally responds to alpha particles in the energy range 8.4-19.0 MeV/n) is also sensitive to higher energy particles that lose part of their energy in the telescope structure. As in the case of L21, the background contribution depends on the energy spectrum of the incident particle population (negligible for differential energy spectral slopes of -2.0 or steeper).
 - Rate channel L26 suffers from background due to pulse pile-up for proton fluxes in L2 greater than 10 protons/cm²/s/sr/MeV.
 - Rate channel L27 suffers from background due to pulse pile-up for proton fluxes in L2 greater than 30 protons/cm²/s/sr/MeV.
 - The energy for rate channel L28 is approximate (species dependent).
 - The energy for rate channel L29 is approximate (species dependent).
 - The energy for rate channel L30 is approximate (species dependent).

- The energy for rate channel L31 is approximate (species dependent).
- The energy for rate channel L32 is approximate (species dependent).
- The energy range for rate channel L33 is approximate. L33 suffers from background from the RTG and GCR.
- Rate channel L34 includes all particles depositing energy greater than the minimum discriminator level (D1).
- Rate channel L35 includes all particles depositing energy greater than the minimum discriminator level (D2).
- Rate channel L36 includes all particles depositing energy greater than the minimum discriminator level (D3).
- Rate channel L37 includes all particles depositing energy greater than the minimum discriminator level (D4).
- Rate channel L38 includes all particles depositing energy greater than the minimum discriminator level (D5).

II. Background issues from high energy protons [RD2]

Under specific conditions, the LET rate channels L1 and L12 (see **Table 2**) are affected by background from high-energy particles that interact with, i.e. lose energy in, the (passive) internal structure of the telescope. The degree to which this occurs depends on the slope of the differential energy spectrum: the harder the spectrum, the higher the background. A correction procedure has been developed using the results of Monte Carlo simulations of the LET response. Channels L3 and L4, which are coincidence channels and as such effectively unaffected by background events, are used to determine the true spectral slope (γ_0). A correction factor F_c is then applied according to the following equations:

<u>L1</u>	$F_c =$
$\gamma_0 < -3.5$	1.0
$-3.5 \leq \gamma_0 \leq -0.5$	$-0.3 \cdot \gamma_0 - 0.05$

$\gamma_0 > -0.5$	0.0
<hr/>	
<u>L12</u>	
<hr/>	
	$F_c =$
$\gamma_0 < -2.0$	1.0
$-2.0 \leq \gamma_0 \leq +1.25$	$-0.275 \cdot \gamma_0 + 0.45$
$\gamma_0 > +1.25$	0.0

True rate = F_c * measured rate

III. Counting limitations (“roll-over” effect) [RD2]

Channels L1, L2 and L22 (see **Table 2**) show a non-linearity in input rate vs. output rate at high counting rates (see **Figure 5**). This so-called “roll-over” becomes significant above the following *measured* intensities:

L1: $I > 5.0 \cdot 10^3$ particles/cm² s sr MeV/n

L2: $I > 7.5 \cdot 10^2$ particles/cm² s sr MeV/n

L22: $I > 3.0 \cdot 10^2$ particles/cm² s sr MeV/n

At somewhat higher intensities, the response curves turn over, so that ambiguities occur.

Figure 5 LET counting rate linearity curves for channels L1, L2 and L22 [taken by RD2]

4.2 Summary of the COSPIN/LET data

SEPServer provides

1. COSPIN/LET spin-averaged and sectorized measurements
2. A comprehensive description of the data set
3. A remarkable consistent dataset as this has been confirmed by spectrum comparisons, already from [RD1]

SEP Server

Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report Ulysses/HISCALE Instrument description and data quality

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Summary

This document contains the Solar Energetic Particle Instrument Document and Data Quality Report for the SEPServer database server. Herein the following three sections are included:

1. Description the Ulysses/HISCALE instrumentation
2. Data sets delivered
3. Caveats and data quality assessment.

In Section 2 a detailed description on the Ulysses/HISCALE instrumentation is provided. It includes details on the two basic telescopes of HISCALE, namely LEFS and LEMS, together with the basic scientific objectives of the instrument. Section 3 refers to the datasets delivered to SEPServer in terms of the format of the files and contents as well as to special features of the datasets that currently are available through the SEPServer database. Section 4 describes the quality controls and the caveats spotted at the HISCALE data. The RTG background issues are being reported. The results of the detailed checks for solar contamination from solar photons as well as for cross-talk contamination are presented with examples and are tabulated for the whole mission duration. Finally, a summary of the limitations of the dataset is presented at the end of this document.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document contains the Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report (DDR) of the Heliosphere Instrument for Spectra, Composition, and Anisotropy at Low Energies (HISCALE) for the SEP Server database server.

The DDR's roughly break down into the following components:

1. Description the Ulysses/HISCALE instrumentation
2. Data sets delivered
3. Caveats and quality assessment.

Each class of requirements will be detailed in a section of the document.

1.2 Applicable documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
AD1	Description of Work	EC-GA #262773, Annex I	10 Dec 2010
AD2	Data Delivery Plan	SEPSERVER-009-CAU- WP2	02 Oct 2012

1.3 Reference documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
RD1	Heliosphere instrument for spectra,	Lanzerotti, et al.: Astron.	

	composition and anisotropy at low energies.	Astrophys. Suppl. Ser. 92, 349-363, 1992	
RD2	Ulysses HISCALE Data Analysis Handbook	http://hiscale.ftecs.com/uly-handbk-oview.html	
RD3	Low-energy particle response to CMEs during the Ulysses solar maximum northern polar passage	Lario et al., JGR, 109, A01107, doi:10.1029/2003JA010071, 2004	
RD4	Energetic particle fluxes of two large solar events using the EPAM instrument: November 1997 and April 1998	Keeney, A. C., Master's thesis, Johns Hopkins Univ., Laurel, Md, 1999	
RD5	An Analysis of Solar Energetic Particle Spectra Throughout the Inner Heliosphere	Patterson J. D. Ph.D. Thesis, 2002	
RD6	Monte Carlo simulation of MFSA response to RTG gamma rays	Gomez, J., Fundamental Technologies, 1996	
RD7	Near-relativistic electron events. Monte Carlo simulations of solar injection and interplanetary transport	Agueda N., Ph.D. Thesis, Universitat de Barcelona, 2008	

1.4 Abbreviations and acronyms

ACE	Advanced Composition Explorer
CA	Composition Aperture
DDP	Data Delivery Plan
DDR	Data Delivery Report

DE	Deflected Electrons
EPAM	Electron, Proton, and Alpha Monitor
HISCALE	Heliosphere Instrument for Spectra, Composition and Anisotropy at Low Energies
IPM	Interplanetary Medium
LEFS	Low Energy Foil Spectrometers
LEMS	Low Energy Magnetic Spectrometers
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
SEP Server	Data Services and Analysis Tools for Solar Energetic Particle Events and Related Electromagnetic Emissions

2 Ulysses/HISCALE description

The Heliosphere Instrument for Spectra, Composition, and Anisotropy at Low Energies (HISCALE) instrument onboard the Ulysses spacecraft has been described in RD1, RD2 and in RD5. In what follows some parts are repeated in order to better understand the limitation and quality of the data.

HISCALE was constructed to investigate low energy ions and electrons. HISCALE consists of five apertures in two telescope assemblies mounted in a unit that contains the instrument electronics. The opening angles and spin-axis orientations of the telescopes are shown schematically in **Figure 1**. To attain the lowest energy of response over a wide variety of particle species with appropriate geometrical factors and angular resolution, HISCALE utilizes three distinct silicon solid-state detector systems. These are Low-Energy Magnetic/Foil Spectrometers (LEMS/LEFS) and Composition Aperture (CA) [CA; is sometimes called “WART”; the user should note that CA data are not delivered through SEPServer]. The LEMS/LEFS systems provide pulse-height-analysed single-detector measurements with active anticoincidence. The CA system uses a multiparameter detection technique to provide measurements of ion composition in an energy range similar with LEMS/LEFS.

Figure 1 HISCALE viewing cones with respect to Ulysses spin axis [taken by RD1]

The five separate detector systems are contained within two mechanical structures, LAN2A and LAN2B, as shown in **Figure 2**. The individual telescopes are referred to as LEFS 60, LEFS 150, LEMS 30, LEMS 120, and CA 60, where the number indicates the inclination of the telescope axis with respect to the spacecraft spin axis.

Figure 2 LEMS30/LEFS150 and LEFS60/LEMS120 Telescope Assemblies for HISCALE [taken by RD2]

In the LEMS30 and LEMS120 telescopes, electrons with energies below ~ 300 keV are swept away from detectors M and M' with a rare-earth magnet. In the LEFS60 and LEFS150 telescopes, a thin (~ 0.35 mg/cm²) aluminized parylene foil prevents ions (below approximately 350 keV) from reaching the F and F' detector, while electrons (≥ 30 keV) can penetrate the foil with little energy loss. In the LEMS 30 telescope the magnetically-deflected electrons are counted by a separate detector B (see **Figure 2**).

HISCALE measures omni-directional and sectorized data for: pure electrons (Deflected electrons – DEs) in the energy range of 0.038-0.315 MeV with a geometrical factor of 0.14 (cm² sr) in 4 sectors, electrons (from LEFS150) in the energy range of 0.040-0.280 MeV with a geometrical factor of 0.397 (cm²*sr) with a look direction of 150 degrees from the spin axis and 4 sectors, electrons in the energy range of 0.042-0.290 MeV (from LEFS60) with a look angle of 60 degrees to the spin axis in 8 sectors. The geometrical factor for the LEFS60 telescope is 0.397 (cm²*sr). LEMS120 telescope measures ions in the energy range of 0.061-4.752 MeV and presents a geometrical factor of 0.428 (cm²*sr). LEMS30 telescope measures ions in the energy range of 0.056-4.752 MeV with an orientation at 30 degrees from the spin axis in 4 sectors. The geometrical factor for the LEMS30 ions is 0.428 (cm²*sr).

The specific scientific objectives for the HISCALE instrument are as follows [RD5]:

- Use low energy solar particles to monitor changes in structure of the solar corona and interplanetary magnetic fields, specifically as a function of heliolatitude.
- Study solar flare processes through relativistic and non-relativistic electron events and non-relativistic ion events at a range of heliolatitudes.
- Obtain a baseline of solar elemental abundances as a function of heliolatitude and in the active region band.
- Investigate propagation processes for low energy solar particles via the composition and anisotropy components of HISCALE at a range of heliolatitudes.
- Use on-board radio measurements and non-relativistic electron events to study outward-propagating wave-particle interactions as a function of heliolatitude.
- Compare high-heliolatitude particle acceleration processes with known acceleration processes that occur at low heliolatitudes.
- Obtain a better overall model of heliospheric structure and dynamics so that influences upon the terrestrial environment may be better known and predictable

2.1 The low energy Magnetically Shielded (LEMS) Telescopes

The LEMS30 and LEMS120 telescopes use a magnetic field to shield the M and M'

detectors, respectively, from any incoming electrons. **Figure 2** shows the two detectors and the location of the shielding magnets. In the rendition of the LEMS120 telescope, the magnetic field runs from the top pole to the bottom one, and in the illustration of the LEMS30 telescope, the magnetic field is directed into the page. The shielding magnetic field of the LEMS30 telescope directs the incoming electrons toward the bottom detector in the CA60 stack, whereas the electrons entering the LEMS120 telescope are allowed to impact the wall of the telescope housing.

One concern with the LEMS120 telescope is the effect of the electrons scattered from the telescope housing on the observed count rates in the M' detector. It is conceivable that a scattered electron with sufficient energy could be incorrectly interpreted by the detector as a proton. Modeling of this process has shown that this is an unlikely event [RD6].

Another possible source of electron contamination of the M and M' detectors is the arrival of an electron energetic enough to not be deflected sufficiently by the shielding magnetic field and striking the detector. The energy of an electron capable of this, however, is significantly higher than the penetration energy of the detector. Such an occurrence is ignored by the detector electronics [RD5].

The electrons that are deflected by the shielding magnetic field in the LEMS30 telescope are detected by the B detector at the base of the detector stack for the CA60 telescope. The counts measured by this detector are recorded in the four DE (Deflected Electron) channels and can be assumed to be only electrons (i.e. 'pure electrons').

2.2 The low energy Foil Shielded (LEFS) Telescopes

The LEFS60 and LEFS150 telescopes utilize an aluminized Parylene foil, nominally 0.35 mg cm^{-2} thick, to block low energy ions [RD7]. The foil does a modest job of this, but does not work well at all for shielding higher energy ions with energies about 300 keV-nuc^{-1} or greater. Because of this leakage of higher energy ions through the foil shield, the counts recorded by the F and F' detectors are not exclusively electrons, even at low energies. The

ions that pass through the foil deposit energy into the detector that, of course, does not match the incident energy, but is monotonically related to the incident energy.

Another source of contamination is the forward scattering of electrons by energetic ions incident on the foil shield. One way to obtain an estimate of the number of counts attributable to this phenomenon is to compare the F and F' data, corrected for the contributions of ions incident on the detector, with the DE data. When the electron distribution is isotropic, the two means of measuring electron counts should be in good agreement. If forward-scattered electrons provide a significant contribution to the count rates in the F and F' detectors, it will be readily apparent when compared to the DE data (see section 4.3 for details).

3 Data Delivery

3.1 Format of the Ulysses/HISCALE delivered data

The Ulysses/HISCALE data that have been delivered to SEP Server include electron and ion omnidirectional as well as sectorized counting rates. The two LEFS telescopes measure the flux and direction of electrons above 30 keV while the two LEMS telescopes measure the flux and direction of ions above 50 keV. Sectorized data have been delivered for all telescopes in all energy ranges. These counting rates consist of 8 sectors for ions and 4 sectors for electrons with 12 sec time resolution. All data have been provided in ASCII files. The files format of the Ulysses/HISCALE data delivered to SEP Server has been described in details the Data Delivery Plan (DDP) [AD2].

3.2 Special features of the delivered datasets

The Ulysses/HISCALE data that have been delivered to SEP Server are unique in the sense that those include apart from the actual count and the timestamp for both the sectorized and omni-directional sets, the duty cycle, the accumulation time and the uncertainty for each entry in the datasets (see AD2 for details).

4 HISCALE Caveats and Quality Assessment

The power source for Ulysses is a radioisotope thermoelectric generator (RTG). The RTG produces a spray of gamma rays that contribute strongly to the low energy background counts (see Section 4.1). There are some troublesome solar X-ray influences in the LEMS30 detector at times (see Section 4.2). Furthermore, contamination arises from electrons recorded as ions and vice versa (see Section 4.3).

4.1 Radiothermal Generator Background in HISCALE

The RTG used by Ulysses produces a spectrum of gamma rays that penetrate the side walls of the four telescopes. These gamma rays Compton-scatter electrons in the wafer or neighboring hardware which then may be recorded by the detector electronics as a count. The gamma ray spectrum was measured in a pre-flight test and the induced rates in the various HI-SCALE detectors were recorded for a 120-second accumulation. These data were recorded in 1984 and the spacecraft was launched in 1990, so the gamma ray spectrum of the RTG has changed slightly as a result of the changing abundances of the radioisotopes within the RTG; but the rate of change is slow, and not significant over even the twenty-year duration of the Ulysses flight [RD5].

4.2 Solar Contamination

During half of the spin of the spacecraft, the LEMS30 telescope is exposed directly to the solar disc and, therefore, solar X-rays. For HISCALE, the contamination is not tremendously severe. Only sectors 1 and 4 of LEMS30 show signs of saturation by solar photons. Sectors 2 and 3 are unaffected (see Figure 3 and **Table 1**).

Table 1 DOYs with X-ray contamination for the whole mission

Year	Day of Year	Description of the problem
1991	1-365	Channels P1, P2: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
1992	1-39, 46-366	ok
	40-45	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P8: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3

1993	1-233	ok
	234-334	Channels P1: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	335-365	Channels P1, P2: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
1994	1-365	Channels P1, P2: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
1995	1-365	Channels P1, P2: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
1996	1-366	Channels P1: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
1997	1-365	ok
1998	1-365	ok
1999	1-310	ok
	311-365	Channels P1: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
2000	1-339	Channels P1, P2, P3: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	340-366	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
2001	1-365	Channels P1, P2, P3: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
2002	3-99, 104-148, 179, 300-365	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	1-2, 100-103, 149-178, 180-299	ok
2003	6-109, 142-365	ok
	1-5	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	110-141	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
2004	1-366	ok
2005	1-160, 165-181, 190-319	ok
	161-164	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	182-189	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	327-365	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
2006	1-24	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	25-50	Channel P1: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	50-91	Channel P1: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	92-200	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	200-216	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3

	217-280	Channels P1, P2, P3: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	281-365	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
2007	1-84	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	85-90	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P8: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	91-149	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	150-279	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P8: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	280-309	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	310-353	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	354-365	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
	2008	1-99
100-149		Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
150-366		Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3
2009	1-181	Channels P1, P2: Solar Contamination in sectors S1, S4. We must use only sectors S2, S3

Figure 3 X-ray contamination as spotted in the high-resolution HISCALE data for DOY 365 in 1999 (right panel) versus non-contaminated rates on DOY 303 in 1999 (left panel).

4.3 Cross-talk

Electrons are magnetically deflected in the LEMS30 and LEMS120 telescopes, and those deflected from the LEMS30 telescope are detected by an off-axis detector that separates them in four different energy channels referred to as DE1–4 or ‘pure electrons’ [RD3]. This magnetic deflection system diverts a very high fraction of electrons that enter the LEMS collimators. However, when the >50 keV electron flux is sufficiently high, some electrons are counted in the LEMS30 and LEMS120 telescopes, even though the absolute efficiency for counting these electrons is quite small. Thus the ion channels may be contaminated at the beginning of large SEP events when many electrons arrive promptly, well before the slower ions can reach the spacecraft [RD4].

Furthermore, contamination from ions is possible in the LEFS60 data. Therefore, we qualitatively compare clean electron measurements (from DEs) to LEFS60 data and to ion measurements (from LEMS120). When data are not contaminated we expect similar trends in the electron profiles observed by the two telescopes. If we spot a significant difference then we compare the electron profile from LEFS60 to the ion profile from LEMS120. Usually, when contamination is present these latter profiles follow each other’s trend. An example of such comparison is presented in Figure 4 and the corresponding results are tabulated in **Table 2**

ULYSSES/HISCALE spin-averaged data E'1, P'1, DE1 channels, Year 1991

Data time-resolution: ~2min

E' chan. (LEFS60) -----
DE chan. (LEMS30) -----
P' chan. (LEMS120) -----

— Fitting curve (method: running averaging, window width:7)

Figure 4 Example of the comparison between E's (LEFS60), P's (LEMS120) (top panel), DE (LEMS30) (middle panel) and the ratio between E's and DEs (bottom panel). The contamination is clear from (DOY/HOUR) 321/00:00-321/12:10:00, noted by the coloured vertical box.

Table 2 DOYs with contamination due to cross-talk

Year	Day of Year	Description of the problem
1991	001,00:00 – 320,00:00 321,12:00 – 365,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	320,00:00 - 321,12:00	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions
1992	001,00:00 - 052,05:00 053,00:00 - 202,03:30 202,19:00 - 366,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	052,05:00 - 053,00:00 202,03:30 - 202,19:00	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions
1993	001,00:00 – 365,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
1994	001,00:00 – 365,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
1995	001,00:00 – 365,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
1996	001,00:00 – 266,16:00 296,12:00 – 366,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	266,16:00 – 296,12:00	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels)
1997	001,00:00 – 365,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
1998	001,00:00 – 358,13:00 359,00:00 – 365,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	358,13:00 - 358,24:00	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions

1999	001,00:00 – 018,24:00 019,04:30 - 019,13:00 019,16:30 - 069,08:00 069,15:00 - 194,22:00 235,00:00 - 365,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	019,00:00 - 019,04:30 019,13:00 - 019,16:30 069,08:00 - 069,15:00 194,22:00 - 234,24:00	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions
2000	001,00:00 – 366,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
2001	001,00:00 – 365,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
2002	001,00:00 – 060,24:00 063,22:30 – 262,00:00 263,00:00 - 361,00:00 364,00:00 – 365,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	061,00:00 - 063,22:30 262,00:00 - 262,24:00 361,00:00 - 363,24:00	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions
2003	001,00:00 – 365,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
2004	001,00:00 - 013,00:00 014,20:00 - 051,00:00 078,03:00 – 114,09:00 115,00:00 – 333,00:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	013,00:00 - 014,20:00 051,00:00 - 078,03:00 114,09:00 - 114,24:00 333,00:00 - 366,24:00	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions
2005	001,00:00 - 115,00:00 116,00:00 – 260,04:00 290,00:00 – 365,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	115,00:00 - 115,24:00 260,04:00 - 289,24:00	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions
2006	001,00:00 - 118,11:00 156,12:00 – 365,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two

		telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	118,11:00 - 156,12:00	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions
2007	001,00:00 - 365,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
2008	001,00:00 - 058,03:00 063,00:00 - 366,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	058,03:00 - 062,24:00	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions
2009	001,00:00 - 181,24:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated

4.4 Summary of Limitation and Caveats of the HISCALE data

Known limitations/caveats:

1. The HISCALE instrument was commanded into in-flight calibration mode on 5 occasions. Foreground measurements are not valid at these times (1990 Day 319; 1992 Day 9, Day 49; 1993 Day 8; 1994 Day 91).
2. Solar X-ray contamination tabulated results present in **Table 1**
3. Cross-talk contamination results tabulated in **Table 2**

SEPServer

Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report

Wind 3DP Instrument description and data quality

	Name	Signature	Date
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DISTRIBUTION

Name	Organisation

CHANGE LOG

Date	Issue	Rev.	Pages	Reason for change
01.01.2013	0.1			First draft
29.4.2013	1.	0		Consolidation of team inputs
01.10.2013	1	1	Several	Summary supplemented Comment on cross-talk between electron and proton channels added Figure showing preliminary results of electron correction method added
24.10.2013	1.	2.	Several	Comments from the PI inserted

Summary and Recommendation

This document contains the Wind/3DP part of the Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report (SEP DDR) for the SEPServer database server. In this part of the SEP DDR the Solid State Telescopes (SST) of the 3DP instrument aboard the Wind spacecraft is described. The Wind/3DP SST data delivered for SEPServer are also summarized and the functional characteristics and caveats of the instrument are described. In addition to the introduction the following three sections are included in this document:

1. Description the 3DP instrumentation
2. Summary of the data sets delivered
3. Caveats and data quality assessment

The functional and operational characteristics of the Wind/3DP SST instrument and the generation and processing of the data provided for SEPServer require the user to take into account in particular the following data quality issues.

1. Effect of photon contamination (Section 4.1)

Sectors pointing directly towards the Sun/anti-Sun directions are affected from irradiation effects from the Sun, mostly by X-rays emitted in the first 10 minutes of a solar flare. The measurements were cleaned by omitting these sectors, but remaining effects in neighboring sectors might still be present. They can be clearly identified by an experienced user or a request can be sent to sepserver-WP2@helsinki.fi

2. Cross-Talk between Electron and Proton channels (Section 4.2)

Occasionally apparent intensity increases are observed in both electron and proton channels, which in fact are caused by the other particle species in the corresponding energy channel. There is no correction available for misidentification of protons in the electron channels and vice versa. Therefore, electron data during periods of high proton intensities at energies above 400 keV should not be used for scientific analysis. The onset analysis in the proton channel requires a careful cross checking with the electron intensity time profiles using the electron channels with energies above a few hundreds of keV.

3. Distortion in energy channels (Section 4.3)

It was found that an approximately 15% of incident electrons will scatter back out of the detector before fully depositing their incident energy. Due to this effect, electrons with energies corresponding to higher energy channels could contaminate the energy channels below in solar events with hard electron spectra. Since this effect is different from event to event no general correction can be performed. But it is known to be only important for very hard electron spectra as observed during the onset of solar electron events. Thus the results of an onset time analysis or velocity dispersion analysis may lead to unphysical results. The user should be aware that time periods with hard or even inverted electron spectra might suffer from this effect.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document contains the Data Delivery Report part for the 3DP instrument aboard the Wind spacecraft for the SEP Server database server.

This document roughly breaks down into the following components:

1. Description the 3DP instrumentation
2. Summary of the data sets delivered
3. Caveats and data quality assessment

Each class of requirements will be detailed in a section of the document.

1.2 Applicable documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
AD1	Description of Work	EC-GA #262773, Annex I	10 Dec 2010
AD2	Data Delivery Plan	SEPSERVER-009-CAU-WP2	02-Oct-2012
AD3	SEP Server Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: Spacecraft descriptions and data comparison	SEPSERVER-010-00-CAU-WP2	24-Sep-2013

1.3 Reference documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
RD1	A Three- Dimensional Plasma and Energetic Particle Investigation for the Wind Spacecraft.	R. P. Lin, et al. (1995) Space Sci. Rev., 71:125-153.	
RD2	Testing Transport Theories with Solar Energetic Particles	W. Dröge and Y. Y. Kartavykh, (2009) Astrophs. J., 693:69-74.	

1.4 Abbreviations and acronyms

3DP	3-D Plasma
DDP	Data Delivery Plan
DDR	Instrument Description Document and Quality Report
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SST	Solid State Telescope
UNI WUE	Julius-Maximilians Universität Würzburg

2 Instrument

2.1 Wind 3DP Solid State Telescopes

Each of the five double-ended semi-conductor detectors mounted on board the WIND spacecraft covers a $36^\circ \times 20^\circ$ spherical section. Together they have a $180^\circ \times 20^\circ$ field of view, which is enlarged to the full spherical surface by the spinning of the spacecraft.

The detectors are designed to measure particles with energies that exceed 20 keV but stay well below the energies of normal cosmic rays. While the one end of the telescope is covered with a lexan foil of adequate thickness to prevent the protons below 400 keV from penetrating the detector on the other end of the telescope a broom magnet prevents the electrons below 400 keV from penetrating the detector (see Figure 1). This leaves the ion and electron spectra essentially unchanged and just filters out the ions from the electron detector and the electrons from the ion detector. Therefore one aperture of the double-ended telescope detects only electrons and the other aperture only protons assuming that the amount of protons and electrons with higher energies than 400 keV is negligible. Additional telescopes (SSTs) with lower geometry-factor, which cover the area from 36 to 72 degrees measure particles at even energies, in the range from 400 keV to 1 MeV for electrons and from 6MeV to 11MeV for protons, and at high fluxes. The measurements of this telescope are redundant during normal conditions [RD1].

Figure 1 Double-ended semi-conductor telescopes used on the WIND spacecraft. Broom magnets filter out the electrons if the particles enter the magnet side collimator while a lexan foil prevents the penetration of protons to the foil side collimator [RD1].

3 Data delivered

3.1 The Wind3D/SST data structure

The measurements are stored in a three-dimensional data structure including the directions of the incoming particles and the number of particles detected in every direction ('Counts'). Particles are binned in 40 sectors of approximately the same size, which are represented by their phi and theta angles (Fig. 2). In addition to those 40 sectors there are 8 sectors with low geometry-factors for the measurement of high fluxes, which are not used here. The data contained in the original structure have to be cleaned from sectors, which are distorted by direct or scattered X-ray irradiation emitted from the Sun during a solar flare (see Fig. 3). The particle fluxes from the remaining sectors are rebinned into a pitch-angle distribution with 8 evenly spaced sectors. An example is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Temporal evolution of the electron flux in different pitch angle intervals before during and after the solar particle event on 18th February 2000 in the 108 keV electron channel.

3.2 Technical specifications of the data sets

Electron and proton fluxes measured with the Wind 3DP SST were delivered to the consortium in the form of text files containing data in ASCII format. The file name defines the instrument (always Wind 3DP), the time (year, month, day), the particle species (electrons or protons), omnidirectional or sectorized data, and the energy channel for sectorized data. The Wind 3DP SST has 7 channels (E1 – E7) for electrons, which are named by the approximate mean value of their energy intervals in units of keV (27, 40, 66, 108, 182, 311, 519). Similarly, the 9 channels for protons (P1 – P9) are named by the approximate mean value of their energy intervals, also in units of keV (74, 128, 197, 333, 552, 1018, 2074, 4440, 6755). Four types of files were created from the Wind/3DP data sets, which were made available by the University of California, Berkeley, in CDF format files (<http://sprg.ssl.berkeley.edu/wind3dp/data/wi/3dp/>). Each of those files contains data for one day in the energy intervals defined in Table 1 and Table 2. The time period covered is from the launch of Wind in November 1994 through the end of 2010. Due to temporary malfunctioning of the SST instrument there are no data for the time intervals 2006/12/02 – 2007/07/30 and 2009/09/09 – 2010/05/10.

Table 1 Energy characteristic of SST Electron channel (Foil)

Energy Range (keV)	Mean Energy (keV)	Acronym
24-30	27	E1
30-50	40	E2
50-82	66	E3
80-135	108	E4
135-230	182	E5
230-392	311	E6
392-646	519	E7

Table 2 Energy characteristic of SST Proton channel (Magnetic)

Energy Range (keV)	Mean Energy (keV)	Acronym
47-101	74	P1
101-156	128	P2
156-238	197	P3
238-429	333	P4
429-676	552	P5
676-1360	1018	P6
1360-2787	2074	P7
2787-6092	4440	P8
6423-7087	6755	P9

The relation between the names of the files and the data they contain are in the following exemplarily given for Wind 3DP SST particle observations for 11 November 1997. We keep the notations of the University of Berkeley data sets: "sf" for electrons, "so" for protons, "sp" for sector-averaged intensities, "pd" for pitch-angle distributions.

Data set 2.1 includes one file for electron intensities for the 7 energy channels described above. The intensities are averaged over the 40 sectors of the instrument, which continuously cover the full three-dimensional particle distribution. These data are therefore always close to the "omni-directional" intensities. According to the above convention, the file name for the content of the data set is: "wind3dp_sfsp_19971104.txt".

Data set 2.2 includes one file for proton intensities for the 9 energy channels described above. Accordingly, the file name for the content of the data set is: "wind3dp_sosp_19971104.txt".

Data set 2.3 includes 7 files with directional electron intensities for the 7 electron energies. Here the original 40 angular sectors have been reduced to 8 pitch-angle bins. Also magnetic field data in GSE coordinates are provided. Accordingly, the name for one file (for ~40 keV electrons) in the data set is: "win3dp_sfpd_E2_19971104.txt".

Data set 2.4 includes 9 files with directional proton intensities for the 9 proton energies. Here the original 40 angular sectors have been reduced to 8 pitch-angle bins. Also magnetic field data in GSE coordinates are provided. Accordingly, the name for one file (for ~ 333 keV proton) in the data set is: "win3dp_sopd_P4_19971104.txt". Each data set contains data for one day. The exact formats of the data files are given in [AD2].

4 Caveats and Data Quality assesment

4.1 Photon contamination

WIND/3DP data from the three pairs of double ended semiconductor detector telescopes of electrons in seven energy channels between approximately 27 and 510 keV and of protons in nine energy channels between approximately 0.068 and 7 MeV were provided by the PI institute to UNI WUE. The measurements were cleaned from irradiation effects from the sun (mostly X-rays which produce counts in sun / anti-sun sectors). Questionable data are flagged. The time resolution of the data provided by the University of Berkeley of 12 seconds is reduced to 1 minute for electrons and to 5 minutes for protons. The time value given in the data files denotes the middle of the time interval.

4.2 Cross-Talk between Electron and Proton channels

Occasionally apparent intensity increases are observed in both electron and proton channels, which in fact are caused by the other particle species in the corresponding energy channel (e.g., E4/P4). Usually proton channels are affected in the early phases of particle events when large numbers of electrons arrive first due to their higher speed. Correspondingly, electron channels are affected at later times, in particular during ESP-events. A method to correct the Wind/3DP SST data for the effects of electron-proton cross talk is currently not available.

4.3 Corrected Electron Intensities

It had been noted (Wang 2009, PhD Thesis, University of California, Berkeley) that an approximately 15% of incident electrons will scatter back out of the detector before fully depositing their incident energy. Due to this effect, electrons with energies corresponding to higher energy channels could contaminate the energy channels below in events with hard electron spectra. This contamination can lead to significant errors in the transport modeling of electrons in the lower energy channels. An attempt to compute corrected intensities by means of a matrix equation, i.e.,

$$I_m = C_{mn} i_n$$

where I and i denote the corrected and uncorrected intensities, respectively, $n, m = 1, \dots, 7$ denote the number of the electron channel from lowest to highest energy, C_{mn} are elements of the correction matrix and the summation runs over n . A preliminary result from applying a correction matrix based on phenomenological considerations to the omni-directional intensities is shown in Figure 5. It becomes apparent from the figure that a reliable reconstruction of the intensities in the lower energy channels is important for onset analyses and transport modeling (see RD2).

It is planned to determine more advanced correction matrices from results of GEANT simulations of the detector response, and to verify them by applying them to sectorized data for a number of electron events with different energy spectra. Once they become available, the user will have the opportunity to apply them to the uncorrected data files.

Figure 5 Corrected (red) and uncorrected (black) Wind 3DP electron fluxes in different energy ranges during the solar particle event on 20 October 2002. The corrected fluxes were obtained with the matrix scheme indicated above.

SEP Server

Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report (II)

SOHO/EPHIN Instrument Description and Data Quality Report

	Name	Signature	Date
Prepared by	B. Heber		31.8.2013
Checked by	E. Valtonen		31.8.2013
Approved by	R. Vainio		

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Name	Organisation

CHANGE LOG

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	1.	1		Consolidation of team inputs
31.08.2013	1.	2.		Implementation of suggestions from the reviewer

Summary

This document contains the Solar Energetic Particle Instrument Document and Data Quality Report for the SEP Server database server. Herein the following sections are included:

1. Description the SOHO COSTEP/EPHIN instrumentation
2. Details and caveats
3. Data delivery and quality assessment

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document contains the Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report (DDR) of the Electron Proton Helium INstrument (EPHIN) for the SEP Server database server.

The DDR can be subdivided into the following components:

- a. Description the SOHO COSTEP/EPHIN instrumentation
- b. Details and caveats
- c. Data delivery and quality assessment

1.2 Applicable documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
AD1	Description of Work	EC-GA #262773, Annex I	10 Dec 2010
AD2	SEPServer SEP Data Delivery Plan	SEPSERVER-009-CAU-WP2	02 Oct 2012
AD3	SEPServer Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: Spacecraft descriptions and data comparison	SEPSERVER-010-00-CAU-WP2	

1.3 Reference documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
RD1	COSTEP – Comprehensive Suprathermal and Energetic Particle Analyser.	R. Müller-Mellin et al.: Sol. Phys., 162: 483-504, 1995.	
RD2	Regularization methods used in error analysis of solar particle spectra measured on SOHO/EPHIN.	A. Kharytonov, E. Böhm, and R. F. Wimmer-Schweingruber: Astron. & Astroph. 495: 663-675, 2009.	
RD3	Semiconductor detector systems	H. Spieler: Oxford University Press, USA, 2005.	
RD4	Geometrical factor and directional response of single and multielement particle telescopes.	Nuclear Instruments and methods, 95:5; 11, 1971.	

1.4 Abbreviations and acronyms

ACE	Advanced Composition Explorer
CEPAC	COSTEP/ERNE particle analyser collaboration (SOHO)
COSPIN	Cosmic and Solar Particle Investigation (Ulysses)
COSTEP	Comprehensive Suprathermal and Energetic Particle Analyser (SOHO)
DDP	Data Delivery Plan
DDR	Data Delivery Report
EPAM	Electron, Proton, and Alpha Monitor (ACE)
EPHIN	Electron Proton Helium Instrument (SOHO, Chandra)
ERNE	Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron (SOHO)
FoV	Field of View
HISCALE	Heliosphere Instrument for Spectra, Composition and Anisotropy at Low Energies (Ulysses)
KET	Kiel Electron Telescope (Ulysses)
LET	Low Energy Telescope (Ulysses)
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SIS	Solar Isotope Spectrometer (ACE)
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
TBA	To be added
TBC	To be confirmed
TBD	To be described
UB	University of Barcelona
UH	University of Helsinki
UNI WUE	Julius-Maximilians Universität Würzburg
U. Turku	University of Turku
3DP	3-D Plasma Analyzer (Wind)

2 Instrument description of the SOHO EPHIN

The SOHO EPHIN instrument has been described in Müller-Mellin et al. (1995) and Kharytonov et al. (2009). In what follows some parts are repeated in order to better understand the limitation and quality of the data.

The EPHIN instrument (Electron Proton Helium INstrument) forms part of the COSTEP experiment (Comprehensive Suprathermal and Energetic Particle Analyser) within the CEPAC collaboration on-board of the SOHO spacecraft (SOlar and Heliospheric Observatory, see AD3. The EPHIN sensor is a multi-element array of solid-state detectors with anti-coincidence to measure energy spectra of electrons in the range 250 keV to > 8.7 MeV, and hydrogen and helium isotopes in the range 4 MeV/n to > 53 MeV/n.

The sensor head consists of a stack of six silicon detectors, surrounded by an anti-coincidence shield of plastic scintillator (see Figure 1). Two passivated ion-implanted detectors (A and B) define the 83° full width conical field of view with a geometric factor of $5.1 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sr}$. Detectors A and B are divided into six segments. This coarse position sensing permits sufficient correction for path length variations (resulting from the large field of view) needed to resolve isotopes of hydrogen and helium. Another important advantage of segmentation is the capability to implement a commandable or self-adaptive geometric factor. On detection of high count rates in the centre segment A_0 , the logic will disable all but the inner circular segments of both detectors A and B, reducing the effective geometric factor by a factor of 24 to permit measurements of fluxes as high as $10^6 \text{ counts}/(\text{cm}^2 \text{ s sr})$ without significant dead time losses (compare the geometric factors for status flags 71 and 69 in Table 2). The lithium-drifted detectors C, D, and E stop electrons up to 10 MeV and hydrogen and helium nuclei up to 53 MeV/n. The ion-implanted detector F allows particles stopping in the telescope to be distinguished from penetrating particles. The fast plastic scintillation detector G, viewed by a 1 inch photomultiplier and used in anti-coincidence, helps to reduce background. The inner titanium foil ensures light tightness and closes the electrical shielding of the sensor while the outer aluminized Kapton foil is needed for thermal control.

Figure 1: EPHIN sensor schematics

The instrument registers counts in a fixed accumulation interval of 59.953 seconds. A subset of counting rates in the data products for level-2 and higher are already converted into intensities [counts/(cm² s sr MeV/n)] by dividing the counting rates [counts/s] through the intensity factor:

$$\text{Intensity Factor} = \text{Geometry Factor} \times \text{Energy Window} \quad [\text{cm}^2 \text{ sr MeV/n}]$$

The intensity factors vary with observation modes of EPHIN. The corresponding status flags have been summarized in Table 2 of section 2.1. For SEPServer only data for the observation modes summarized in Table 1 are provided. The geometry factors and energy windows are given in Table 2. It is important to note:

- No energy window is given for the integral counter INT. The geometry factor given is twice the forward incident factor assuming an idealized response for forward and backward incident particles. The actual factor is somewhat lower due to absorption in the spacecraft matter.
- Switching ring segments off (status flag 71) does not change the energy window substantially.

Table 1. EPHIN modes that are allowed for data delivery to the SEP Server database

Observation Mode	Description	Status flag
nominal mode	high voltage on, all detectors logically on	0
failure mode E	high voltage on, detector E logically off, detector E patch uploaded	5
failure mode E	high voltage on, detector E logically off, detector E patch uploaded, automatic ring segment switching enabled	69
ring A/B off	high voltage on, detector E logically off, detector E patch uploaded, segments A1 ... A5 and B1 ... B5 logically off and respective preamplifiers power off	71

Note:

Data from inflight testing or other modes of operation as described in Table 3 are excluded.

Table 2 EPHIN nominal energy ranges and geometry factors

Electrons				Protons				Helium			
Energy Range [MeV]	Geometric factor [cm ² sr]			Energy Range [MeV]	Geometric factor [cm ² sr]			Energy Range [MeV/n]	Geometric factor [cm ² sr]		
	Status flag				Status flag				Status flag		
	0	5 / 69	71		0	5 / 69	71		0	5 / 69	71
0.25 - 0.70	0.25	0.25	0.01	4.30 – 7.80	5.14	5.14	0.18	4.30 - 7.80	5.14	5.14	0.18
0.67 - 3.00	1.78	1.78	0.14	7.80 – 25.0	5.14	5.14	0.18	7.80 - 25.0	5.14	5.14	0.18
2.64 - 6.18	2.01	----	----	25.0 – 40.9	4.77	----	----	25.0 - 40.9	4.77	----	----
4.80 - 10.4	1.58	----	----	40.9 – 53.0	3.8	----	----	40.9 - 53.0	3.8	----	----
2.64 - 10.4	----	1.80	0.11	25.0 – 53.0	----	4.29	0.18	25.0 - 53.0	----	4.29	0.18

Note:

In failure mode E the two highest energy ranges are combined (marked in red).

2.1 EPHIN status flag

The EPHIN status flag shall facilitate the use of the EPHIN dataset. The contents of the status flag is a decimal code, which results from the summation of the flag bit values (see Table 3).

The SEPServer files contain only data for the nominal modes (0), mode with Failure mode E (1), mode with Failure mode E and E patch uploaded (5) and Ring segment switching enabled (69) and Failure mode E, Ring switching enabled and Ring A/B off (71). Other modes have been omitted for simplicity.

Table 3. Interpretation of the EPHIN status flag

Flag Bit Value	Remarks
0	Nominal observation, i.e. high voltage ON, no failure mode, ring segment switching disabled
1	Failure mode E
2	Ring A/B OFF
4	E patch uploaded
8	Commissioning
16	Standby or maintenance, i.e. high voltage OFF
32	Calibration, i.e. test mode
64	Ring segment switching enabled
128	TBD

3 Data Caveats and Corrections

3.1 Energetic photon contamination

Contamination of electron and some proton channels can occur due to hard X-ray emission with energies >30 keV during strong solar X-ray flares with importance of $\geq X1$. Duration of such contamination is a few minutes (up to 10 minutes for very strong X-ray

flares of $\geq X10$). Figure 2 displays as an example the November 6 event showing that these contaminations usually occur some minutes before the first true electrons reach the EPHIN detector. Due to the measurement principle we believe that these entries are caused by random coincidences.

Figure 2: Intensity time profile showing the sensitivity of the electron channel to a strong hard X-ray flare on November 6, 1997.

3.2 Particle identification

In a solid-state charged particle telescope such as EPHIN, the only quantities one has available to identify a particle incident on the telescope are the energy deposited in the various detectors of the stack as it comes to rest, and the incident direction of the particle. EPHIN consists of 5 detectors A through E of varying but known thicknesses, whose signals are energy analysed.

The detector F and the anticoincidence detector G ensure that the particle entered from a limited range of directions, has deposited all its energy and not escaped unseen. Their signals must exceed a threshold above the noise level, but otherwise are not energy analysed.

Knowledge of the angle of incidence of the particle relative to the stack normal direction is

needed to determine the increase of the pathlength in a detector as this increases the energy deposit. To separate electrons, protons, and heavier nuclei, it is sufficient to limit the half-angle opening cone (42° for EPHIN). To separate protons, deuterons, tritons, ^3He nuclei, and ^4He nuclei, the uncertainty in the angle should be less than 25° (accomplished by segmenting A and B detectors in EPHIN, see Figure 1). So in what follows only parallel coincidences are used, i.e. particles trigger the same segments in detectors A and B.

3.2.1 The dE/dx vs. total energy method

A particle of charge z and mass m enters a telescope made up of a thin front and a thick rear detector. It will deposit energy ΔE in the front and E^* (= total energy – ΔE) in the rear detector. The mean energy loss per unit path length dE/dx is given by the Bethe-Bloch formula and can be approximated in the EPHIN energy range by

$$\frac{dE}{dx} \propto \frac{z^2}{v^2}$$

where v is the velocity of the particle. The total kinetic energy of the particle is

$$E = \frac{mv^2}{2}$$

Taking the product of these two quantities yields mz^2 , which is independent of the particle's velocity, only a function of its mass and charge:

$$\frac{dE}{dx} \bullet E \propto mz^2$$

A plot of dE/dx vs. E over a range of velocities forms a band of hyperbolae of constant mz^2 . Tracks for different elements have a wider spacing, with several more closely spaced tracks corresponding to different isotopes of the element. This results from the quadratic dependence on z and the linear dependence on m .

3.2.2 Application to EPHIN flight data

For EPHIN, the energy deposit in detector A can approximate the derivative dE/dx , while E can be approximated by the sum of the energy deposits in detectors A through E. Figure 3 demonstrates the dE/dx vs. E method with flight data from 31-OCT-2004 (day of year 305). Penetrating events are excluded. The track in the upper right corresponds to helium between 16 and 100 MeV (4 – 25 MeV/n), the branch in the middle are protons between 4 and 25 MeV, the area in the lower left are electrons between 0.2 and 2 MeV. Electrons, because of their multiscattering ability, are not organized along tracks. While the nuclei tracks would show a broader distribution if all incidence directions were accepted (half cone angle 42°) the hydrogen and helium isotopes are clearly separated if the uncertainty in the angle of incidence is limited to 25° . During quiet time periods, nearly every incident particle is pulse height analyzed. During high fluxes, only a sample can be pulse height analyzed due to AD converter dead time. However, nearly all incident particles are counted in the coincidence channels. In the coincidence conditions, a threshold in the A detector at $A_1=270$ keV is used to separate electrons from nuclei. It is evident from

Figure 3 that a modest amount of electrons will be mistaken as protons. Whether it is negligible depends on the ratio of electrons to protons in the particle event. The correction method described below uses in the first step masks around the nuclei tracks and determines the ratio of entries inside these masks to the total matrix entries. In a second step this ratio has to be normalized with the associated counting rates.

Figure 3: dE/dx vs. E distribution from the EPHIN instrument on October 31, 2004. The different tracks for ${}^4\text{He}$, ${}^3\text{He}$, protons ${}^1\text{H}$ and electrons are observed.

In the double logarithmic representation of Figure 3, the helium track shows nearly a linear dependence with a negative slope of -1, i.e. the characteristic $1/v^2$ or $1/E$ behaviour expected from the Bethe-Bloch formula. The slight deviation at its low energy end results from the breakdown of the assumption, that ΔE in detector A can serve as a good approximation for dE/dx , as these particles lose a large fraction of their energy already in the first detector. It can be approximated by a hyperbola with a pole at $x=a$. Hence we have fitted the function

$$y(x) = y_0 + m(x - x_0) + \frac{z}{x - a}$$

to specifically selected flight data with low electron contamination after parameterizing the logarithm of the energy deposits in a two-dimensional 400 * 200 field. The coordinates x_0 and y_0 are picked from the linear branch of the curve, the variables m , z , and a are determined from the curve fitting procedure. The best fit for the helium track is obtained by

$$y(x) = 138.9 - 0.389(x - 250) + \frac{668}{x - 147.6}$$

Scaling back to energy in MeV we obtain for the energy deposit in detector A:

$$\Delta E(x - 178) = 10^{-0.7 + \left(138.9 - 0.389(x - 250) + \frac{668}{x - 147.6}\right) / 100}$$

and for the total energy deposit in detectors A through C:

$$E(x - 178) = 10^{0.3 + \frac{x}{200}}$$

3.2.3 How to apply the proton masks

In a first step, the logarithms of the ΔE vs. E matrix will be rotated by 45°, applicable to both the helium calibration track described in Section 3.2.2 and to the EPHIN PHA events condensed in detector A energy deposit y and total energy deposit x . The coordinate transformation is

$$x = \log E$$

$$y = \log \Delta E$$

$$x' = x \cos \varphi + y \sin \varphi$$

$$y' = -x \sin \varphi + y \cos \varphi$$

$$\varphi = 45^\circ \Rightarrow \sin \varphi = \cos \varphi = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$$

$$x' = 0.707107 \log(E \cdot \Delta E)$$

$$y' = 0.707107 \log\left(\frac{\Delta E}{E}\right)$$

The matrix after rotation is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4: (ΔE times E vs. E divided by ΔE) - matrix

In a second step, the logarithm of the horizontal distance of a given PHA event to the helium calibration curve is calculated. The event is classified as electron, proton, or helium nucleus according to the following mask:

Table 4 Mass identification criteria

Particle species	Mask
electron	$\log \text{ distance} < - 1.5$
proton	$-1.5 < \log \text{ distance} < - 0.5$
helium and heavier	$\log \text{ distance} > - 0.5$

A histogram generated from the entries in Figure 5 is shown in Figure 6

Figure 5: Mass histogram

The priority scheme of the EPHIN pulse height analysis system does not alter the relative abundances for a given coincidence. Thus, the ratio of the events within the mask to the total number of entries in the matrix yields a correction factor between 0 and 1, which allows correcting the corresponding rate channel.

An example of uncorrected and corrected P4 and E150 rates is given in Figure 7 and Figure 8. The increase early on day of year 304 is caused by electrons and later by genuine protons.

3.3 Deadtime correction

When a large particle flux is entering the telescope, an instrumental feature called “dead time” can occur, which inhibits the instrument from processing all of the incoming particles, due to processing time being longer than the delay between subsequent events. The crucial parts of the instrument regarding this effect are the electronics, which handle the data acquisition for every detector. Different steps in the processing chain of detector

signals can be responsible for the electronics being unable to process the next upcoming event (Spieler, 2005):

- ✓ Time to acquire a signal, based on the slope of the amplifier signal peaking over time and the subsequent settling of the amplifier signal back to the baseline
- ✓ Time to convert the signal in the ADC, which depends on the signal peak
- ✓ Time to store the data in memory, which depends on the memory speed and bandwidth

Effects of deadtime can be ignored in cases where the time between Poisson-distributed incoming pulses (like in extra-terrestrial particle distributions) is sufficiently larger than the combined time of these processing steps, since the case of two events occurring in the time window of instrument dead time is very rare. Generally, for a telescope designed to study interplanetary particles, this is true for solar quiet times, which show much decreased particle fluxes compared to solar events. However, it is important to estimate the deadtime when generating particle spectra for solar events, since otherwise the particle fluxes will be underestimated.

In case of the EPHIN the correction due to instrument deadtime had not been used until this work, and became possible after the calculation of instrument deadtimes based on the analyses described in Müller-Mellin et al. (1996). For low flux conditions the predominant dead time is that of the anticoincidence counter G. If the discriminator G_0 triggers before any of the other discriminators A_0 through F_0 , the coincidence logic is blocked for $t_{G_0} = 1.6 \mu\text{s}$, to avoid counting particles not entering through the instrument's aperture. Thus in the case of quiet times (low fluxes), this determines the instrument dead time. The lower limit for the deadtime in this case can be calculated by multiplying the single count rates of G_0 with the duration t_{G_0} . The upper limit can be calculated by taking into account the time of a complete coincidence cycle, $t_{cc} = 3 \mu\text{s}$, and multiplying this number by the G_0 count rate. For quiet times, with an estimated G_0 count rate of 400 counts/s, this sets the expected deadtime in the range of 0.064% up to 0.12%. During high flux conditions the determining factor of deadtime are the pulse shapers of the detectors A through F. The pulse width of a single pulse was determined to be about $t_{pw} = 5 \mu\text{s}$. To acquire a lower limit one has to multiply this number by the sum of all coincidence counters. An upper limit cannot easily

be determined due to possible pile-up effects in the analogue circuit. At a particle rate above 30 kHz (Poisson-distributed), an upper limit cannot even be estimated.

In practice one calculates the maximum value of the deadtime in detector G (low flux) and the deadtimes in detectors A through F (high flux) to calculate the dead times of EPHIN. The calculations were done based on EPHIN level 1 data for every minute. The results are saved in form of instrument livetimes in column 9 of Table 12 of the DDP. For the purpose of calculating particle spectra each particle is weighed with its lifetime value in the creation of the histogram data. In case of high flux events the weighing of spectrum data with the life times will result in increased particle intensities. As an example a deadtime corrected and uncorrected proton spectrum on Jan. 20, 2005 is shown in Figure 9, clearly showing the effect.

Figure 8: Uncorrected and dead time corrected proton spectrum of an event on Jan. 20, 2005. The dead time correction corrects the spectrum to higher particle fluxes. Note that due to the defect of detector E particle fluxes above 25 MeV are incorrect.

3.4 Noise in detector D and E

The single count rates for detector E in the beginning of 1996 show occasional increases during some periods. While the baseline count rate for this detector stayed at about 2800 counts/min, the increases occurred more and more often during 1996. Figure 10 compares the single count rates of detector B and detector E in the upper and lower panel for the year 1996, respectively. While detector B stayed nearly constant sudden increase of detector E counts in October were observed. The red points indicate time periods influenced by the noisy detector E. The single count rates of detector E are in the same order of magnitude in 2010 as they were at the end of 1996, at about 10^4 counts/sec. The increased count rates led to the triggering of detector E even in cases where no particles

reached this detector. This in turn leads to an increased instrument dead time (see section 3.3), prohibiting real particle events to be processed instead of pure noise events triggering detector E. Consequently, the EPHIN instrument team decided to enable the failure mode for detector E on October 31, 1996, which removes detector E from the coincidence tables and prohibits detector E to start a data acquisition cycle.

Figure 9: Detector single count rates of the EPHIN detectors B and E in the year 1996. Detector E shows occasional noise in the beginning of 1996. In October the base count rate of detector E starts to rise from about 40 counts/sec. and reaches about 10^4 counts/sec. at the end of 1996. Detector B is stable in the same period. The red points display periods, when detector E shows a noisy behaviour.

Figure 10: Detector single count rates of the EPHIN detectors B and D in the year 2008. Detector D shows occasional noise in November 2008. From that time on occasional periods are observed when the base count rate of detector D rises from about 40 counts/sec to about 10^4 counts/sec. During these periods detector B is stable. The red points display periods, when the detector D shows a noisy behaviour.

In failure mode E, the coincidence counters involving E will simply not count (i.e. E3000, P41, H41), instead particles stopping in E will be registered as having stopped in D (i.e. E1300, P25, H25). Another consequence is that the coincidences E1300, P25 and H25 have an increased energy window up to 10.4 MeV for electrons and 53 MeV/nucleon for nuclei. The PHA data is analysed assuming that the particles stop in detector D, since no PHA data for detector E is saved (31-OCT-1996 to 13-Mar-1997). To recover the detector E PHA data – although with reduced accuracy – a software patch was uploaded on 13-MAR-1997. Since 2000 the energy loss measurement of this detector is only usable for helium spectra, where the particle's energy loss is much larger than the noise level.

In November 2008 the first anomalous behaviour of detector D was observed (Figure 11). In contrast to detector E the base single detector count rate is only slightly increasing to less than a 100 counts/sec. However, the bursty count rate increases, indicated by the red points in Figure 11, make the analysis of the scientific data of the instrument difficult so that a selection procedure has been developed as explained in Figure 12.

Figure 11: The four panels show from the top left to the lower right panel the count rates of detector B as a function of the count rate ratio of detectors D/B in 2000, 2008, 2010 and 2012. For details see text.

The four panels of Figure 12 show from the top left to the lower right panel the count rate of detector B as function of the count rate ratio of detectors D/B in 2000, 2008, 2010 and 2012. 2008 (upper right panel) corresponds to a time of low solar activity. Time periods with a noisy detector D are identified by a large single count rate ratio of detectors D/B and small variation in the count rate of detector B. During large solar activity the count rates in detector B and the count rate ratio of detectors D/B vary strongly. In order to separate “good times” from noisy times the function shown by the red line in Figure 12 has been introduced. All entries to the right of the line are now attributed to the noisy detector D (red points) and the corresponding time periods are not provided to SEPServer. As an example

Figure 13 displays the measured intensities during the energetic particle event in March 2012. An increase of spurious coincidences in high energy helium is visible when detector D turns noisy at day of year 56 of 2012.

Figure 12: Intensity time profiles of protons from 8 to 25 MeV and single detector count rates of detector D for the time period of day of year 56, 2012. Time periods with count rates in D above a certain threshold are omitted from the SEP Server data set due to the increased risk of data misinterpretation. In SEP Server only periods indicated by the red arrow are included.

3.5 Directional measurement capability of the EPHIN

The sensor head consists of a stack of six silicon detectors, surrounded by an anti-coincidence shield of plastic scintillator (see Figure 1). Two passivated ion-implanted detectors (A and B) define the 83° full width conical field of view with a geometric factor of $5.1 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sr}$. Detectors A and B are divided into six segments. This coarse position sensing permits not only sufficient correction for path length variations but also allows an estimation of the incident particle direction as displayed in Figure 14. From that figure it

becomes obvious that EPHIN has some directional sensitivity – although limited – which can be explored using the files being submitted to SEPServer.

Figure 13: Geometry of the EPHIN entrance telescope consisting of detectors A and B.

3.5.1 EPHIN directional capabilities

The following figures describe the directional capabilities of EPHIN sectorized data set. The figures display the result of a Monte Carlo simulation in order to determine valid tracks through the sensor using the technique described in Sullivan (1971). From the section it becomes obvious that the instrument has some directional capabilities, but that further complex investigations are needed. This was foreseen for the second period, unfortunately not granted by the EU.

Figure 14: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D10 and D20.

Figure 15: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D10 and D21.

Figure 16: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D10 and D22.

Figure 17: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D10 and D23.

Figure 18: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D10 and D24.

Figure 19: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D10 and D25.

Figure 20: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D11 and D20.

Figure 21: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D10 and D22.

Figure 22: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D10 and D23.

Figure 23: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D10 and D24.

Figure 24: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D10 and D25.

Figure 25: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D12 and D20.

Figure 26: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D12 and D21.

Figure 27: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D12 and D22.

Figure 28: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D12 and D23.

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Figure 32: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D13 and D21.

Figure 33: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D13 and D22.

Figure 34: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D13 and D23.

Figure 35: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D13 and D24.

Figure 36: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D13 and D25.

Figure 37: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D14 and D20.

Figure 38: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D14 and D21.

Figure 39: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D14 and D22.

Figure 40: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D14 and D23.

Figure 41: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D14 and D24.

Figure 42: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D14 and D25.

Figure 43: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D15 and D20.

Figure 44: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D15 and D21.

Figure 45: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D15 and D22.

Figure 46: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D15 and D23.

Figure 47: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D15 and D24.

Figure 48: Result of a Monte-Carlo simulation for a valid coincidence between segments D15 and D25.

4 EPHIN Data Delivered and Quality Assessment

4.1 Solar cycles 23-24 electron, proton and helium data

The Level 2 data file structure as well as the data format is described in Table 9 of the AD2. In contrast to the Level 3 data, no corrections have been applied. These data sets correspond to the ones provided to NASA. They are available on SEPServer from day of year 342, 1995 up to the date data are available for ingestion by 31-May-2013. However, at some point these files are useful when corrections, making use of PHA data, as described in section 3.2, lead to statistically insignificant results (see Figure 8).

4.2 EPHIN corrected data

These files are generated from the Level 2 files using further informations and are available from day of year 342, 1995 up to the date data are available for ingestion by 31-May-2013. These data are currently provided only via SEPServer to the community and facilitate the data interpretation because of the following major inclusions. In section 4.2.1 we filter the EPHIN data set that way, that the intensities are calculated by taking into account the change of the instruments energy reponse after switching off detector E logically. This reflects itself in introducing a new set of energy channels (see table 11 of the DDP). Livetime corrections (see section 4.2.2) are applied for the first time to EPHIN data and improve the interpretation of solar energetic particle event data. If this correction exceeds a certain threshold (50%) data will be set to -99 to avoid misinterpretations. Experienced users can still go back to the uncorrected data as described above. The particle identification method (section 4.2.3) has been applied previously on www2.physik.uni-kiel.de combining two different data files. This has been performed on SEPServer to facilitate the accessibility of the proton data. Note, that a possible photon contamination in the electron channels can only be identified by analyzing the time profiles. Another important improvement of the EPHIN data provided via SEPServer is the rejection of time periods when detector E and later detector D became noisy (see section 4.2.4). As illustrated in Figure 13 an increased noise level may lead to spurious coincidences that can be misinterpreted by an unexperienced user.

4.2.1 EPHIN status flag

- If the EPHIN status flag is not 0,1,3,5, 69, or 71 all data are set to -99.
- Status flag 0: Intensities are calculated using geometric factors and energy windows of Table 2 and the channels e104, p35, and He53 are set to -99
- Status flag 1, 3 and 5 (failure mode E, and Ring A/B off or Patch E uploaded): The following channels are defined: $e104 = e1300+e3000$, $p53 = p25+p41$, and $He53=He25+He41$. The nominal channels $e1300 = e3000 = p25 = p41 = He25 = He41$ are set to -99.
- For the different status flags the geometry factors and energy windows are different (see Table 2).

4.2.2 Livetime corrections

The livetime is determined as described in section 3.3. If the livetime is larger than 0.5 times the accumulation time intensities are calculated using the livetime instead of the nominal accumulation time. In case that the livetime is smaller than 50% the intensities are set to -99.

4.2.3 Particle Identification corrections

Next for each entry of the PHA files the particle identification number is calculated (see Figure 6). Using the criteria described in Table 4 each entry is associated to the electron, proton or alpha channel.

4.2.4 Correction for the noisy detectors E and D

Finally, for the years after 2007 a correction for noise in detectors D and E is applied.

4.3 SOHO Sectorized data

SEP Server provides sectorized data for the EPHIN in 36 bins within the view cone, listed in Table 11 of the AD2. There are two files per day, one for electrons and one for protons named EPHIN-E and EPHIN-P, respectively. Each file contains a header line indicated by the #-sign. Data are delivered from day of year 342, 1995 up to the date data are available for ingestion by 31-May-2013. These files are useful for EPHIN status 0, 1, 5, and 69.

4.4 Data quality assesment

EPHIN uncorrected ; EPHIN corrected; ERNE

Electron contamination

Correction via Energy loss distribution

Corrected: $(I_{\text{EPHIN}} - I_{\text{ERNE}})/(I_{\text{EPHIN}} + I_{\text{ERNE}})/2$

Figure 49 Intensity time profile of 4.3 to 7.8 MeV protons during the July 13, 2005 event (left). The right panel shows the relative deviation of the SOHO/EPHIN to SOHO/ERNE intensities. For details see text.

Figure 50 displays in the left panel the 20 minute averaged intensities of uncorrected (green curve) and corrected (red curve) SOHO EPHIN and ERNE 4.3 to 7.8 MeV protons during the July 13, 2005 solar energetic particle event. Comparing the corrected and uncorrected EPHIN data sets we find a strong contamination by electrons during the onset of the event. The profile of corrected proton intensities follows more or less the time profile of the ERNE intensities, but at a lower absolute intensity. During the time of PHA correction even stronger deviation exists, which can be attributed to the low statistics of

PHA words. In order to quantify the difference between the two sensors we calculated the relative difference $(I_{EPHIN} - I_{ERNE}) / (I_{EPHIN} + I_{ERNE}) * 50$ as shown in the right panel of Figure 50. From the figure it is evident that EPHIN determines an intensity that is about 40% smaller than ERNE. As we show in the AD3 similar differences between the ERNE instrument and EPHIN can be found for other energy channels. The comparison with ACE/SIS leads to the same conclusion: for overlapping data channels the three instruments close to Earth differ from each other by less than 50%.

4.5 Summary of major improvements and recommendation

SEPServer provides for the first time

1. EPHIN data corrected for:
 1. Electron contamination in the proton channel
 2. Dead times at high intensity levels
 3. Sporadic noise events in detectors D and E
2. EPHIN sectored data to be used for exploring the directional capability of the instrument
3. EPHIN channels which take into account the status word of the instrument.
4. Most comprehensive description of the data set
5. A quantitative comparison with other instruments showing an agreement within less than 50 %.

Although these major improvements have been implemented and a comparison between the different instrumentation show a reasonable agreement (AD3) we recommend to get in contact with the SOHO/EPHIN team via the SEPServer page in case of questions.

SEPServer
Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report
SOHO/ERNE instrument description and data quality

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Summary

This document contains the SOHO/ERNE part of the Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report (SEP DDR) for the SEP Server database server. In this part of the SEP DDR the Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron (ERNE) instrument aboard the Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO) is described. The ERNE data delivered for SEP Server is also summarized and the functional characteristics and caveats of the instrument are described. In addition to the introduction presenting the applicable and some reference documents, the following five sections are included in this document:

1. Brief overview of the SOHO mission
2. Description of the ERNE instrument and delivered data
3. Functional characteristics and caveats of the instrument
4. Examples of measured energy spectra of protons, ^4He , and heavy ions.
5. Conclusions

The functional and operational characteristics of the SOHO/ERNE instrument and the generation and processing of the data provided for SEP Server require the user to take into account in particular the following data quality issues.

1. Effect of signal thresholds (Section 4.2)
 - a. For those time periods when the higher signal threshold level (3xHIT) is used for initiating the data collection cycle, only interpolated proton and helium data are provided. These time periods are flagged in the status word of the data.
 - b. The lower signal threshold (1xHIT) may have an effect on the energy spectra of heavy ions resulting in reduced intensities in particular at high energies (Figure 4.3 and Figure 4.4).
2. During large events ERNE/HED saturates (Section 4.3, Table 4.1)
3. Inefficiency of the anticoincidence detectors of ERNE/HED causes a background in particular for high-energy protons, which during quiet times is significant (Section 4.4, Figure 4.6).
4. SOHO rolls change the view direction of ERNE sensors from the direction of the nominal Parker magnetic field line to 45° east from the Sun (Section 4.8). SOHO keyhole periods cause gaps in the ERNE data (Section 4.8, Figure 4.9).
5. Distortions in energy spectra.
 - a. There is a possible cut-off of the energy spectra of protons and ^4He above about 70-80 MeV/n and at >100 MeV/n for heavy ions (Section 5, Figure 5.1, Figure 5.2, and Figure 5.3).
 - b. There is a tendency that the intensities of heavy ions (in particular of oxygen) in the lowest energy channel of ERNE/HED are unexpectedly low (Figure 3.7, Figure 4.3, Figure 4.4).

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document contains the SEPServer Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report for the ERNE instrument aboard the SOHO spacecraft.

This document roughly breaks down into the following components:

1. Brief overview of the SOHO mission
2. Description of the ERNE instrument and delivered data
3. Functional characteristics and caveats of the instrument
4. Examples of spectra of protons, helium and heavy ions measured by ERNE
5. Conclusions

Each topic will be detailed in a section of the document.

1.2 Applicable documents

Applicable documents are referenced to their latest version.

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference
AD 1	Description of Work	EC-GA #262773, Annex I
AD 2	SEPServer SEP Data Delivery Plan	SEPSERVER-009-CAU-WP2
AD 3	SEPServer Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: Mission description and data comparison	SEPSERVER-010-00-CAU-WP2

1.3 Reference documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference
RD 1	The SOHO Mission: An Overview	V. Domingo, B. Fleck, and A.I. Poland: Solar Physics, Vol. 162, 1-37, 1995.
RD 2	SOHO web page	http://sohowww.nascom.nasa.gov/
RD 3	Energetic Particle Experiment ERNE	J. Torsti, E. Valtonen, M. Lumme, et al.: Solar Physics, Vol. 162, 505-531, 1995.
RD 4	Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron Experiment of the SOHO Mission	E. Valtonen, J. Peltonen, J. Peltonen, et al.: Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research A, Vol. A391, 249-268, 1997.
RD 5	Response simulations of ERNE/HED with Geant4 (in Finnish)	J. Lehti, MSc Thesis, University of Turku, 2005.
RD 6	Analysis of directional distributions of solar energetic particles detected by SOHO/ERNE	T. Sahla, PhD Thesis, Annales Universitatis Turkuensis, Ser. A, Tom. 312, 2003.

RD 7	SEPServer Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: SOHO/EPHIN Instrument description and data quality	SEPSERVER-010-06-CAU-WP2
RD 8	Real-time particle analysis in ERNE/LED (in Finnish)	S. Urpila, MSc Thesis, University of Turku, 1998.

1.4 Abbreviations and acronyms

AC	AntiCoincidence
ACE	Advanced Composition Explorer
BGO	Bismuth Germanium Oxide
CEPAC	COSTEP/ERNE particle analyser collaboration
COSTEP	COm-prehensive SupraThermal and Energetic Particle Analyser
CSI(Tl)	Thallium activated Cesium Iodide
DDP	Data Delivery Plan
DDR	Data Delivery Report
DPU	Data Processing Unit
EPHIN	Electron Proton Helium Instrument
ERNE	Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron
ESA	European Space Agency
GANIL	Le Grand Accélérateur National d'Ions Lourds
GSFC	Goddard Space Flight Center
GSI	Gesellschaft für Schwerionenforschung
HED	High Energy Detector
IP	Interplanetary
ISN	Institut des Science Nucléaire
LED	Low Energy Detector
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
OSS	On-board Science Software
PIF	Particle Identification Function
PIN	Particle Identification Number
PRn	Priority n
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SEPServer	Data Services and Analysis Tools for Solar Energetic Particle Events and Related Electromagnetic Emissions
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SRC	Sample Rate Control
SRD	Sample Rate Divider

2 Brief overview of the SOHO mission

The Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO) is a cooperative mission between the European Space Agency (ESA) and the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) to study the Sun, from its deep core to the outer corona, and the solar wind [RD 1]. To achieve these scientific goals, the spacecraft carries a complement of twelve instruments consisting of remote sensing and *in-situ* instruments.

SOHO is a three-axis stabilized spacecraft nominally pointing to the centre of the Sun. Energetic particles on-board SOHO are measured by the CEPAC (COSTEP-ERNE Energetic Particle Collaboration) instruments. Data have been delivered for SEPServer from the ERNE and COSTEP/EPHIN instruments [AD 2].

SOHO was launched on December 2, 1995 into a halo orbit around the Lagrangian point L1 of the Sun-Earth system. For more detailed description of the mission, see [AD 3]. The history and current status of the mission are described in [RD 2].

3 Description of the ERNE instrument and delivered data

The ERNE instrument is part of the CEPAC collaboration on-board of the SOHO spacecraft. The instrument has been described in detail in [RD 3] and [RD 4]. With its two sensors, Low Energy Detector (LED) and High Energy Detector (HED), ERNE measures energetic particles from protons to nickel in a wide energy range. The most abundant species, protons and helium nuclei, are identified and categorized in energy by the software running in the ERNE on-board computer. These species in 64 energy channels (since April 19, 2000; before this date 24 energy channels) constitute the core of the ERNE data telemetered to ground. In addition, pulse height data of all ions heavier than helium (and those of deuterium and tritium), samples of pulse heights of protons and helium isotopes, and count rates of protons and ^4He in narrow directional bins within the HED viewcone in a few energy channels are sent to ground. The basic data averaging period (measurement period), i.e., time resolution, of ERNE data is 59.9531 s based on the interval of four SOHO 14.98828 s major frame pulses. This time period is usually referred to as “minute”.

3.1 The sensors

Both ERNE sensors, LED and HED, have a telescope structure, i.e., consist of detector layers on top of each other operating in coincidence/anticoincidence mode, and employ the dE-E-technique in particle identification and energy measurement.

3.1.1 Low Energy Detector

The Low Energy Detector consists of three layers of silicon detectors with the two upper ones (D1_i; $i=1, 2, \dots, 7$ and D2) operating in coincidence with each other and in anticoincidence with the bottom detector (AC). Thus, only particles reaching the second detector D2, but not penetrating through it are analysed. These conditions determine the operational energy range of LED.

Figure 3.1 Vertical cross section (left) and top view (right) of the Low Energy Detector of ERNE.

The first detector layer D1 of LED (Figure 3.1) is composed of seven individual circular silicon detectors providing seven different view cones. Two of these seven detectors have a nominal thickness of $20\ \mu\text{m}$ defining the low-energy threshold of $1.5\ \text{MeV/nucleon}$ for the coincidence measurements with D2 for protons and ${}^4\text{He}$ taking into account the $7\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ thick metallized kapton foil above the detectors. For rough measurements at lower energies LED also has counters for D1 single detector hits, but in this case all elements cannot be unambiguously resolved. The upper energy range of LED for protons is $13\ \text{MeV}$ and is achieved by using the five thicker ($80\ \mu\text{m}$) front detectors in coincidence with the $1000\ \mu\text{m}$ detector D2 (Figure 3.1). The AC detector is used to reject D2-penetrating particles from the analysis, because they could not always be unambiguously identified. The total geometric factor of LED (seven view cones) is $0.92\ \text{cm}^2\text{sr}$. The housing surrounding the LED silicon detectors is mainly aluminium, except for the separate D2 and AC housing, which is stainless steel. The mass resolution of LED is sufficient to distinguish helium isotopes ${}^3\text{He}$ and ${}^4\text{He}$ and even isotopes up to neon (${}^{20}\text{Ne}/{}^{22}\text{Ne}$). The achievable mass resolution is mainly dominated by the path length variations of the particles in the first detector layer due to the allowed angles of incidence (mechanically limited by the aluminium collimator). The thickness uniformity of the active area of all D1 detectors was measured to be better than $0.7\ \%$ so having only a minor effect on the mass resolution.

3.1.2 High Energy Detector

The High Energy Detector consists of altogether six layers of silicon detectors (S1, S2, and D1 in Figure 3.2) and of two thick layers of scintillators (D2 and D3) surrounded by a plastic scintillator anticoincidence shield (AC) and assembled in aluminium housing. The rectangular $70.0 \times 70.0\ \text{mm}^2$ -wide aperture of HED is defined by the silicon strip detectors S1 and S2 (Figure 3.2). Both S1 and S2 consist of two layers of strip detectors with strips in orthogonal orientation with respect to each other (X and Y), and thus the pairs (S1x, S1y) and (S2x, S2y) giving two points for the

position of incident particles in three dimensions. The low-energy threshold of HED is determined by the requirements of particles penetrating two metallized kapton foils (thickness 75 and 125 μm) above the first detector and creating coincident signals from all four silicon strip detector layers. Together with the foils and with the nominal thickness of 300 μm of each strip detector and with the signal threshold requirement of ~ 0.1 MeV from the lowest one, the low-energy threshold is set at 12.5 MeV/nucleon for protons and ^4He .

Due to technology limitations at the time of manufacturing, each of the four strip detector layers is further divided in two halves with active area dimensions of 70.0 mm x 33.0 mm. These halves are assembled in parallel to form one X (or Y) layer for coordinate measurements of incident particles. Due to inactive edge regions of the detectors and the necessary separation of the two halves from each other in order to avoid damage from vibration, a cross-shaped inactive region with the width of 4.0 mm remains in the view cone of HED, where the coordinates of incident particles cannot be measured. A similar inactive area appears in D1, which consists of four quadrants. In D1 plastic material within this area is also used to support the detectors mechanically.

The strip detectors S1 and S2 have altogether 66 strips in X and Y directions with a pitch of 1.0 mm. By using the strip detectors, very accurate directional measurements of incident particles are achieved within the view cone of HED. This capability is used to perform accurate anisotropy measurements of particle intensities. The measurement of particle trajectories in the sensor is also necessary in order to take into account the path length variations of particles in the detectors due to the wide (max $140^\circ \times 140^\circ$) acceptance view cone of HED. Only by correcting the energy loss measurements for the path lengths, the required mass resolution can be achieved.

In order to reach high energies of stopping particles (up to 140 MeV for protons), two thick layers of scintillators (D2: CsI(Tl) and D3: BGO) are used in HED below the silicon detectors. The light from these scintillators as well as from the plastic scintillator anticoincidence shield (AC) is read out by silicon photodiodes. All scintillators are wrapped in white light reflecting tapes (teflon and mylar) for maximum light collection efficiency. The total thickness of the tapes varies from 100 μm (D2 upper surface) to 150 μm . In addition, polyethylene sheets acting as vibration isolators had to be installed between the scintillators. These materials create dead layers between the detectors, which have to be taken into account in energy calibrations of the sensor.

The geometric factor of HED is species and energy dependent varying from $\sim 40 \text{ cm}^2\text{sr}$ to $\sim 25 \text{ cm}^2\text{sr}$ for the lowest and highest energy protons.

Figure 3.2. Vertical cross section of HED (left) and a 3-dimensional sketch showing the active detector elements (right). On the right, the detector inactive edge regions and support structures and the photodiodes of the scintillators are omitted for clarity. The principle of coordinate measurement is indicated for a particle incident from the right.

3.1.3 Electronics

Both sensors of ERNE are measuring ions from $Z = 1$ to $Z = 28$. Originally it was expected that ERNE would measure also electrons. Due to the relatively low efficiency of the plastic anticoincidence shield with photodiode readout this has turned out to be very challenging. The dynamic range of the amplifiers required for measuring ions from protons to nickel is already demanding. Triple-gain shaping amplifiers with 12-bit analogue-to-digital converters were required to achieve the dynamic range. This, together with the large number of amplifier channels in HED (22 preamplifier inputs and in total 86 fast and slow shaping amplifier outputs) made the calibration of the amplifier parameters a long-duration and demanding task. At hardware level, all the functions of the electronics are controlled by a gate array. For incident particles fulfilling the required hit pattern (signals from certain detectors), the gate array starts the data collection sequence. The signal levels detected in each detector are also used as inputs to a number of hardware counters (8 in LED and 16 in HED) with logic conditions roughly corresponding to various particle species ($Z=1$, $Z \geq 2$, $Z > 2$) in various energy ranges. Additionally, various logic functions are used to categorize the detector signal patterns. The patterns that seem to correspond to valid particles are given screen priorities depending on whether they resemble stopping protons (PR3) or heavier ions (PR1) or particles penetrating the entire detector stack (in HED; PR2). If a valid particle ("hit event") is detected the related data (detector identifications, hit patterns, gain ranges of the amplifier channels selected for processing, pulse heights) are written into the logic output buffer and a DPU interrupt is flagged. In case a previous event is still waiting in the buffer, no interruption is generated and the particle is discarded. To compensate this loss during very high flux conditions has proved to be one of the most challenging features of ERNE, because due to a design oversight no well-defined event counter is included in the set of hardware counters.

The gate array provides various capabilities to reconfigure the hardware. In fault situations detectors can be disconnected or continuously set as logic "1" in the logic functions (see Section 4.5 for HED S1X failure). The gate array can also be used to control the signal threshold levels of the detectors that cause start of the data collection sequence. The nominal signal threshold level (1xHIT) can be raised to a three times higher value (3xHIT) simultaneously for all detectors of a sensor (LED or HED) (see Section 4.2). The low priority hit patterns (PR2 and PR3) which represent the most abundant particles (particles penetrating the entire sensor and stopping protons in the case of HED) are associated with programmable counters used for controlling the rate at which these priorities can result in DPU interrupts. This function is referred to as sample rate divider (SRD). It is implemented in the gate array and is actively controlled by the ERNE DPU during high flux conditions.

3.1.4 Data processing unit and on-board software

ERNE has a dedicated on-board computer, in addition to the CEPAC common data processing unit. The major task of the ERNE DPU is to run the algorithm used for on-board identification of most abundant ions (i.e., protons and helium) and their isotopes. The proton and helium data delivered for SEPServer (see Section 3.2.1) are based on analysis performed on-board SOHO. Identification of light ions on-board is essential in order to achieve the maximum science return within the allocated telemetry rate of ERNE. In addition to the count rates of identified particles categorized in energy, samples of pulse height data of light ions together with all pulse heights of all heavier ions ($Z > 2$) are telemetered to ground.

The particle data (“events”) received from the gate array are categorised using fast pattern matching tree logic. The main task in this first phase of analysis is to flag various erroneous non-sense hit patterns passed by the non-perfect logic as the lowest priority data. The amount of data in pre-defined categories is recorded by dedicated counters (interrupt counters). Event data are fed to the analysis through an internal memory location (“analysis buffer”) with the size of one particle event. In case a previous event is still waiting for analysis when a new particle interrupt is generated the interrupt server program will determine which of the two is of higher priority (see Section 3.1.3). If the recent data is more valuable than the previous one, the contents of the buffer will be replaced with the new data. Locking up of the operating system by too high a rate of the high priority event interrupts is prevented by the sample rate control system. The interrupt server program monitors the number of consecutive times it is awakened while an earlier event is still pending for analysis. If it seems that the interrupt rate is too high relative to the analysis rate, the program increases the SRD. This will lower the system load due to low priority (proton) interrupts. Likewise if the analysis buffer tends to be empty on consecutive interrupts the system starts decreasing the SRD.

The on-board science analysis starts by transferring the particle data from the analysis buffer. The first task is to turn the pulse height and gain information into calibrated energies. In HED that information is then used to calculate the hit coordinates in the S1 and S2 detectors. The coordinates are used for attenuation correction of the energies in the strip detectors caused by the capacitive signal readout. Particle trajectories are also calculated. The directions of incident particles are determined within narrow solid angles within the view cone of HED and count rates in these angular bins are recorded. From these data the directional intensities are created on ground (see Section 3.2.3). The particle types are identified by calculating a particle identification number (PIN) by using tailored implementations of the well-established particle identification functions (PIF) based on the energy loss and residual energy ($dE-E_{res}$) information. More detailed description of the identification method is given in Section 3.2.1.

Much of the bookkeeping in the system is done by keeping records of the number of occurrence of various incidences during the operation. The two main purposes of such counters are the long-term monitoring of the overall behaviour and health of the instrument and to correct for various sampling effects when converting the measurements into the final scientific data products. There are three sets of counters monitoring the various phases of the on-board processing:

1. Hardware counters up kept by the digital logic
2. Interrupt server counters
3. Analysis counters

The first two were already mentioned above. The analysis counters record the total number of analysed particle events and the number of certain analysis errors detected during the processing. The actual set of the error counters varies between the on-board software versions¹. The most recent versions of the on-board software (OSS 2.50 – OSS 2.52) maintain 37 different counters. For example, records are kept of “PIN errors” representing PIN values that do not correspond to any expected value (like “particles” between tritons and ³He), of occurrences when the energy of any detector is deemed too high or too low to be physically meaningful, and of such cases when in HED the deduced particle track seems to have hit some internal structures of the detector.

¹ For the list of various versions of ERNE on-board software and the dates when used see Table Table 4.1 in Section 4.6.

3.1.5 Pre-flight and in-flight calibration

ERNE was calibrated before launch at several particle accelerator facilities (ISN, Grenoble, F; GANIL, Caen, F; and GSI, Darmstadt, D) by using various energies and ion species. In addition, in-flight data have been extensively used for calibration purposes. A Geant4 model of HED has been created [RD 5] and simulations carried out mainly for verifying the geometric factors of HED at various energies for protons.

3.2 ERNE data delivered for SEPServer

The ERNE data delivered for SEPServer consist of the following data sets:

1. Continuous² time series of count rates and intensities of protons and helium from May 1996 till May 2013 in 20 energy channels from 1.6 MeV/n to 131 MeV/n of the project (slightly different energy channels/ranges before April 19, 2000).
2. Count rates and intensities of heavy ions (C, N, O, group of CNO, Ne, Mg, Si, group from Si to Ar, group from Fe to Ni) in ten energy channels from 1.8 MeV/nucleon (C) to 200 MeV/nucleon (all ions) for those events identified in the SEPServer ERNE proton event list.
3. Directional count rates and intensities in the field of view of ERNE/HED of protons in four energy channels (15.9 – 101 MeV) and helium in one energy channel (64 – 80 MeV/nucleon) for most³ of the events identified in the SEPServer ERNE proton event list.

The data contents and detailed formats are defined in [AD 2]. In the following sections, the generation process of the delivered data is briefly described. The contents, purpose and special features of the data, which may not be self-explanatory from [AD 2] and which have significance from the user point of view are also explained.

3.2.1 Proton and helium data

3.2.1.1 On-board processing

The ERNE proton and helium data delivered for SEPServer are based on the analysis carried out by the ERNE DPU on-board the SOHO spacecraft. Based on the pulse heights measured in various detectors of LED and HED, protons and ⁴He nuclei are identified and binned in energy. Identification of particles is based on the *dE-E*-method. The measured pulse heights from various detectors are converted into energies by using empirical (linear) calibration curves for each amplifier channel and gain range (ref. Section 3.1.3). Based on the energies, the Particle Identification Number (PIN) is calculated for each incident particle by using a Particle Identification Function (PIF) (see below). Particles within certain PIN ranges are labelled as protons or helium based on theoretical values. Counts within the PIN ranges corresponding to protons and ⁴He nuclei (together with some other PIN ranges corresponding to the isotopes of hydrogen and ³He) at twenty energy channels (10 from LED and 10 from HED) are telemetered to ground. The exact lower and upper energy limits of the energy channels are dependent on the software version (two different divisions from May 1996 till April 2000 and from April 2000 till present) and are defined in [AD 2].

² Subject to availability of data (see Section 4.7).

³ Directional intensities are not provided for the events before 19 April 2000.

Identification of light particles (hydrogen and helium with their isotopes) by the ERNE on-board software is based on an optimized particle identification function [RD 8] taking into account limitations set by the available memory size and the requirement that the algorithm has to be fast to minimize the time required for the analysis of a single particle. The PIF calculated for particles measured by LED is

$$(3.1) \quad PIF = C_{LED} \frac{1}{L} \left[\left(E + \frac{D \cdot dE}{L} \right)^\alpha - \left(E_{res} + \frac{D \cdot dE}{L} \right)^\alpha \right].$$

The symbols used in equation (3.1) stand for:

α	constant equal to 1.75
C_{LED}	constant equal to $6.95359 \times 10^{-5} \mu\text{m}/\text{keV}^{1.75}$
D	constant equal to 4.21 μm
L	thickness of the energy loss (D1i) detector (D11: 20.1 μm ; D16: 21.7 μm ; D12, ..., D15 and D17: 82.0 μm)
dE	energy loss of the particle in the D1i detector [keV]
E	total energy of the particle (sum of energies measured in one of the D1i detectors and in D2) [keV]

This form of PIF has been used since on-board software Version 2.40 (starting 19.04.2000). Before April 19, 2000, a simpler version of identification function was used, which caused spreading of PIF values of protons and ^4He into the regions of their rarer isotopes (deuterium, triton and ^3He), in particular at high and low energies, respectively. In this case, the main effect was contamination of these rare isotopes, while the effect on the much more abundant protons and ^4He themselves was not significant. Examples of “PIN contour plots” are shown in Figure 3.3 and Figure 3.4 based on the data collected on November 13, 1997 (On-board software Version 2.15) and October 31, 2004 (On-board software Version 2.40), respectively.

As the result of the analysis, the number of particles identified as protons, ^3He or ^4He categorized in 32 energy bins (OSS 2.40 and later) within the operational energy range of LED for each minute are included in the ERNE science telemetry.

Figure 3.3. Contour plot of the Particle Identification Number (horizontal axis) in the region of hydrogen and helium vs. total particle energy (vertical axis) for LED. The plot is based on the data collected on November 13, 1997(On-board software Version 2.15). The red vertical lines show the PIN regions, which are interpreted as protons and ^4He .

Figure 3.4. Contour plot of the Particle Identification Number (horizontal axis) in the region of hydrogen and helium vs. total particle energy (vertical axis) for LED. The plot is based on the data collected on October 31, 2004 (On-board software Version 2.40). The histograms show the distributions as function of PIN with the scale on the right. Also shown are the PIN limits for selection of protons and ^4He (red vertical lines).

Figure 3.5. Contour plot of the Particle Identification Number (horizontal axis) in the region of hydrogen and helium vs. total particle energy (vertical axis) for HED. The plot is based on the data collected on October 31, 2004

Light particle identification in HED is based on the following simple formula:

$$(3.2) \quad PIF = C_{HED} \frac{E^\alpha - E_{res}^\alpha}{L / \cos \theta},$$

where

- α = constant equal to 1.75
- C_{HED} = constant equal to $1.1 \times 10^{-3} \mu\text{m}/\text{keV}^{1.75}$
- L = thickness of the energy loss detector (S1=S2=300 μm ; D1=1000 μm ; D2=10300 Si equivalent μm)
- θ = angle of incidence of the particle
- E_{res} = residual energy in the stopping detector [keV]
- E = total energy of the particle (sum of energies measured in the energy loss and stopping detector) [keV]

An example of the PIN contour plot for HED is shown in Figure 3.5.

In order to be accepted as an “event” starting the data collection sequence, a particle has to penetrate at least to the lower layer of S2 (=S2Y; allowing determination of the direction of incidence of the particle) and in each detector layer deposit an energy exceeding a threshold value. There are, therefore, four detectors that can serve as the stopping detector (S2Y, D1, D2, and D3; Figure 3.2). The estimated minimum energies of protons reaching these detectors and producing the required signal level are 12.5 MeV, 14.5 MeV, 17.0 MeV, and 52 MeV, respectively. As a baseline, the energy measured by the detector where the particle stops is used as the residual energy E_{res} and the sum of energies from all detectors above it as the energy loss dE ($E = dE + E_{res}$). However, if the energy loss is more than twice the residual energy, then the energy loss is reduced by the amount of energy measured in the last penetrated detector and this is added to the residual energy. In the analysis, the trajectories of particles are calculated. Based on the trajectory information, particles hitting the inactive edge regions of the detectors or the support structures or missing the side anticoincidence detectors (see Figure 3.2) are rejected, but recorded in counters.

As the result of the analysis, the number of particles identified as protons, ${}^3\text{He}$ or ${}^4\text{He}$ categorized in 32 energy bins (OSS-2.40 and later) within the operational energy range of HED for each minute are included in the ERNE science telemetry.

3.2.1.2 On-ground processing

The data processing on ground consists of several steps during which the telemetry data are unpacked and combined with external data into meaningful physical entities. These external data consist of e.g., pre-calculated geometrical factors for different particle paths and penetration depths (in HED) used for intensity calculations.

In various phases of the on-board data processing there is potential for some loss of data. Therefore, the data included in the telemetry does not necessarily represent the full ambient particle flux, but only a sample of it. On ground, the data from each measurement period (minute) are first corrected for dead-time and various sampling effects encountered during the on-board processing. The reasons for the need of correction are summarized in this Section. The correction methods are described in more detail in Section 4.1.

Correction for the dead time caused by the analogue processing of the detector signals is done for both sensors based on specific interrupt counters. Estimates for the dead time correction factors are calculated as the ratio of the values of these interrupt counters to the corresponding values of associated hardware counters, which count signals processed by the fast shaping amplifiers (c.f. Section 3.1.3).

The number of particles with priorities 2 or 3 (PR2 and PR3) must be corrected for the sampling effect. In order to keep the processing load at optimum level, the associated sample rate dividers are varied constantly. Both priorities have an auxiliary counter (SRC) at the interrupt server that is increased by the current value of the relevant SRD each time a particle with that priority is served. The effective sample rate correction factor is calculated from the ratio of the total number of the particles with each priority and the value of the associated SRC.

Typically only part of the particle data that passes through the checks at the interrupt server will be analysed further by the on-board science analysis program. At the interrupt server the data are divided into different categories based on their apparent types and each of the categories is associated with an internal priority. In case of high particle flux, the less valuable data waiting for

analysis will be overwritten with more valuable data. In this scheme, also some of the highest priority particles may be lost, if one of the same priority is already occupying the analysis buffer. In addition to the hardware priorities (PR1, PR2, PR3), the software upkeeps two additional lower level priorities corresponding to electrons and particles with corrupt HIT-pattern (“errors”) as detected by the interrupt server. Both sides of the data feed keep track of the number of particles offered (interrupt server) and accepted (analysis code) for each of the categories. The correction factor for each internal priority can thus be calculated by the ratio of the corresponding counters.

There are specific counters for the “Heavy” particle and the deuteron and triton pulse height data keeping track of the number of each different particle type eligible for the PHA tabulation in the down-loaded data. These counters are used for normalizing the pulse height data in the typical case that the pulse height data tables are filled during an integration period.

The corrections and normalizations described above are done for the on-board processed proton and helium data when processing the level-0 data received from GSFC to level-3 data for distribution. The ERNE proton and helium data delivered for SEP Server contains proton and helium intensities and count rates in 20 energy channels (10 from LED and 10 from HED) [AD 2]. The energy channels are shown in Table 3.1 with their nominal (mean) energies.

Table 3.1. ERNE proton and helium energy channels and nominal energies

Channel	Energy range (MeV/nucleon)	Nominal energy (MeV/nucleon)	Channel	Energy range (MeV/nucleon)	Nominal energy (MeV/nucleon)
1	1.6 - 1.8 ¹⁾	1.7 ¹⁾	11	14 – 17	15.4
2	1.8 - 2.2	2.0	12	17 – 22	18.9
3	2.2 - 2.7	2.4	13	21 – 28	23.3
4	2.7 - 3.3	3.0	14	26 – 32	29.1
5	3.3 - 4.1	3.7	15	32 – 41	36.4
6	4.1 - 5.1	4.7	16	41 – 54 ¹⁾	45.6
7	5.1 - 6.4	5.7	17	51 – 67	57.4
8	6.4 - 8.1	7.2	18	64 – 80 ²⁾	72.0 ²⁾
9	8.1 – 10	9.1	19	80 – 101 ³⁾	90.5 ³⁾
10	10 – 13	11	20	101 – 131 ⁴⁾	108 ⁴⁾
	¹⁾ 1.5-1.8 for both species before 19-04-2000	¹⁾ 1.6 for both species before 19-04-2000		¹⁾ 41-51 for both species before 19-04-2000	
				²⁾ 54-79 for protons before 19-04-2000	²⁾ 67.5 for protons before 19-04-2000
				³⁾ 79-114 for protons before 19-04-2000	³⁾ 94.0 for protons before 19-04-2000
				⁴⁾ 111-140 for protons before 19-04-2000	⁴⁾ 116 for protons before 19-04-2000

Table 3.1 shows the estimated mean energies for each nominal energy channel for a flat spectrum. The variations of geometric factor inside a channel influence the mean energy. The energy deposited in the thermal foil(s) of LED and HED has been taken into account at energies below 6 and 60 MeV/n in LED and HED, respectively. Energies deposited in the mylar, Teflon, and polyethylene layers of the HED scintillators have been taken into account, as well. The energy

dependent geometric factor and the dead layers, however, cause uncertainties in the mean energies. A conservative way of taking into account these uncertainties is to assume that the total uncertainty in the mean energy is equal to the width of the corresponding energy channel, while the uncertainty in the intensity is given by the statistical error of the corresponding count rate.

Table 3.2. ERNE SEPServer proton and helium data status word

Bit N:o	Explanation
15	HED OFF
14	LED OFF
13-8	Reserved
7	HED S1H2XHIT Disconnected ¹⁾
6	HED AC1 Disconnected
5	HED AC2 disconnected
4	HED EL Bit OFF
3	HED 3xHIT Level ²⁾
2	LED 3xHIT Level ³⁾
1	HED Overload ⁴⁾
0	LED Overload

¹⁾ Constantly “1” since 03-07-2001

²⁾ Value “1” flags for interpolated data for HED

³⁾ Value “1” flags for interpolated data for LED

⁴⁾ Separately given as a flag in the ERNE heavy ion data set (see Section 3.2.2)

The delivered ERNE proton and helium data contains a status word (column 5 of the data; AD 2). The most important use of this status word is that it tells the user which signal threshold, 1xHIT or 3xHIT, was valid for each integration period (minute). The user should be aware that during the time periods when either LED or HED 3xHIT signal levels are in use, only interpolated data for the respective sensor is given (see Section 4.2). Nominally all other status bits of Table 3.2 are set to “0” with the exception of bit n:o 7, which since July 3, 2001 has been constantly set to “1” to compensate for the noisy S1H2X detector (see Section 4.5).

3.2.2 Heavy ion data

Production of the heavy ion data delivered for SEPServer starts from the ERNE level-3 pulse height data processed on-ground. The on-board software identifies ions heavier than helium as one group and the related data are sent to ground as pulse heights. Level-3 data also include the pre-calculated correction coefficients related to the loss of data for various known reasons as discussed in Section 3.2.1.1.

Particles whose status word (as defined in Table 3.2) indicates exceptional situations are removed. These situations include LED or HED overload, LED or HED OFF, and HED AC1 or AC2 disconnected. The overload situation occurs in case the sample rate divider (Section 3.1.3) has been set to the maximum value and increase is still called for. The measuring periods (“minutes”) during which the above situations have occurred are identified with a status flag in the delivered data [AD 2].

Level-3 data includes energies measured by each of the detectors of LED and HED. These have

been obtained from the measured pulse heights by using calibration curves established for each detector amplifier channel and gain. The energy loss dE and E_{res} are then determined. For LED, the energy loss is the energy measured by one of the D1i ($i = 1, \dots, 7$) detectors, and the residual energy is the energy measured by D2 (Figure 3.1). For HED, the sum of energies from the detectors that the particle penetrates is used as the energy loss. The residual energy is the energy measured by the stopping detector. However, if the residual energy is less than half of the energy loss, the energy from the detector before the stopping one is added in the residual energy instead of the energy used as the energy loss dE .

The derived energy loss and residual energy are used for a simple noise removal process. For LED, all particles whose residual energy is less than one tenth of their total energy are removed. For HED the noise removal condition is the same, except that it is used only for particles stopping in D1 and D2 (Figure 3.2). The regions in the plot of the element charge number (=PIN) vs. total energy, where the noise events occur in the case of oxygen, are shown in Figure 3.6. No corrections are applied in the intensities to take into account the rejected particles. Slightly too low intensities may thus result in energy channels where particles have been rejected (see Figure 3.7 and Figure 3.8).

Heavy ion identification in both LED and HED is based on the formula similar to equation (3.2). For LED, the value used for the constant multiplier C is $C = 2.66 \times 10^{-4}$ and the exponent α is $\alpha = 1.57$. A correction matrix is used to shift the obtained PIF values in their proper places corresponding to the ion mass. For HED the following particle identification function is used:

$$(3.3) \quad PIF = C_1 + C_2 \{[(E - E_C)^\alpha - (E_{res} - E_C)^\alpha] \cdot \cos \theta\}^{1/(\alpha+1)},$$

where C_1 , C_2 and E_C are constants depending on the stopping detector and $\alpha = 1.75$. The angle θ is the angle of incidence, which is calculated from the coordinate information given by the strip detectors S1 and S2 of HED. After identifying the ions, their energies are converted into the units of MeV/nucleon. The various heavy ions are selected based on the PIN value limits given in Table 3.3. The ERNE heavy ion data delivered for SEP Server include the ion species shown in Table 3.3 in ten energy channels with the nominal energies of each channel as defined in [AD 2].

Table 3.3. Limits of particle identification number for selection of various ions in LED and HED

Ion	LED		HED	
	PIN _{low}	PIN _{high}	PIN _{low}	PIN _{high}
C	133.8	162.0	5.709	6.258
N	202.0	238.0	6.712	7.260
O	288.1	332.4	7.714	8.261
Ne	519.4	582.3	9.500	10.50
Mg	838.6	922.4	11.50	12.50
Si	1255	1362	13.50	14.50
CNO	133.8	332.4	5.500	8.500
Si-Ar	1255	2576	13.50	18.50
Fe-Ni	6286	7934	25.50	28.50

Figure 3.6. Scatter plot of element charge number Z vs. total energy for the region of carbon and oxygen. The data are from the time period April 24-25, 1999. Blue crosses show the selected oxygen data. Diamonds and asterisks correspond to rejected (noise) data.

Figure 3.7. Energy spectrum of oxygen from the period of April 24-25, 1999. Within the statistical errors there is no difference between the spectrum of “all data” within the oxygen PIN limits and “selected data” (blue crosses in Figure 3.6) for oxygen. In both cases the PIN ($=Z$)-limits given in Table 3.3 have been used. The upper curve is for LED, the lower for HED. Typically for HED, its lowest-energy data point seems to be lower than might be expected.

Figure 3.8. Same as Figure 3.7, but for carbon. As suggested by Figure 3.6, the difference between the “all data” within the carbon PIN limits and the “selected data” for carbon is visible at the lowest energy channels of LED and HED, but still within the statistical errors.

The ERNE level-3 data are divided in different categories for protons, helium and heavy ions based on the information provided by the on-board software. Usually all of the heavy ions are in the "correct" category, but some may be found in the helium category. The pre-calculated correction coefficients, which take into account data loss due to instrumental effects and loss in various phases of on-board processing, are different for each of the above categories. The number of selected ions per category, energy channel and measurement period (1 minute) is calculated. In HED the calculation of the number of ions is done separately for each of the four possible stopping detectors (S2Y, D1, D2, D3) of HED.

The intensities are calculated from the counts by first applying the correction coefficients, summing the different categories together and then dividing by the geometric factor, measurement time and energy channel width. Finally the two separate cases of LED (D17 and D1i, $i=1, \dots, 6$) and the four cases of HED are combined to produce the final total intensities for each measurement period. Also the counts of the separate cases are combined to produce total counts for the data. The necessary time stamps, ion type, status flag, intensities and counts are then saved into the data files in the required format [AD 2].

3.2.3 Directional intensities

From the recorded directions of incidence of protons and helium (^4He) in HED in selected energy ranges, directional intensities are calculated in narrow directional bins. An integration time of 4 minutes is used. The directional and energy bins used by various versions of the on-board software are defined in [AD 2], but for convenience they are collected in Table 3.4. The directional bin numbering is presented in Figure 3.9. Directional intensity data are delivered for SEPServer for the SEP events identified in the SEPServer ERNE proton event list in the format defined in [AD 2].

Table 3.4. Directional binning and energy ranges for protons and ⁴He used for deriving directional intensities by various versions of the on-board software (OSS)

OSS Version	Dates in use	Directional bins ¹⁾²⁾ in semi-circular aperture	Species and energy ranges (MeV/nucleon)
OSS-2.20	12.12.1997-04.02.1998	Circular centre area and 9 concentric rings divided in 16 azimuth sectors	Protons 17-22, 21-28, 26-40
OSS-2.21	05.02.1998-01.12.1998	Circular centre area and 9 concentric rings divided in 24 azimuth sectors	Helium 17-28, 26-51, 51-101
OSS-2.22 - OSS-2.24	03.12.1998-18.04.2000		
OSS-2.40 and later	19.04.2000-present	One circular centre area surrounded by 10 concentric rings divided in 24 azimuth sectors	Protons 15.9-17.4, 17.4-18.5, 18.5-20.0, 27-50, 69-101 Helium 64-80

¹⁾ For definition of the azimuth φ and elevation θ angles see Figure 3.10 and Figure 3.11.

²⁾ The elevation angle θ limits are defined in [AD 2]

Figure 3.9. Directional bin numbering in the HED field of view for the on-board software Versions 2.21 – 2.24 (left) and 2.40 and later (right).

Directional intensities follow a probability distribution, which is a combination of a likelihood distribution from Poisson distributed counts and from that of the additional correction factors. The correction factors take into account instrument-dependent effects and are assumed to follow a log-normal distribution. The mean deviations of their distributions are set to reflect the uncertainties of the instrument model. The intensities are calibrated and normalized to the standard units of $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{ s sr MeV})$ by applying the appropriate geometric factor of each directional bin, measuring time, and width of the energy channel. The geometric factors of individual directional bins were determined experimentally based on observations of long time series during isotropic particle flux conditions. The geometric factors were determined separately for each energy range used in directional measurements as well as for various shapes of the energy spectra. The intensities I_{ij} (i th measurement, j th directional bin) include a bin-dependent multiplier, which accounts for the linear and to some extent dynamic (nonlinear) effects and contains multiple corrections depending on the on-board software version and energy channels. As the count rates in each directional bin are limited to 255 per 4 minute measurement period, the Poisson process likelihoods contribute considerably to the final uncertainties. For highly saturated measurements the correction factors a_{ij} are a major source of uncertainty since their variances $\sigma_{a_{ij}}^2$ are set to reflect the uncertainty of the instrument model. With the assumption of log-normal distribution, the probability distribution of $\lg(I_{ij})$ is written as

$$(3.4) \quad \lg(I_{ij}) \sim N(\mu_{I_{ij}} + \mu_{a_{ij}}, \sigma_{I_{ij}}^2 + \sigma_{a_{ij}}^2),$$

where N represents normal distribution. The values $\mu_{I_{ij}}$ do not have a closed-form expression and have to be numerically calculated.

Correction factors a_{ij} can change rapidly for both temporally and directionally neighbouring measurements. Therefore, the data are smoothed both temporally and directionally partly in order to minimize this effect and partly to smooth out pure statistical variations. The smoothing has been implemented by setting covariance between measurements with temporal and angular-dependent weights. The weights follow a Gaussian distribution with mean deviations (scale parameters) s_t and s_{dir} .

Due to its large geometric factor ERNE/HED may saturate, when the particle flux is very high (see Section 4.3). Saturation effects have not been taken into account in the data inversion (calculation of the means), but they have been taken into account in calculation of the variances $\sigma_{a_{ij}}^2$. This means that in very high intensity periods the variances $\sigma_{a_{ij}}^2$ can have very high values. Therefore, it is advised not to jump to conclusions without taking the variances also into consideration.

As a simple parameter describing the possible presence of anisotropy in particle intensity, the so-called anisotropy index AI_i is provided. This index is calculated from the directionally and temporally smoothed measurements. It is defined to be $AI = I_{i,85th} - I_{i,15th}$, where $I_{i,85th}$ is the 85th and $I_{i,15th}$ the 15th percentile values of measurement i . Also the variance of AI $\sigma_{i,AI}^2 = \sigma_{I_{i,85th}}^2 + \sigma_{I_{i,15th}}^2$ is given as part of the data set.

SOHO payload does not include a magnetometer, which makes conversion of directional intensities into pitch angle distributions challenging. In some case magnetic field measurements from close-by spacecraft like ACE or WIND could be used. Based on only the precise directional measurements of particle intensities and searching for azimuthal symmetry in the intensity, one can try to estimate the

direction of the magnetic field line as function of time. The method requires a relatively strong anisotropy of the particle flux and assumes that the particles are symmetrically distributed around the magnetic field line. When the symmetry axis of the intensity distribution is found, it is then defined as the magnetic field line direction. The symmetry axis is found by minimizing the difference between the observed and theoretical distribution functions by an iterative method [RD 6].

Figure 3.10. Principle of directional measurements from the coordinate measurement, through the Δx - Δy space to the directional bins. The inset on the upper right defines the SOHO coordinate system and the HED x and y coordinates. The origin of the HED coordinate system is on the lower left corner of the rectangular view cone. The axis perpendicular to the xy -plane is pointing to 45° to the west of the Sun during the SOHO nominal roll attitude.

Figure 3.11. Schematic presentation of the correspondence between the Δx - Δy space and the directional bins (θ, φ) on the surface of a sphere. The figure shows the real shape of the flat rectangular surface elements.

When interpreting ERNE directional measurements it is important to note that since July 2003 SOHO has been periodically rotated (rolled in respect with the axis pointing to the Sun) by 180° . When SOHO is in the 180° roll attitude, the field of view direction of HED differs from that of the nominal attitude (see Section 4.8). Information on the roll attitude (roll angle) of SOHO is included in the ERNE proton and helium directional intensity data provided by the SEP Server (Column 8 of the data format) [AD 2].

4 Functional characteristics and caveats of the instrument

This Section collects together those aspects and characteristics of the ERNE instrument, which affect the data interpretation and which may have effects on the data quality.

4.1 From counts to intensities

The recorded particle counts represent only a sample of the ambient flux. The counts recorded

during a measurement period (minute) are corrected for the various sampling effects in the on-board processing.

4.1.1 Correction for the hardware to interrupt server loss

Before OSS-2.30 (see Table 4.2) the counter functions at the interrupt level proved to be problematic for estimation of the “hardware-logic-to-interrupt-server” particle loss. Somewhat workable function could be devised for HED, but for LED there was no such option. However, due to the small geometric factor of LED the need for such correction also remains relatively small in all situations.

From OSS-2.30 onwards the correction for LED is done based on the ratio of the LED hardware counter C5 (counting all particles $Z \geq 2$) and the sum of the recorded PR1 events at the LED interrupt server. This correction factor affects all LED measurements.

From OSS-2.30 onwards the correction for HED is done based on “Shadow HWC” Interrupt Counter. It counts the number of interrupt events that fit the logic of any of the first four HED hardware counters (in theory these should be PR3 protons penetrating to different depths in the sensor). Estimate for the correction factor is calculated as the ratio of the shadow register value to the sum of the associated hardware counters. This correction factor affects all HED measurements.

4.1.2 Analysis sampling correction

High priority particles replace lower priority particles in the on-board analysis buffer (see Section 3.1.4). As described in Section 3.2.1.2, the on-board software keeps track of the number of particles offered and accepted for analysis for each priority category. To compensate for the loss of some particles in this phase, a correction factor is calculated for each internal priority and used for normalizing the counts when calculating the intensities.

4.1.3 Sample rate correction

During very high flux situations there are not enough computing resources to handle all the incoming particles. The sample rate control mechanism is used to reduce the number of the most abundant particle species offered by the hardware for analysis, thus increasing the relative amount of the more valuable heavier elements in the data. The low priority hit patterns are associated with programmable counters (sample rate dividers or SRDs) that are used to control the rate at which each type of hit data results in interrupts. The SRDs are actively controlled by the ERNE DPU (Section 3.1.4).

For LED there is one SRD with the range of 1 – 16 controlling the LED PR2 events (protons). For HED there are two dividers, one with the range of 1 – 16 for the HED PR2 events (penetrating particles) and another for the HED PR3 events (protons and electrons) with the range of 1 – 128.

The on-board science program monitors the interrupt-to-analysis ratio. If it seems that the ratio is too high, the SRD values are increased. This will lower the system load due to the most abundant low priority (proton) interrupts. Likewise if the ratio falls below a set limit the system starts decreasing the SRD.

From the OSS-2.30 onwards the interrupt-to-analysis ratio is tried to be kept in a range between 1.2 and 1.8 (same limits for both LED and HED). The PR2 SRD-values are always increased by one. The HED PR3 SRD increase step is one fourth of the current value (rounded up). The decrease is

done in steps of one for all SRDs.

Before OSS-2.30 the SRD control was basically similar but was based on a somewhat more coarse logic, which resulted in an unnecessarily frequent SRD manipulation.

The sample rate divider values are recorded and the average for each measurement period is used to normalize the particle counts for intensity calculation (see Section 3.2.1.2). The counts given in the SEPServer data are those actually recorded and which can be used to evaluate the statistical errors of the measurements. The effect of SRDs on the data, similarly to the analysis sampling correction discussed above, is that the same number of counts can result in different intensity values depending on what values SRDs have had during each measurement period (minute).

4.1.4 Pulse-height data samples

Pulse-height data of heavy ions and isotopes of hydrogen as well as samples of pulse-height data of protons and helium are written in a pulse height table on-board. Typically this table fills up in the middle of the measurement period. The analysis program keeps track of the number of each different particle type eligible for the pulse-height tabulation. There are specific counters for the “Heavy” particles and the deuterons and tritons, which can be used for re-normalization purposes.

4.2 Effect of signal thresholds

ERNE has the capability of raising the signal thresholds, causing the start of a data collection sequence, to three times the nominal values. These threshold levels are called 1xHIT (nominal) and 3xHIT. Originally this capability was designed as a precaution against increasing noise with aging of the detectors. This property can also be used as one way of selecting only heavy ions for analysis. Aging of the detectors has not yet caused any reason to raise the signal thresholds. Instead, it was found soon after launch that there is some cross talk from the D1 detector of HED to the side anticoincidence shield of HED. At nominal signal threshold, this results in discarding some of the heavy ions. When raising the signal threshold the loss of heavy ions can be completely avoided, but with the expense of losing large part of the proton spectrum, because only a small portion of protons produce signals large enough to reach the 3xHIT signal threshold.

Variation of the signal thresholds is implemented by the on-board software monitoring the count rate of helium in certain energy ranges. In LED the energy range used is 11.8-23.5 MeV and 127-403 MeV in HED (total energy of helium in both cases). If the total number of counts of ^4He nuclei in a 4-minute period exceeds pre-set limits (20/4minutes in the case of LED and 30/4minutes in HED), the signal thresholds are raised to three times the nominal value for the next 16 minutes. After 16 minutes, the thresholds are lowered back to the nominal values for four minutes to collect high energy protons and for monitoring the helium count rate again. Thus, typically during a solar particle event the 1xHIT-level and 3xHIT-level measurement periods follow each other in a 4 minute/16 minute pattern. This pattern is synchronised with the 4 minute periodicity of the HED direction distribution recordings. This feature was implemented to HED in the OSS-2.23 (Table 4.2). Later, in the OSS-2.51 the same scheme was implemented also in LED.

Figure 4.1. Effect of increased signal threshold (3xHIT) compared to the nominal level (1xHIT) in LED. The higher signal threshold cuts out a significant part of higher-energy protons. It also affects the lowest energy protons and helium.

The effect of the higher signal threshold in LED is illustrated in Figure 4.1. A large part of the highest energy protons measured by LED is cut out or the detection efficiency is significantly lower, because the required signal threshold is not at all or only rarely exceeded. Correspondingly, the detection efficiency is reduced at the very lowest proton and helium energies. At higher energy end, all helium nuclei produce signals exceeding also the higher (3xHIT) threshold. There is a similar effect in HED. Since during many SEP events the signal thresholds are varied periodically, these effects result in highly varying intensities in several proton energy channels and deteriorated energy spectra. In order to avoid confusion, it was decided to deliver ERNE proton and helium data only for those periods of time, when the nominal (1xHIT) signal threshold levels are in use. To avoid complete data gaps for those time periods when the higher signal threshold level is used, interpolated data for those periods are provided. A simple interpolation method is used, which leads to somewhat spiky-looking intensity vs. time plots as illustrated in Figure 4.2. The time periods for which only interpolated data are provided are flagged by the status word provided with the ERNE proton and helium data (column 5) [AD 2] and defined in Table 3.2.

Figure 4.2. Intensity plots of protons measured by ERNE/LED (10.1-12.7 MeV) and ERNE/HED (50.8-67.3 MeV and 101-131 MeV) for time periods when three times nominal (3xHIT) signal thresholds are applied. In HED the signal threshold was automatically raised at ~02:00 UT and in LED at ~05:00 UT on August 24, 2002. For the 3xHIT time periods only interpolated data are available. Actually measured data are provided only for 4 minutes in each 20-minute cycle.

Figure 4.3. Energy spectra of oxygen for the 1xHIT and 3xHIT signal thresholds. The spectra are integrated for the time period December 25-30, 2001, covering the event of December 26, 2001.

Figure 4.4. As Figure 4.3, but with the integration time of January 14-19, 2005 covering the events of January 15 and 17 of 2005.

For heavy ions the possible effects of varying signal thresholds cannot be seen from the plots like that of Figure 4.2, because the count rates are almost always below ten per minute for all ions heavier than helium. Therefore, statistical errors are very large. The effect can be studied from event-integrated energy spectra, which are shown for oxygen in two events in Figure 4.3 and Figure 4.4. In the first case there is no difference in the energy spectra with 1xHIT and 3xHIT-levels taking into account the statistical (1-sigma) uncertainty. In Figure 4.4 some difference is seen at highest energies with the intensity at 3xHIT somewhat higher as might be expected, if there is cross talk from the anticoincidence shield to detector D1 causing discarding of some ions. The spectra shown in Figure 4.4 have been integrated over the time period January 14-19, 2005. The event of January 15, 2005 of the SEP Server ERNE list was followed by another event on January 17. This latter event caused HED saturation (which is the reason why this event was discarded from the ERNE event list). Saturation of HED (Section 4.3) may have some unexpected effects, which also may affect the intensities recorded at different signal thresholds. Therefore it is not certain what causes the difference of the energy spectra in Figure 4.4.

4.3 HED saturation

Saturation of ERNE/HED presumably results from simultaneous particle hits in the two halves of the strip detectors. Such particles are discarded at hardware level from the analysis based on the digital status of the detectors recorded by the gate array (Section 3.1.3). Due to a design oversight, such particles are not recorded in any counter and the effects of these “double hits” cannot be reconstructed and cannot be compensated for.

Table 4.1. List of SEP events during which ERNE/HED suffers from saturation

Event n:o	Date	Comment
0032	14-Jul-2000	Strong saturation
0038	08-Nov-2000	Strong saturation
0045	02-Apr-2001	Possible saturation and two data gaps
0058	24-Sep-2001	Strong saturation just after rise phase and at the arrival of an interplanetary shock
0059	01-Oct-2001	Relatively short-duration saturation at the maximum phase of the event
0063	04-Nov-2001	Strong saturation
0064	22-Nov-2001	Strong saturation
0072	21-Apr-2002	Strong saturation
0079	22-Aug-2002	Possibly a very short-duration saturation at the end of the rise phase
0087	26-Oct-2003	Strong saturation
0088	28-Oct-2003	Strong saturation
0090	02-Nov-2003	Strong saturation
0097	07-Nov-2004	Strong saturation
	17-Jan-2005	Strong saturation and event discarded from the list
0112	13-Dec-2006	Some saturation at the end of the event (IP shock)
0113	14-Dec-2006	Short-duration saturation right after rise phase
0133	07-Mar-2012	Saturation after rise phase.
0134	13-Mar-2012	Saturation after rise phase.

HED has a large geometric factor (Section 3.1.2), and SEP events, which can produce intensities high enough to cause saturation are unfortunately not very rare. A list of SEP events during which HED was saturated is given in Table 4.1. The event number refers to the SEP Server list of ERNE events.

4.4 Inefficiency of HED anticoincidence detector

ERNE/HED has an anticoincidence shield to record particles, which do not stop in the detector stack, and to protect the sensor from background radiation. The shield is made of plastic scintillator from which the light produced by charged particles is read out by using silicon photodiodes (Section 3.1.2). It has turned out that the efficiency of the anticoincidence shield is low for very high energy particles. Therefore, all particles entering through the aperture of the sensor and penetrating through all the detectors are not properly recorded. Because no signal is obtained from the anticoincidence shield, these particles are mixed up with stopping particles causing background mainly for stopping protons. On the other hand, the anticoincidence scintillators do not provide an efficient shield against galactic cosmic rays entering the sensor from the bottom or from the sides in such a way that they cause an event trigger starting a data collection sequence. These cause unwanted background, as well.

Figure 4.5. Background caused by galactic cosmic rays for high-energy protons. The data are from the end of October 2004, when there were no solar particle events.

Figure 4.6. Protons recorded on November 1, 2004 SEP event. The background caused by galactic cosmic rays at proton energies around 80-100 MeV is visible.

Figure 4.5 demonstrates the background caused by galactic cosmic rays. The data were collected at the end of October 2004, when there were no solar energetic particle events. The background concentrates in the region of 80-100 MeV energy range. A corresponding plot for the SEP event of November 1, 2004, is shown in Figure 4.6. The amount of background is not very high, but will cause some distortion in the shape of the energy spectrum of protons at the highest energies measured by HED. No attempt was made to correct for the background in the data provided for SEP Server. Therefore, the highest energy proton data of ERNE have to be interpreted with caution and being aware of this background.

4.5 Breakdown of S1XH2 detector

The position-sensitive silicon strip detectors of HED are used for measuring the coordinates (x,y) of incident particles, and based on the coordinate information from two levels separated by 31 mm the trajectories of particles are calculated. Each of the strip detectors (S1X, S1Y, S2X, S2Y; Figure 3.2) consists of two halves (H1 and H2). The signals are read out capacitively from the two opposite edges of each half, called the E-edge and the C-edge. The coordinates are obtained as the ratio of the C-edge signal to the sum of the C-and E-edge signals taking also into account the attenuation in the capacitive chain.

On November 21, 2000 HED experienced a failure of the E-edge channel of the S1XH2 detector rendering that measurement useless due to high noise. As the C-edge still remained in good condition, it was possible to devise a contingency action.

Figure 4.7. Coordinates calculated from the measurements with the noisy S1XH2 channel.

Figure 4.8. Coordinates calculated from the same measurements as shown in Figure 4.7 by using the correction method.

A requirement for the start of a data collection sequence in HED is that the particle reaches at least detector S2Y (the last strip detector). This means that the amounts of energy deposited in the first three detector layers (S1X, S1Y, S2X) have a nearly fixed ratio. Thus the total energy E_{est} in S1X can be estimated based on the measured energy in S1Y. In the on-board analysis of HED the S1X energy is estimated to be 96 % of the S1Y energy. Thus, when a particle hits S1XH2, the corresponding coordinate is read from a table using the ratio E_C/E_{est} as an index instead of the sum of the ratio $E_C/(E_C + E_E)$ of the measured SiXH2 energies.

Figure 4.7 and Figure 4.8 demonstrate the result obtained with the correction method. Figure 4.7 shows the uncorrected measurements with clearly uneven distribution of particles in the aperture. A more uniform distribution is expected when there is no anisotropy in the particle flux, and Figure 4.8 shows the same measurement, when the method described above was used to calculate the coordinates. It is concluded that the method developed to replace the noisy S1XH2 works relatively well and the coordinates can still be calculated with sufficient accuracy.

4.6 On-board software versions

Because various versions of the ERNE on-board software have some characteristics affecting the data (e.g., Section 3.2.3 and Section 4.1) the on-board software versions and the dates they have been in use are collected in Table 4.2 for users' convenience.

Table 4.2. ERNE on-board science software versions

Software Version	Dates in use
OSS-2.15	1996-05-07 – 1996-12-20, 1997-03-04 – 1997-12-11
OSS-2.16	1996-12-20 – 1997-02-17
OSS-2.20	1997-12-12 – 1998-02-04
OSS-2.21	1998-02-05 – 1998-12-01
OSS-2.22	1998-12-03 – 1999-06-03
OSS-2.23	1999-06-04 – 1999-08-19
OSS-2.24	1999-08-20 – 2000-02-22, 2000-02-25 – 2000-03-13, 2000-03-31 – 2000-04-18
OSS-2.30	2000-02-23 – 2000-02-24
OSS-2.31	2000-03-14 – 2000-03-29
OSS-2.40	2000-04-19 – 2001-07-02
OSS-2.50	2001-07-03 – 2002-01-24
OSS-2.51	2002-01-25 – 2003-01-14
OSS-2.52	2003-01-15 – present

4.7 Data continuity

As a baseline, SOHO has the requirement of very high data continuity mainly due to the helioseismology investigations. This guarantees excellent data recovery also for particle instruments allowing long, continuous data series to be collected. However, an unexpected loss of contact with SOHO occurred on 25 June 1998. The mission was completely recovered and normal operations were resumed in mid-November 1998 after successful re-commissioning of all instruments. ERNE observations were continued already on 9 October 1998. Right after ending the re-commissioning there was the first safing of all instruments for the Leonids meteor shower. For ERNE this meant switching off the instrument. Another longer break in observations occurred soon after (from December 18, 1998 till February 2, 1999) related to the loss of the last of the three SOHO gyroscopes. In addition there have been several shorter interruptions in the ERNE observations, in some cases due to spacecraft anomalies (e.g., emergency sun acquisitions), but mainly due to reasons related to the instrument itself, like software updates (see Table 4.2) and some thermal anomalies. For SEPServer these interruptions in observations are mainly significant in the sense that the SEPServer catalogue includes a list of SEP events based on ERNE observations, and due to these interruptions some events have been missed. Table 4.3 includes a list of ERNE observation interruptions with a length longer than one day.

Table 4.3. ERNE observation interruptions with duration longer than one day

Start date	Time UT	End date	Time UT	Duration (d)
1996-05-28	8:26	1996-05-31	16:42	3.3
1996-06-02	23:59	1996-06-04	0:00	1.0
1996-12-20	15:52	1997-03-04	16:02	74.0
1997-10-25	5:26	1997-10-28	17:27	3.5
1997-11-19	5:06	1997-11-21	22:38	2.7
1997-11-26	23:59	1997-11-28	0:00	1.0
1998-02-25	4:50	1998-02-28	15:02	3.4
1998-06-24	23:12	1998-10-09	11:17	106.5
1998-11-14	16:05	1998-11-21	16:04	7.0
1998-12-01	13:04	1998-12-03	14:16	2.0
1998-12-21	17:26	1999-02-08	21:18	49.2
1999-02-14	13:49	1999-02-18	13:52	4.0
1999-05-21	12:52	1999-05-26	16:06	5.1
1999-06-03	15:06	1999-06-04	15:40	1.0
1999-08-19	13:06	1999-08-20	18:47	1.2
1999-11-15	13:55	1999-11-20	16:17	5.1
1999-11-28	11:51	1999-11-29	22:38	1.4
1999-12-01	18:37	1999-12-02	23:57	1.2
2000-01-07	0:24	2000-01-08	1:03	1.0
2000-02-22	17:11	2000-02-25	16:18	3.0
2000-03-13	18:05	2000-03-31	20:21	18.1
2000-04-18	13:20	2000-04-19	15:05	1.1
2000-05-22	2:49	2000-05-24	14:49	2.5
2001-01-14	20:58	2001-01-15	21:12	1.0
2001-07-02	14:31	2001-07-03	16:00	1.1
2001-08-10	15:34	2001-08-17	16:49	7.1
2002-01-01	22:45	2002-01-03	19:26	1.9
2002-01-24	16:16	2002-01-25	16:47	1.0

Table 4.3 continued

Start date	Time UT	End data	Time UT	Duration (d)
2002-02-05	2:36	2002-02-12	15:40	7.5
2002-05-23	23:59	2002-05-25	0:00	1.0
2003-02-28	17:53	2003-03-11	15:02	10.9
2004-01-19	7:03	2004-01-22	14:07	3.3
2004-03-25	23:59	2004-03-27	0:03	1.0
2004-04-01	23:59	2004-04-03	0:00	1.0
2004-04-22	21:41	2004-04-29	12:49	6.6
2004-06-22	23:26	2004-06-26	0:00	3.0
2004-08-06	9:16	2004-08-12	12:31	6.1
2005-07-31	3:37	2005-08-03	12:37	3.4
2006-08-13	3:23	2006-08-14	12:46	1.4
2007-01-27	9:39	2007-01-29	14:41	2.2
2010-09-26	14:57	2010-09-27	17:38	1.1
2010-12-10	14:39	2010-12-15	15:26	5.0
2011-01-09	7:49	2011-01-13	12:28	4.2
2011-04-06	23:59	2011-04-08	0:00	1.0
2011-11-30	14:43	2012-01-05	10:56	35.8
2012-01-22	19:42	2012-01-24	20:16	2.0
2012-01-25	09:09	2012-01-27	16:17	2.3
2012-01-28	14:08	2012-02-10	17:03	13.1
2012-02-15	10:43	2012-02-16	18:47	1.3
2012-05-11	23:26	2012-05-14	19:35	2.8
2012-05-21	23:59	2012-05-23	00:00	1.0
2012-07-06	23:35	2012-07-09	00:13	2.0
2012-11-02	00:51	2012-11-07	20:44	5.8
2012-12-06	13:00	2012-12-08	00:00	1.5
2012-09-12	04:29	2013-02-05	15:01	58.4
2013-05-06	12:28	2013-05-07	19:16	1.3
2013-05-10	12:40	2013-05-13	12:48	3.0

Figure 4.9. An example of series of breaks in the ERNE data during SOHO keyhole periods. Comparable breaks are experienced during each SOHO keyhole.

In addition to those interruptions listed in Table 4.3, there are occasional periods of many shorter breaks in ERNE data related to the SOHO keyhole periods (see Section 4.8). The breaks experienced during the November-December 2006 keyhole are illustrated in Figure 4.9.

4.8 SOHO rolls and keyhole periods

In 2003 a failure occurred in the SOHO high-gain antenna driving mechanism. A decision was made to park the antenna in a fixed position, which maximizes the time during one half-orbit when the signal is strong enough to send data to Earth. By turning the spacecraft up-side-down during the other half of its halo orbit, the coverage is doubled. Since July 8, 2003, SOHO is rolled (rotated around the X-axis pointing to the centre of the Sun) 180 degrees approximately every three months. In other words, the nominal roll attitude of SOHO switches between 0 and 180 degrees every 3 months.

The SOHO roll attitude is listed in:

http://sohowww.nascom.nasa.gov/data/ancillary/attitude/roll/nominal_roll_attitude.dat.

The value of the nominal roll attitude in the file of the above link is either 0 or 180. There is no actual roll determination to refine this figure as function of time during the roll. For this reason, the values should only be used for periods when the spacecraft is in Normal Mode (i.e. not during manoeuvres or other special operations).

SOHO rolls have effect particularly on the ERNE directional measurements. As the direction of the HED view cone axis is 45° from the SOHO roll axis, the roll results in a transformation of the direction of the recording bins. Nominally the HED viewcone axis is pointing 45° west from the Sun. During inverted roll attitude (roll angle 180°) of SOHO, HED is pointing 45° east of the Sun and is upside down. The remapping of the direction bins is shown schematically in Figure 4.10.

Figure 4.10. Transformation of the ERNE/HED directional bins when SOHO rolls from the nominal orientation (roll angle 0°) to inverted roll attitude (roll angle 180°).

When SOHO is in the "middle" parts of its orbit, it is not possible to point the spacecraft to the Sun while also pointing the high-gain antenna towards Earth. These parts of the orbit are called SOHO "keyhole periods", and they occur twice per orbit. SOHO's each halo orbit around L1 takes about half a year, so keyholes affect SOHO operations roughly every 3 months. The SOHO keyhole periods are listed in <http://soho.nascom.nasa.gov/soc/keyholes.txt>

5 Energy spectra of protons, helium, and heavy ions

Figure 5.1 and Figure 5.2 show examples of proton and helium spectra measured by SOHO/ERNE. The data are from a big SEP event of November 01, 2004, from a small event of November 13, 1997, and from a very small event of May 19, 2007. A specific feature of the May 19, 2007 event visible in both proton and helium spectra is the “bump” of first increasing and then decreasing intensity starting at about 50 MeV/n. The increase is partly caused by galactic cosmic rays with their rising energy spectra forming the quasi-static background. In the case of protons there is also a contribution from the background caused by galactic cosmic-ray protons and helium penetrating the instrument (see Figure 4.5). However, above about 70-80 MeV/n there seems to be a steep cut-off of the spectra although the galactic cosmic ray spectrum should be steadily rising in this energy range. This is particularly well visible in the proton spectrum of May 19, 2007, but is also seen as a steep fall of the big event of November 1, 2004. Such steep fall is not present in the November 13, 1997 proton spectrum, but this could of cause also be due to the nature of this SEP event. Comparing the helium spectra (Figure 5.2) one can see the rise caused by galactic cosmic ray helium in the events of November 13, 1997 and May 19, 2007 (both at the time of solar minimum activity), while in the event of November 1, 2004 event galactic cosmic rays are still masked by solar energetic particles up to 70 MeV/n. In the November 1, 2004 and May 19, 2007 events the intensities then sharply fall. Although this also occurs in the November 13, 1997 event, the fall is not as strong.

Figure 5.1. Examples of proton energy spectra measured by ERNE during three time periods. Note that the intensity of the highest-energy point of the May 18, 2007 events is just at the lower limit of $10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1} \text{ MeV}^{-1}$ of the plot.

Figure 5.2. Examples of helium energy spectra measured by ERNE during three time periods.

Figure 5.3. Comparison of ^{12}C spectrum measured by SOHO/ERNE, ACE/SIS, and ACE/CRIS during the period October 31 – November 5 in 2004 (from [AD 3]).

An explanation for the sharp fall of intensities above about 70-80 MeV/n could be that the geometric factors used to convert counts to intensities are seriously overestimated at least for the

two highest energy channels of ERNE. This could be related to the change of the available energy channels and the corresponding geometric factors since April 19, 2000. Or perhaps it can be due to an unnoticed malfunction of one or more of the D3 scintillator bars (see Figure 3.2), which all are connected in parallel to one amplifier channel. To find out the origin and true nature of the apparent cut-off of the spectra needs further investigation, and the need and a possible method for correction is not currently known.

A similar cut-off as in the proton and helium spectra is present also in the heavy ion spectra measured by ERNE. Figure 5.3 shows the carbon spectrum measured by ERNE during the end of October – beginning of November 2004 (thus covering the November 1, 2004 SEP event). The ERNE spectrum is compared in the figure with those of ACE/SIS and ACE/CRIS. While the agreement of the spectra is good at low energies, there is some systematic disagreement at the highest energies and the intensity measured by ERNE in its highest energy channel seems to fall well below that of ACE/CRIS.

All the spectra presented in Figure 5.1 and Figure 5.2 as well as spectra from some additional events have been compared in [AD 3] with measurements of other instruments from which data have been provided for SEPServer. Comparisons of ERNE heavy ion spectra with those of ACE have also been carried out in [AD 3].

6 Conclusions

Major parts of this document are devoted for the description of the SOHO/ERNE instrument, the functional characteristics of the hardware and software, the caveats resulting from certain design and operational flaws of the instrument, and the resulting quality of the data delivered for SEPServer.

The most significant findings, of which the user of the SOHO/ERNE data should be aware of, can be summarized as follows:

1. Effect of signal thresholds (Section 4.2)
 - a. For those time periods when the higher signal threshold level (3xHIT) is used for initiating the data collection cycle, only interpolated proton and helium data are provided. These time periods are flagged in the status word of the data.
 - b. The lower signal threshold (1xHIT) may have an effect on the energy spectra of heavy ions resulting in reduced intensities in particular at high energies (Figure 4.3 and Figure 4.4).
2. During large events ERNE/HED saturates (Section 4.3, Table 4.1)
3. Inefficiency of the anticoincidence detectors of ERNE/HED causes a background in particular for high-energy protons, which during quiet times is significant (Section 4.4, Figure 4.6).
4. SOHO rolls change the view direction of ERNE sensors from the direction of the nominal Parker magnetic field line to 45° east from the Sun (Section 4.8). SOHO keyhole periods cause gaps in the ERNE data (Section 4.8, Figure 4.9).
5. Distortions in energy spectra.
 - a. There is a possible cut-off of the energy spectra of protons and ^4He above about 70-

80 MeV/n and at >100 MeV/n for heavy ions (Section 5, Figure 5.1, Figure 5.2, and Figure 5.3).

- b. There is a tendency that the intensities of heavy ions (in particular of oxygen) in the lowest energy channel of ERNE/HED are unexpectedly low (Figure 3.7, Figure 4.3, Figure 4.4).

SEP Server

Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report ACE/EPAM Instrument description and data quality

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Summary

This document contains the Solar Energetic Particle Instrument Document and Data Quality Report for the SEPServer database server. Herein the following three sections are included:

1. Description the ACE/EPAM instrumentation
2. Data sets delivered
3. Caveats and quality assessment.

In Section 2 a detailed description on the ACE/EPAM instrumentation is provided. It includes details on the two basic telescopes of EPAM, namely LEFS and LEMS, together with the basic scientific objectives of the instrument. Section 3 refers to the datasets delivered to SEPServer in terms of the format of the files and contents as well as to special features of the datasets that currently are available though the SEPServer database. Section 4 describes the quality controls and the caveats spotted at the EPAM data. The LEFS150 malfunction issue is being reported. The results of the detailed checks for solar contamination from solar photons as well as for cross-talk contamination are presented with examples and are tabulated for the whole mission duration. Finally, a summary of the limitations of the dataset is presented at the end of this document.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document contains the Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report (DDR) of the Electron Proton and Alpha Monitor (EPAM) for the SEPServer database server.

The DDR is roughly broken down into the following components:

1. Description the ACE/EPAM instrumentation
2. Data sets delivered
3. Caveats and quality assessment.

Each topic will be discussed in detail in a section of the document.

1.2 Applicable documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
AD1	Description of Work	EC-GA #262773, Annex I	10 Dec 2010
AD2	Data Delivery Plan	SEPSERVER-009-CAU-WP2	02 Oct 2012

1.3 Reference documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
RD1	Electron, Proton, and Alpha Monitor on the Advanced Composition Explorer Spacecraft	Gold, et al. Space Sci. Rev. 86, 541,1998	

RD2	An Analysis of Solar Energetic Particle Spectra Throughout the Inner Heliosphere	Patterson J. D. Ph.D. Thesis, 2002	
RD3	The Advanced Composition Explorer	Stone et al., Space Sci. Rev. 86, 1,1998	
RD4	Monte Carlo simulation of MFSA response to RTG gamma rays	Gomez, Fundamental Technologies, 1996	
RD5	Near-relativistic electron events. Monte Carlo simulations of solar injection and interplanetary transport	Agueda N., Ph.D. Thesis, Universitat de Barcelona, 2008	

1.4 Abbreviations and acronyms

ACE	Advanced Composition Explorer
CA	Composition Aperture
DDP	Data Delivery Plan
DDR	Data Delivery Report
DE	Deflected Electrons
EPAM	Electron, Proton, and Alpha Monitor
HISCALE	Heliosphere Instrument for Spectra, Composition and Anisotropy at Low Energies
IPM	Interplanetary Medium
LEFS	Low Energy Foil Spectrometers
LEMS	Low Energy Magnetic Spectrometers
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
SEPServer	Data Services and Analysis Tools for Solar Energetic Particle Events and Related Electromagnetic Emissions

2 ACE/EPAM description

The Electron Proton Alpha Monitor (EPAM) on board the Advanced Composition Explorer (ACE) is the flight-spare of the Heliospheric Instrument for Spectra, Composition, and Anisotropy at Low Energy (HISCALE) on board Ulysses. Therefore, aside from some minor issues, the two instruments are identical. EPAM onboard ACE has been described in RD1, RD2. In what follows some parts are repeated in order to better understand the limitation and quality of the data.

EPAM was constructed to investigate low energy ions and electrons. There are five main telescopes on the EPAM instrument: the composition aperture (CA), two low energy magnetically shielded telescopes (LEMS30 and LEMS120) and two low energy foil shielded telescopes (LEFS60 and LEFS150). A schematic of these five telescopes can be seen in **Figure 1**. The name of each telescope is representative of the type of shielding that is used and its look direction relative to the spacecraft spin axis. For example, LEMS30 is magnetically shielded and its look direction is 30 degrees off the spin axis, whereas LEFS150 is foil shielded and its look direction is 150 degrees off the spin axis. At the base of the two LEMS and the two LEFS telescopes lie 2000-micron solid-state wafers that serve as the detecting devices.

The two Low Energy Foil Spectrometers (LEFS) measure the flux and direction of electrons above 30 keV (geometry factor = 0.397 cm² sr) - the LEFS are pointed 60° and 150° from the spacecraft spin axis and are known as the LEFS60 and LEFS150 telescopes, the two Low Energy Magnetic Spectrometers (LEMS) measure the flux and direction of ions greater than 50 keV (geometry factor = 0.48 cm² sr) - the two LEMS sensors are oriented 30° and 120° from the spin axis and are identified as LEMS30 and LEMS120, and the Composition Aperture (CA) measures the elemental composition of the ions (geometry factor = 0.24 cm² sr) - its look-direction is oriented 60° from the spacecraft spin-axis and so is known as the CA60 telescope. The telescopes use the spin of the spacecraft to sweep the full 4π sky (**Figure 2**). ACE/EPAM omnidirectional data, which are the averaged data over all sectors of each telescope; consist of electrons and ions in the

energy range from about 50 keV to 5 MeV.

Figure 1 LEMS30/LEFS150 and LEFS60/LEMS120 Telescope Assemblies for HISCALE [taken by RD2]

Figure 2 EPAM viewing cones with respect to ACE spin axis [taken by RD1]

Most of the goals and objectives for ACE mission involve compositional and origin studies of the various particle populations that are found in the near IPM. These goals are as follows [RD3]:

- Determine the solar isotopic abundances through direct sampling of solar material,
- Determine the elemental and isotopic composition of the solar corona, interplanetary pick-up ions, and anomalous cosmic rays,
- Explain the formation processes for the solar corona and the acceleration of the solar wind, and
- Characterize the mechanisms of energetic particle acceleration and transport in the heliosphere.

2.1 The low energy Magnetically Shielded (LEMS) Telescopes

The LEMS30 and LEMS120 telescopes use a magnetic field to shield the M and M' detectors, respectively, from any incoming electrons. **Figure 1** shows the two detectors and the location of the shielding magnets. In the illustration of the LEMS120 telescope, the magnetic field runs from the top pole to the bottom, and in the illustration of the LEMS30 telescope, the magnetic field is directed into the page. The shielding magnetic field of the LEMS30 telescope directs the incoming electrons toward the bottom detector in the CA60 stack, whereas the electrons entering the LEMS120 telescope are allowed to impact the wall of the telescope housing.

One concern with the LEMS120 telescope is the effect of the electrons scattered from the telescope housing on the observed count rates in the M' detector. It is conceivable that a scattered electron with sufficient energy could be incorrectly interpreted by the detector as a proton. Modeling of this process has shown that this is an unlikely event [RD6].

Another possible source of electron contamination of the M and M' detectors is the arrival of an electron energetic enough to not be deflected sufficiently by the shielding magnetic field and striking the detector. The energy of an electron capable of this, however, is

significantly higher than the penetration energy of the detector. Such an occurrence is ignored by the detector electronics [RD4].

The electrons that are deflected by the shielding magnetic field in the LEMS30 telescope are detected by the B detector at the base of the detector stack for the CA60 telescope. The counts measured by this detector are recorded in the four DE (Deflected Electron) channels and can be assumed to be only electrons (i.e. 'pure electrons').

2.2 The low energy Foil Shielded (LEFS) Telescopes

The LEFS60 and LEFS150 telescopes utilize a utilize an aluminized Parylene foil, nominally 0.35 mg cm^{-2} thick, to block low energy ions [RD7]. The foil does a modest job of this, but does not work well at all for shielding higher energy ions with energies about 300 keV-nuc^{-1} or greater. Because of this leakage of higher energy ions through the foil shield, the counts recorded by the F and F' detectors are not exclusively electrons, even at low energies. The ions that pass through the foil deposit energy into the detector that, of course, does not match the incident energy, but is monotonically related to the incident energy.

Another source of contamination is the forward scattering of electrons by energetic ions incident on the foil shield. One way to obtain an estimate of the number of counts attributable to this phenomenon is to compare the F and F' data, corrected for the contributions of ions incident on the detector, with the DE data. When the electron distribution is isotropic, the two means of measuring electron counts should be in good agreement. If forward-scattered electrons provide a significant contribution to the count rates in the F and F' detectors, it will be readily apparent when compared to the DE data (see section 4.3 for details).

3 Data Delivery

3.1 Format of the ACE/EPAM delivered data

The ACE/EPAM data that have been delivered to SEPServer include electron and ion omnidirectional as well as sectorized counting rates. The two LEFS telescopes measure the flux and direction of electrons above 30 keV while the two LEMS telescopes measure the flux and direction of ions above 50 keV. Sectorized data have been delivered for all telescopes in all energy ranges. These directional counting rates consist of 8 sectors for ions and 4 sectors for electrons with 12-s time resolution. All data have been provided in ASCII files. The file format of the ACE/EPAM data delivered to SEPServer has been described in details the Data Delivery Plan (DDP) [AD2].

3.2 Special features of the delivered datasets

The ACE/EPAM data that have been delivered to SEPServer are unique in the sense that those include apart from the actual count and the timestamp for both the sectorized and omni-directional sets, the duty cycle, the accumulation time and the uncertainty for each entry in the datasets (see AD2 for details).

4 Data Caveats

Known malfunction of LEMS150 has been reported since almost the beginning of the ACE mission (see **Section 4.1**). There are some troublesome solar X-ray influences in the LEMS30 detector at times (see **Section 4.2**). Furthermore, contamination arises from electrons recorded as ions and vice versa [cross-talk] (see **Section 4.3**).

4.1 LEFS150 Malfunction on EPAM

In 1998, late in day 78, the LEFS150 detector on EPAM began to malfunction. The count rates at low energies soared upwards by as much as four orders of magnitude. As a result, the data from the LEFS150 detector were deemed too contaminated for use and subsequent data, although still collected, are ignored. As the LEMS30 detector experiences solar contamination (see the next section), this leaves only two detectors,

LEFS60 and LEMS120 that remain fully functional on EPAM. [RD5].

4.2 Solar Contamination

During half of the spin of the spacecraft, the LEMS30 telescope is exposed directly to the solar disc and, therefore, solar X-rays. For EPAM, the contamination is a constant problem. The counts in the lower discriminator channels are severely elevated in sectors 2 and 3 for the LEMS30 instrument. Sectors 1 and 4 are unaffected since the telescope has turned away from the solar disc slightly during these portions of the spin (see **Table 1** and **Figure 3**).

Table 1 DOYs with X-ray contamination for the whole mission

Year	Day of Year	Description of the problem
1997	242-365	Channels P1, P2 : Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only the sectors S1, S4
1998	1-365	Channels P1, P2: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
1999	1-365	Channels P1, P2: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	50	All sectors ok !
2000	1-199	Channels P1, P2: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	200-209	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	210-310	Channels P1, P2, P3: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	311-339	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	340-359	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	360-366	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
2001	1-50	Channels P1, P2, P3: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	51-184	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	185-200 201-249 251-300	Channels P1, P2, P3: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	250 301-362	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	363-365	Channel P1: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4 http://www.swpc.noaa.gov/ftpd/ir/lists/ace/README In late November and early December 2001 the P1 channel

		(47 to 65 keV) data increased during an energetic particle event (small radiation storm) and never returned to nominal levels. The channel became "noisy" and after monitoring for a few weeks the decision was made to replace the P1 channel with the P2 channel (65 to 112 keV) data, the next higher energy channel within the same detector on EPAM, from that point on. During the later part of December 2001 the P5 channel (310 to 580 keV) showed anomalous periods of increased particle flux. The instrument PI from JHU/APL determined that when the detector was pointed in the general direction of the sun, the sector pointed toward the sun showed large increases in particle flux. This is believed to be due to solar contamination and only happens during limited times between each set of spacecraft maneuvers. The decision was to change the processing of all channels from this detector to eliminate the solar noise problem. A third problem was induced by the solar noise problem: Whenever the P5 channel became noisy the P1 and P3 data would drop out. The cause of the drop out was a programming filter designed to eliminate "bad" data. Since not all of the data were "bad", only the sunward directed sector, a decision was made to eliminate all data from the sunward sector. Problems two and three were solved by the removal of the data from the sunward sectors for all channels. The only impact from removing the sunward sector data is larger statistical fluctuations in the sector-integrated data when the flux is near background levels.
2002	1	Channel P1: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	2-6	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	7-10	Channels P1, P2: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	11-18	Channels P1, P2, P3: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	19-100	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	101-350	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	351-365	Channels P1, P2 : Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
2003	301, 306-307	The EPAM/LEMS120 ion time-intensity profiles indicate time intervals with possible electron contamination (Figure 4, Lario et al., JGR, VOL. 110, A09S11, doi:10.1029/2004JA010940, 2005).
	1	Channels P1, P2, P3: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	2-59	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	60-304	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	305-329	All sectors ok !
	330	Channel P7: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use only sectors S1, S4
	331-365	Channel P5: Contamination in sectors S2, S3. We must use

		only sectors S1, S4
2004	1-4	Channel P5: Contamination in sectors S2, S3 . We must use only sectors S1, S4
	5-185	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Contamination in sectors S2, S3 . We must use only sectors S1, S4
	186-250	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5: Contamination in sectors S2, S3 . We must use only sectors S1, S4
	251-315	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Contamination in sectors S2, S3 . We must use only sectors S1, S4
	316-366	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5: Contamination in sectors S2, S3 . We must use only sectors S1, S4
2005	20	The spectral index of the peak sector is well-represented by $\gamma = 1.45$ for the LEFS60 electrons and $\gamma = 1.05$ for the deflected electrons. Thus the hard spectrum strongly suggests that we are witnessing directly-accelerated flare electrons. The differences in spectral index are probably due to ion contamination in the LEFS60 detector ; thus we have more confidence to the spectrum from the deflected electrons. (Simnett, A&A 445, 715–724, DOI: 10.1051/0004-6361:20053503, 2006).
	1-251	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4, P5: Contamination in sectors S2, S3 . We must use only sectors S1, S4
	299-365	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Contamination in sectors S2, S3 . We must use only sectors S1, S4
2006	1-364	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Contamination in sectors S2, S3 . We must use only sectors S1, S4
	365	All sectors ok !
2007	1	All sectors ok !
	2-249	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Contamination in sectors S2, S3 . We must use only sectors S1, S4
	250	All sectors ok !
	251-365	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Contamination in sectors S2, S3 . We must use only sectors S1, S4
2008	1-366	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Contamination in sectors S2, S3 . We must use only sectors S1, S4
2009	1-365	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Contamination in sectors S2, S3 . We must use only sectors S1, S4
2010	1-365	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Contamination in sectors S2, S3 . We must use only sectors S1, S4
2011	1-59	Channels P1, P2, P3, P4: Contamination in sectors S2, S3 . We must use only sectors S1, S4

Figure 3 X-ray contamination as spotted in the high-resolution EPAM data for DOY 149 in 2009 (right panel) versus non-contaminated rates on DOY 1 in 2009 (left panel).

4.3 Cross-talk

Electrons are magnetically deflected in the LEMS30 and LEMS120 telescopes, and those deflected from the LEMS30 telescope are detected by an off-axis detector that separates them in four different energy channels referred to as DE1–4 or ‘pure electrons’ [RD3]. This magnetic deflection system diverts a very high fraction of electrons that enter the LEMS collimators. However, when the >50 keV electron flux is sufficiently high, some electrons are counted in the LEMS30 and LEMS120 telescopes, even though the absolute efficiency for counting these electrons is quite small. Thus the ion channels may be contaminated at the beginning of large SEP events when many electrons arrive promptly, well before the slower ions can reach the spacecraft [RD4].

4.3.1 Comparison between LEFS60/LEMS30/LEMS120

Furthermore, contamination from ions is possible in the LEFS60 data. Therefore, we qualitatively compare clean electron measurements (from DEs) to LEFS60 data and to ion measurements (from LEMS120). When data are not contaminated we expect similar trends in the electron profiles observed by the two telescopes. If we spot a significant difference then we compare the electron profile from LEFS60 to the ion profile from LEMS120. Usually, when contamination is present these latter profiles follow each other’s trend. An example of such comparison is presented in **Figure 4** and the corresponding results are tabulated in **Table 2**.

ACE/EPAM spin-averaged data E'1, P'1, DE1 channels, Year 2000

Data time-resolution: ~2min

— Fitting curve (method: running averaging, window width:51)

Figure 4 Example of the comparison between E's (LEFS60), P's (LEMS120) (top panel), DE (LEMS30) (middle panel) and their corresponding ratio $J_{E'} / J_{DE}$ (bottom panel). Contamination is clear as the E's profile does not follow the DEs one and the ration exceeds 1 in this example. The contamination is indicated with a purple background in the figure.

4.3.2 Comparison between LEFS60/LEMS30

Contamination from ions, is possible in the LEFS60 (E' chan.) data. Therefore we qualitatively compare DE (LEMS30) electron measurements to LEFS60 data. When the data are not contaminated, we expect similar trends in the electron spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences may be caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5 Example of the comparison between E's (LEFS60) (top panel), DE (LEMS30) (middle panel) and their ratio (bottom panel). No contamination has been spotted in this example.

Table 2 DOYs with contamination due to cross-talk

Year	Day of Year	Description of the problem
1997	242-365	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
1998	1-365	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
1999	1-40, 42-365	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	41	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions
2000	1-41/12:00, 45-50, 52-113, 115-157, 159 162-169, 171-181/12:00, 182-261/14:00, 262-300, 303-366	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	41/12:00-43/12:00, 44/00:00-44/12:00, 51, 114 158, 160-161, 170 181/12:00-181/24:00, 261/14:00-261/24:00, 301-302	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions
2001	1-30, 33-98, 103-131/12:00, 132/04:00-222/12:00, 225/12:00-294, 296-325, 327-361, 362/12:00-365	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	31-32, 99-102, 131/12:00-132/04:00, 222/12:00-225/12:00, 295, 326 362/00:00-	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions

	362/12:00	
2002	1-76, 78-82/16:00, 84-229, 231-251/12:00, 252/12:00-330/08:00, 333/06:00-365	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	77, 82/16:00-83, 230, 251/12:00-252/12:00, 330/08:00-333/06:00	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions
2003	1-32, 33/18:00-323, 325-365	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	33/00:00-33/18:00, 324	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions
2004	1-22, 24/18:00-43, 44/05:00-101, 103-213, 214/12:00-311, 313-314/08:00, 314/18:00-366	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	23-24/18:00, 44/00:00-44/05:00, 102, 214/00:00-214/12:00, 312, 314/08:00-314/18:00	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions
2005	1-164, 165/18:00-244/12:00, 245/17:00-365/07:00	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	165/00:00-165/18:00, 244/12:00-245/17:00, 365/07:00-365/24:00	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions
2006	1-347, 349-365	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	348	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions
2007	1-365	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-

		averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
2008	1-366	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
2009	1-365	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
2010	1-248, 250/08:00-365	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated
	249-250/08:00	Contamination in LEFS60 (E' channels) from LEMS120 (P') ions
2011	1-59	The profiles of DE and E' electrons present similar trends in the spin-averaged profiles observed by the two telescopes; small differences caused by the fact that the two telescopes sweep different regions of space; i.e. E' channels are non-contaminated

4.4 Summary of Limitation and Caveats of the EPAM data

Known limitations/caveats:

1. Data from the LEFS150 detector were deemed too contaminated for use and subsequent data, although still collected, are ignored.
2. Solar X-ray contamination tabulated results present in **Table 1**
3. Cross-talk contamination results tabulated in **Table 2**

SEPServer

Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report ACE/SIS Instrument description and data quality

	Name	Signature	Date
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Checked by	B. Heber		
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DISTRIBUTION

Name	Organisation

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21.11.2012	0.1			First draft
22.01.2013	1.	0		Consolidation of team inputs
20.05.2013	1.	1	Several pages	Several additions based on comments by BH
14.10.2013	1.	2	Several pages	Several additions based on comments by RV

Summary

This document contains the Solar Energetic Particle Instrument Document and Data Quality Report for the SEPServer database server. Herein the following three sections are included:

1. Description the ACE/SIS instrumentation
2. Data sets delivered
3. Caveats and quality assessment.

In Section 2 a detailed description on the ACE/SIS instrumentation is provided, including a summary of its characteristics together with the basic scientific objectives of the instrument. Section 3 refers to the datasets delivered to SEPServer in terms of the format of the files and contents that currently are available through the SEPServer database. Section 4 provides a summary of the known limitations of the SIS data and tabulates the time periods that need to be used with caution from the user of SEPServer. Finally, a summary of the dataset distributed by SEPServer is presented at the end of this document.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document contains the Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report (DDR) of the Solar Isotope Spectrometer (SIS) for the SEPServer database server.

The DDR's roughly break down into the following components:

1. Description the ACE/SIS instrumentation
2. Data sets delivered
3. Caveats and quality assessment.

Each topic will be discussed in detail in a section of the document.

1.2 Applicable documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
AD1	Description of Work	EC-GA #262773, Annex I	10 Dec 2010
AD2	Data Delivery Plan	SEPSERVER-009-CAU-WP2	02 Oct 2012

1.3 Reference documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
RD1	The Solar Isotope Spectrometer for the Advanced Composition Explorer	Stone, et al. Space Sci. Rev. 86, 357, 1998	
RD2	ACE Science Center	http://www.srl.caltech.edu/ACE/ASC/level2/sis_l2desc.html	
RD3	ACE/SIS Caltech website	http://www.srl.caltech.edu/ACE/CRIS_SIS/sis.html	

1.4 Abbreviations and acronyms

ACE	Advanced Composition Explorer
ACRs	Anomalous Cosmic Rays
DDP	Data Delivery Plan
DDR	Data Delivery Report
GCRs	Galactic Cosmic Rays
LISM	Local Interstellar Medium
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
SEPs	Solar Energetic Particles
SEP Server	Data Services and Analysis Tools for Solar Energetic Particle Events and Related Electromagnetic Emissions
SIS	Solar Isotope Spectrometer

2 ACE/SIS description

The Solar Isotope Spectrometer (SIS) (see **Figure 1**) has been thoroughly presented in [RD1] and [RD3], therefore several parts will be repeated in this document in order to illustrate the capabilities and the scientific usage of the instrument. ACE/SIS is designed to provide high-resolution measurements of the isotopic composition of energetic nuclei from He to Zn ($Z = 2$ to 30) over the energy range from ~ 10 to ~ 100 MeV/nuc. During large solar events SIS measures the isotopic abundances of solar energetic particles (SEPs) to determine directly the composition of the solar corona and to study particle acceleration processes. During solar quiet times SIS measures the isotopes of low-energy cosmic rays from the Galaxy (GCRs) and isotopes of the anomalous cosmic ray (ACRs) component, which originates in the nearby interstellar medium (LISM). **Table 1** summarizes key characteristics of the SIS instrument.

Figure 1 Photograph of the SIS instrument with the acoustic covers open. The dimensions of the housing are 30:0 X 41:9 X 27:5 cm. [taken from RD1]

Table 1 Summary of SIS characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Measurement objective	Elemental and isotopic composition of SEPs, ACRs and low-energy GCRs
Measurement technique	Multiple- ΔE vs. residual energy, plus trajectory
Energy Loss Measurements	Two detector stacks, each composed of 15 ion-implanted Si detectors of varying thicknesses, all 10 cm in diameter
Trajectory Measurements	Two 2-dimensional Si multi-strip detectors per stack; 6 cm separation; position resolution ~ 0.29 mm
Energy Interval for Mass Analysis	
O	10 – 90 MeV/nucleon
Si	13 – 125 MeV/nucleon
Fe	17 – 170 MeV/nucleon
Field of view	95° full angle
Geometry factor	38.4 cm ² sr
Event yields (large SEPs)	$>10^5$ O ; $>10^4$ Fe

There are two identical telescopes in SIS, referred to as “A” and “B”, respectively. Each is composed of 17 high-purity silicon detectors as shown in **Figure 3** and summarized in **Table 2**. The top two detectors, M1 and M2, are position sensitive (“matrix”) devices that form the hodoscope and measure both the trajectory and energy loss of incident nuclei. Below M1 and M2 is a 15-element energy-loss stack composed of thicker, single-electrode silicon devices. Stack detectors have 65 cm² active areas and would be completely circular in shape (with 46 mm radii) but for a 42 mm long orientation flat. Thicknesses range from 100 μ m to 3.75 mm and progress with depth in each telescope. Note that T6 and T7 are composite devices made by summing the outputs of three and six wafers, respectively. The crystal axes of all detectors are aligned, which allows particle channeling effects to be more easily recognized.

Figure 2 Scale drawing of one of the two SIS telescopes, showing only the active regions of the detectors. Detector designations are listed at right, while the total silicon thicknesses are listed at left. The metallized kapton entrance foils total ~7.2 mg/cm² thick. The opening angle of 95° is an average which accounts for the octagonal shape of the matrix detectors [taken by RD1]

The apertures of the SIS telescopes are covered by three Kapton windows that provide protection from sunlight and micro-meteorites. The combined thickness of these windows has a stopping power that is equivalent to ~31 μm of silicon.

Table 2 SIS detector design characteristics

Range	Detector name	Nominal Detector Thickness (mm)	Active area (cm ²)	Geometry factor (cm ² sr)
-	M1	0.075	34	~150
R0	M2	0.075	34	38.4
R1	T1	0.1	65	38.4
R2	T2	0.1	65	37.2
R3	T3	0.25	65	36.6
R4	T4	0.5	65	34.4
R5	T5	0.75	65	33
R6	T6	2.65	65	27.2
R7	T7	3.75	65	19.4
R8	T8	1	65	19.4

SIS aims to achieve the objectives of excellent mass resolution and large collecting power beyond that of previous instruments that have measured ACRs and SEPs, therefore SIS needs to satisfy several design requirements. First of all, it must have a mass resolution of ~ 0.25 amu or better. In addition one should note that measurements of SEPs are usually made in a very hostile environment in which the flux of protons >1 MeV may exceed $10^5/\text{cm}^2\text{-sr-sec}$. Chance of coincidences between these low energy protons and the heavier nuclei that are of primary interest to SIS can lead to ambiguous trajectories or distorted energy loss measurements. It is therefore necessary that SIS be capable of returning accurate composition measurements in the presence of high fluxes of low energy protons and helium nuclei. To ensure that as few as possible of the nuclei with $Z \geq 10$ are missed requires that the instrument be capable of selecting the most interesting nuclei for analysis and that the bit rate be sufficient to transmit several events per second. Σφάλμα! Το αρχείο προέλευσης της αναφοράς δεν βρέθηκε. shows the energy and charge intervals for which isotopic analysis is possible (in gray). Particle elemental identification can be continued to higher energies, while integral fluxes can be calculated from events fully penetrating the telescope.

Figure 3 SIS energy range for nuclei with $1 \leq Z \leq 30$. In addition SIS will make exploratory measurements of SEP nuclei with $31 \leq Z \leq 40$. [taken from RD2]

Measurements of ACRs, free from contamination of solar and interplanetary particles at lower energy and free from GCR contamination at higher energy are best made in the energy interval from ~ 5 to 25 MeV/nucleon, where the flux is a decreasing function of energy. Similarly, SEP spectra typically decrease rather steeply with increasing energy. It follows that to maximize the number of detected particles for both of these species requires the use of thin detectors with as low a threshold for penetration as possible, combined with a large geometry factor. For this reason SIS has two telescopes composed of the largest area devices available (~ 65 cm² each). It is also of interest to extend measurements of SEPs to as high energy as possible to understand the acceleration process in these events. The SIS detector stack is composed of devices of graduated

thicknesses in order to cover a broad energy range. There are two identical telescopes in SIS (one pictured here), each composed of 17 high-purity silicon detectors.

Goals and objectives for SIS instrument involve the provision of high-resolution measurements of the isotopic composition of energetic nuclei from He to Ni ($Z=2$ to 28) over the energy range from ~ 10 to ~ 100 MeV/nucleon. Therefore SIS identifies the isotopic composition of SEPs, given its greatly improved collecting power over earlier instruments. Finally, it has been used to facilitate the need for Space Weather services [RD2]. In summary, the science objectives of SIS are summarized as follows [RD1]:

- The Isotopic Composition of SEPs
- The Isotopic Composition of ACRs and Local Interstellar Medium (LIM)
- Studies of Low Energy GCRs Isotopes
- Space Weather

2.1 The SIS sensor system

The sensor system is illustrated in **Figure 3** and in **Figure 4**. As noted here above, there are two identical telescopes in SIS, referred to as “A” and “B”, respectively and each is composed of 17 high-purity silicon detectors. The top two detectors, M1 and M2, are position sensitive (“matrix”) devices that form the hodoscope and measure both the trajectory and energy loss of incident nuclei. The matrix detectors are octagonal in shape, 70 to 80 μm in thickness, and have 34 cm^2 active areas that are divided into 64 strips (see Figure 5). The strips are 0.96 mm wide, separated by 0.040 mm gaps, and oriented in perpendicular directions on opposite sides to provide both X and Y axis readout.

Figure 4 Scale drawing of one of the two SIS telescopes, similar to Figure 2, showing the particle's detection. Matrix detectors have 64 strips on each side, oriented in perpendicular directions to provide both X and Y readouts [taken from RD3]

Figure 5 SIS matrix detector. Each surface of the detector has 64 metallized strips. The X-surface strips are orthogonal to the Y-surface strips and all strips are individually pulse-height analyzed. [taken from RD1]

Valid events in SIS typically require a coincidence between M1A and M2A or between M1B and M2B (where A and B refer to the A and B telescopes, respectively).

3 Data Delivery

3.1 Format of the ACE/SIS delivered data

SIS records and transmits a variety of count rates, some primarily to assess the health of the instrument, others crucial for determining event detection efficiencies in order to properly calculate absolute particle fluxes. These rates are summed over the entire 256 second instrument cycle (SIS does not measure “sector” rates over fractions of the ~12

second spacecraft spin period and is not designed to look for particle anisotropies). ACE/SIS data that have been delivered to SEP Server include omnidirectional fluxes and counts of He, C, O and Fe. Eight energy bins apply to each element but for different energy partitions, i.e. He ranges between 3.43–41.19 MeV, C ranges between 6.42–76.34 MeV, O ranges between: 7.29–89.78 MeV and Fe ranges between 10.68–167.66 MeV. All data have been provided in ASCII files. The files format of the ACE/SIS data delivered to SEP Server has been described in details the Data Delivery Plan (DDP) [AD2].

4 Data Caveats

Known malfunction and caveats of the SIS have been reported since almost the beginning of the ACE mission [RD2]. In what follows a summary of the known limitations and caveats of the SIS data is presented (Section 4.1).

4.1 Summary of Limitation and Caveats of the SIS data

During time periods of extremely low livetime, the SIS on-board processing gives priority to analyzing and telemetering higher-energy, Z>=6 ions. During such times the efficiency corrections for He and low-energy heavy ions are substantial and the raw counts can be quite low. Users of ACE/SIS data are cautioned that high-time resolution (e.g., 256 sec) intensities during such time periods may be very uncertain and are encouraged to use a lower-time resolution (e.g., 1 hour) products when the raw counts for the species of interest are low. Below is a listing of time periods during which the SIS livetime was below 10% of nominal. Users should be aware that the effect on He intensities can last longer than the effect on heavier ions and so should be cautious using 256-sec He data a few hours before and after the time periods listed below:

Table 3 Time periods to use with caution in SIS data

Year	START			STOP			Note
	Month/Day	DOY	HR	Month/Day	DOY	HR	
1997	07.Nov	311	16	11.Nov	315	16	thresholds raised on some stack detectors
1998	21.Apr	111	15	25.Apr	115	16	thresholds raised on all stack detectors
1998	25.Aug	237	16	27.Aug	237	17	thresholds raised on some stack detectors
2000	14.Jul	196	11	15.Jul	197	19	livetime < 10%

2000	14.Jul	196	16	18.Jul	200	19	thresholds	raised	on	all	stack	detectors
2000	09.Nov	314	0	13.Nov	318	17	livetime	<	10%			
2001	03.Apr	93	6	03.Apr	93	7	livetime	<	10%			
2001	24.Sep	267	20	26.Sep	269	12	livetime	<	10%			
2001	02.Oct	275	6	02.Oct	275	8	livetime	<	10%			
2001	05.Nov	309	1	06.Nov	310	12	livetime	<	10%			
2001	23.Nov	327	6	24.Nov	328	15	livetime	<	10%			
2002	21.Apr	111	7	22.Apr	112	7	livetime	<	10%			
2003	28.Oct	301	13	30.Oct	303	21	livetime	<	10%			
2003	02.Nov	306	20	03.Nov	307	22	livetime	<	10%			
2003	04.Dec	338	6	04.Dec	338	8	livetime	<	10%			
2005	17.Jan	17	15	18.Jan	18	11	livetime	<	10%			
2005	20.Jan	20	6	20.Jan	20	16	livetime	<	10%			
2005	15.May	135	0	15.May	135	5	livetime	<	10%			
2005	10.Sep	253	9	12.Sep	255	22	livetime	<	10%			
2005	13.Oct	286	16	13.Oct	286	17	livetime	<	10%			
2005	02.Nov	306	16	02.Nov	306	18	livetime	<	10%			
2005	09.Nov	313	16	09.Nov	313	17	livetime	<	10%			
2006	07.Dec	341	15	08.Dec	342	6	livetime	<	10%			
2012	23.Jan	23	9	27.Jan	27	21	livetime	<	10%			

4.2 Summary of the ACE/SIS data

SEP Server provides

1. ACE/SIS omnidirectional fluxes and counts of heavy ions
2. A comprehensive description of the data set
3. A dataset that allows the user to study in detail the compositional differences in the standard two classes of SEP events, as this has been noted already from [RD1]

SEP Server

Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report

STEREO/SEPT Instrument description and data quality

	Name	Signature	Date
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	1.	0		Consolidation of team inputs
10.09.2013	1.	1.	many	SEPT Caveats inserted
10.10.2013	1.	2.	many	Comments from the PI inserted

Summary and Recommendation

This document contains the Solar Electron Proton Telescope (SEPT) Instrument Document and Data Quality Report for the SEPServer database server. Herein the following three sections are included:

1. Description the of the instrumentation
2. Caveats of the instruments
3. Quality assessment of the data set delivered to SEPServer

The STEREO/SEPT instrument has been designed to measure electrons and ions from a few tens of keV to several hundreds of keV for electrons and to several MeV for ions. Four identical telescopes are mounted on the spacecraft viewing in different directions, and thus allowing information about the pitch angle distribution as long as the local interplanetary field is known. The instrument relies on the magnet-foil measurement principle. Thus, the energy loss in a solid-state detector is digitized and stored in a histogram that is available every minute for scientific usages.

The SEPServer quality assessment study presented here showed that due to their lower efficiency bins 02 and 03 (below 65 keV) of the electron histogram should be handled with care and are not recommended for scientific studies. Conditions for misidentifications are also presented here. Probable effects have been identified:

1. There is no correction available for misidentification of protons in the electron channels and therefore, electron data during periods of high proton intensities at energies above 400 keV should not be used for scientific analysis.
2. There is also no correction available for misidentification of electrons in the proton channels and therefore the onset analysis in the proton channel requires a careful cross checking with the electron intensity time profiles using channels as described in this document.

3. Contaminations of X-rays to the intensity time profiles occur occasionally too. But they can be clearly identified by an experienced user or can be requested from the PI of the instrument.

In the course of the mission some periods of unexpected behaviour of the instrument have been observed. They had their cause in an electronic interference in the energy spectrum during high proton fluxes. Within the SEPServer project a careful re-analysis was performed and presented here indicating that a data analysis of the SEPT channels can be spoiled by high intensities of several MeV protons as measured by the LET instrument. Therefore the user is advised to omit such time periods from the scientific analysis.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document contains the **Data Delivery Report** for the Solar TErrestrial RElations Observatory (STEREO) Solar Electron Proton Telescope (SEPT) for the SEPServer database server.

The document roughly breaks down into the following components:

- (a) Description of the STEREO/SEPT instrumentation
- (b) Caveats of instrument
- (c) Quality assessment for the data set delivered to SEPServer.

Each class of requirements will be detailed in a section of the document.

1.2 Applicable documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
AD1	Description of Work	EC-GA #262773, Annex I	10.10.2010
AD2	Data Delivery Plan	SEPSERVER-009-CAU-WP2	

1.3 Reference documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
Luhmann et al (2008)	'STEREO IMPACT Investigation Goals, Measurements, and Data Products Overview'	Luhmann, J. G.; et al.: Space Science Reviews, Volume 136, Issue 1-4, pp. 117-184, 2008	
Müller-Mellin et al. (2008)	The Solar Electron and Proton Telescope for the STEREO Mission.	R. Müller-Mellin, et al.: Spac. Sci. Rev., 136:363- 389, Apr. 2008.	
Gómez-Herrero et al. (2011)	Spatial and temporal variations of CIRs: Multi-point observations by STEREO.	R. Gómez-Herrero, et al.: Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics, 73:551-565, Mar. 2011.	
RD3	SEPServer Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report: Spacecraft descriptions and data comparison	SEPSERVER-010-00-CAU- WP2-Issue1-Revision1	1.

1.4 Abbreviations and acronyms

3DP	3-D Plasma
ACE	Advanced Composition Explorer
DDP	Data Delivery Plan
DDR	Data Delivery Report
EPAM	Electron, Proton, and Alpha Monitor
EUVI	Extreme UltraViolet Imager
LET	Low energy Telescope
IMPACT	In-situ Measurements of Particles and CME Transients
PDFE	Particle Detector Front End
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SEPT	Solar Electron Proton Telescope
STEREO	Solar TERrestrial RELations Observatory
SSD	Solid-State Detector

2 STEREO/SEPT

The STEREO/SEPT instrument has been described in detail Müller-Mellin et al. (2008) and Gómez-Herrero et al. (2011). It was designed to measure electrons and ions from a few tens of keV to several hundreds of keV for electrons and to several MeV for ions. Four identical telescopes are mounted on the spacecraft viewing in different direction and thus allow some information about the pitch angle distribution albeit the local interplanetary field is known.

2.1 Scientific goal

The Solar Electron and Proton Telescope (SEPT) is one of four instruments of the Solar Energetic Particle (SEP) suite for the In-situ Measurements of Particles and CME Transients (IMPACT) investigation on board the STEREO mission, launched in October 2006 (Luhmann et al., 2008). It is designed to measure electrons in the energy range from 30–400 keV and ions from 60–7 000 keV and has been described in detail by Müller-Mellin et al. (2008).

2.2 Instrument description and principle of measurements important to SEPServer

In order to separate electrons from ions each sensor consists of a double-ended telescope with one end measuring electrons and the other ions, as displayed in Figure 1. Each double-ended telescope has two solid-state detectors (SSDs) that are operated in anti-coincidence. One SSD looks through an absorption foil and its partner through the air gap of a magnet system. The foil leaves the electron spectrum essentially unchanged but stops protons of energy up to the energy of electrons (~ 400 keV), which penetrate the SSD. The magnet is designed to sweep away electrons below 400 keV, but leaves ions unaffected. In the absence of > 400 keV ions, the foil SSD only detects electrons, and in the absence of >400 keV electrons, the magnet SSD only detects ions. Ions from 400 keV to 7 MeV will stop in the magnet SSD and their fluxes will be cleanly measured. The contribution of >

400 keV ions to the foil SSD can then be computed and subtracted to obtain the electron fluxes. The SEPT sensor schematic is shown in Figure 1. Some SEPT sensor characteristics are given in Table 1.

Table 1 SEPT Sensor Characteristics¹

Channel	Species	Geometric al Factor	View Cone	Boresight	Accum. time
D1 D2 G1 G2	electrons 30 – 480 keV	0.13 cm ² sr	52.8°	ecliptic 315°	60 s
D2 D4 G4 G2	protons 70 – 6500 keV	0.17 cm ² sr	52.0°	ecliptic 135°	60 s
D3 D4 G3 G4	protons 70 – 6500 keV	0.17 cm ² sr	52.0°	ecliptic 315°	60 s
D4 D3 G3 G4	electrons 30 – 480 keV	0.13 cm ² sr	52.8°	ecliptic 135°	60 s
D5 D6 G5 G6	electrons 30 – 480 keV	0.13 cm ² sr	52.8°	north	60 s
D6 D5 G5 G6	protons 70 – 6500 keV	0.17 cm ² sr	52.0°	south	60 s
D7 D8 G7 G8	protons 70 – 6500 keV	0.17 cm ² sr	52.0°	north	60 s
D8 D7 G7 G8	electrons 30 – 480 keV	0.13 cm ² sr	52.8°	south	60 s

¹ Note: The STEREO A Sunward telescope has been corrected for efficiency changes. Thus data before 20.01.2007 are difficult to interpret and should thus not be used for scientific use.

Figure 1. SEPT sensor schematics. Detection elements are silicon detectors (D0, . . . ,D3, green) with guard rings (G0, . . . ,G3), Parylene foils (red), and magnetic fields perpendicular to the drawing plane (magenta)

Anisotropy information is acquired in four look directions: SEPT-E observes in the ecliptic plane along the nominal Parker spiral magnetic field direction both forward and backward, SEPT-N/S observes out of the ecliptic plane perpendicular to the magnetic field both North and South. Thus, SEPT partially complements the viewing directions for ions of the Low Energy Telescope (LET, see Mewaldt et al., 2006) the multiple look directions of which are all in the ecliptic. To ensure unobstructed fields of view, the full angle of the viewing cones is limited to 52 degrees and SEPT-N/S is mounted on its own bracket. The geometrical factor for each of the four magnet telescopes is $0.17 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sr}$ and for each of the four foil telescopes $0.13 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sr}$.

3 Technical Data and Specific Features

3.1 Spacecraft pointing

The spacecraft orientation is most of the time close to the nominal situation, with sun, anti-sun, north and south SEPT apertures pointing as described in section 2.2, however this pointing can vary depending on spacecraft maneuvers. STEREO attitude and orbit data are available at the SEP suite website: <http://www.srl.caltech.edu/STEREO/attorb.html>.

3.2 Data gaps and bad data periods due to instrument reconfiguration or commanding

Bad or missing data intervals are filled with -9999.9 (float) or -9999 (integer). During the first years of the mission, some discriminator threshold changes were applied in order to reduce the noise in the low energy bins. For this reason, early data files can contain negative numbers (marking invalid data) affecting only the low energy bins of certain telescopes. For a more detailed description of the threshold changes and other commanding operations affecting SEPT sensors, see the level 1 data caveat file: http://stereo.ssl.berkeley.edu/SEPT_Caveat.pdf. Due to their lower efficiency, bins 02 and 03 should be handled with care and are not recommended for quantitative studies.

3.3 Ion contamination of the electron channels

SEPT electron telescopes are covered by a thin foil which leaves the electron spectrum essentially unchanged but stops protons of energy up to ~ 400 keV. Ions with energies above this limit can pass the foil and stop inside the top silicon detector. They are registered as electrons. For this reason, SEPT electron measurements are subject to proton (ion) contamination during periods where there is a significant enhancement of the ion fluxes above 400 keV. This can happen e.g. during some interplanetary shock transits, as shown in Figure 2. The easiest way to identify periods dominated by ion contamination is the comparison of the electron time profiles with the ion rates corresponding to energies above 400 keV (bin number >15 , see Table 2 and Table 3): a close one-to-one correlation

of the fluctuations shown by both measurements during ion-enhanced periods is normally an indication of strong contamination of the electron measurement. At present, there is no correction available for this effect and electron data during these periods should not be used for scientific analysis.

Table 2 SEPT ion energy bins included in SEPServer data

Bin number	Emin (keV)	Emax (keV)
02	84.1	92.7
03	92.7	101.3
04	101.3	110.0
05	110.0	118.6
06	118.6	137.0
07	137.0	155.8
08	155.8	174.6
09	174.6	192.6
10	192.6	219.5
11	219.5	246.4
12	246.4	273.4
13	273.4	312.0
14	312.0	350.7
15	350.7	389.5
16	389.5	438.1
17	438.1	496.4
18	496.4	554.8
19	554.8	622.9
20	622.9	700.7
21	700.7	788.3
22	788.3	875.8
23	875.8	982.8

24	982.8	1111.9
25	1111.9	1250.8
26	1250.8	1399.7
27	1399.7	1578.4
28	1578.4	1767.0
29	1767.0	1985.3
30	1985.3	2223.6
31	2223.6	6500.

Table 3 SEPT electron energy bins included in SEPServer data

Bin number	Emin (keV)	Emax (keV)
02	45	55
03	55	65
04	65	75
05	75	85
06	85	105
07	105	125
08	125	145
09	145	165
10	165	195
11	195	225
12	225	255
13	255	295
14	295	335
15	335	375
16	375	425

Figure 2 Example of 75-85 keV electron (red line) and 435-496 keV ion (orange line) measurements by SEPT-sunward pointing telescopes onboard STEREO-A during a Solar Energetic Particle (SEP) event in August 2010. The early data show clean electron measurements, while the late data (starting on August 19) are dominated by ion contamination due to the high ion flux, which reach maximum values before an interplanetary shock transit on August 20 at 16:13 UT.

3.4 Electron/high-energy-particle contamination of the ion channels

SEPT ion telescope apertures are surrounded by permanent magnets that sweep away low energy electrons. High-energy electrons can cross the magnet without being completely deflected and produce signal in the front silicon detector. In most cases, these

electrons are energetic enough to completely cross the detector, producing also signal in the second detector, being rejected by the anticoincidence system. However, a small number of such electrons can be scattered out of the sensor without triggering the anticoincidence, and mimicking an ion signal. High-energy particles crossing the housing and entering (or escaping) at high angles through the small gap between the silicon detectors can produce similar effect. Most of the time this kind of contamination remains at undetectable levels. However, if the electron flux is enhanced by several orders of magnitude during a period with no ion enhancement (e.g. during the onset of very large SEP events) it can produce a significant effect as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Top panel: example of ion and electron measurements during a SEP event on April 2013. Ion measurements during the early phase of the event, in coincidence with an electron increase over four orders of magnitude, are affected by electron contamination (marked by an arrow). The actual ion increase corresponding to this event is observed later, and shows velocity dispersion. The contamination is better recognized in the

dynamic spectrum shown in the bottom panel.

3.5 Transient disturbances in the low energy ion bins

Ions above 2.2 MeV produce large pulses, which are counted in the last energy bin of SEPT. A pulse-height overflow can cause extra-trigger of lower energy bins because the analog electronics is not reset fast enough. Due to this limitation in the electronics, SEPT low energy measurements can be occasionally disturbed when large pulses become dominant. This effect is easy to recognize as narrow horizontal “strips” in the low energy part of the ion dynamic spectrum (<350 keV). All SEPT telescopes are affected by this issue, however the effect is only important during periods showing a flat energy spectrum (reduced rate at low energies) accompanied by an ion increase above 2.2 MeV, for instance during the early phase of a SEP event showing velocity dispersion and a significant ion rate above 2.2 MeV. An example of period strongly affected by this effect is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Example of a period with disturbed low-energy ion measurements. The top panel shows the spectrogram and the bottom panel the energy spectrum during March 8, 2011. Note the increase in the last energy bin (white arrow) accompanied by a pattern of narrow strips in certain low energy bins (black arrows).

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X-ray contamination

SEPT is mostly insensitive to X-rays. Very large X-ray flares like the X6.9 flare observed on August 9, 2011, were not able to produce any measurable increase in the SEPT counting rates. However, under certain circumstances, X-ray contamination could produce a significant signal in the low energy channels for some SEPT telescopes. From January 2007 to June 2013, SEPT sensors have only observed one clear case of such X-ray contamination. This only example, observed by STEREO-B on September 20, 2012 is presented in Figure 4. Due to the backside location of the active region (as seen from the Earth), there are no X-ray intensity measurements available from GOES.

Figure 5 Right: Transient increase in the counting-rates measured by the low energy channels of the SEPT instruments onboard STEREO-B during a solar flare on September 20, 2012 (note the linear Y-scale). Left:

sequence of three STEREO/B EUVI images around the flare peak emission in extreme ultraviolet wavelengths.

3.6 Electronic interferences in the energy spectrum during high proton fluxes

Figure 6 From top to bottom the Intensity time profiles during the March 7, 2011 event of about 115 keV, 250 keV and a few MeV ions, the colored proton spectrogram and four different energy spectra are displayed. For the discussion see text.

Figure 6 displays from top to bottom the ion intensities of 115 keV, 250 keV and a few MeV, an energy spectrogram and four ion energy spectra for selected periods during the energetic particle event on March 7 in 2011. From upper panel of the figure it is evident that the two ion energy channels in the hecto-keV range follow the high-energy channel from the end of day of year 67, 2011, for the whole day. Since such a behavior is rather suspicious we show in the middle panel a spectrogram plot of the ion intensities. During the period of interest the energy spectrum becomes flat with a peak at about 200 keV. The energy spectra before and after that period show in contrast a power law like feature that is expected from the usual conditions and several particle acceleration theories.

Therefore a test procedure was set up in order to investigate the response of the electronic box to high frequency of test pulses with signals corresponding to ions with energy losses of 8 to 10 MeV with a frequency $f = 144$ Hz clustered in a time of $t = 10$ s. The result of the test can be summarized as follows:

- ✓ The total number of pulses are twice as high than expected for a small energy range depending on the individual Particle Detector Front End (PDFE).
- ✓ The energy spectrum shows counts in lower bins although all counts are expected in the highest energy bin.
- ✓ The spectral cut off at the lower boundary depends on the individual PDFE and the particle energy in a way that the cut off increases with increasing primary energies.
- ✓ The spectrum only shows these characteristics when the total number of counts is twice as high as expected.
- ✓ The investigation of the dependence with the threshold energy results in the same spectrum characteristics but with the cut off energy decreases with higher thresholds.

The results of the tests clearly demonstrates that the observed intensity time profiles under such conditions (high flux of particles that loose more than 8 MeV in the SSD) can be interpreted in terms of non-functioning electronics. A correction procedure needs to be

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developed that describes the effect in more detail. Since the PDFE has been developed by a company and therefore further details are not available to us such a procedure is beyond the resources in SEPServer,

4 Data Delivery and Quality Assessment

Measurements from the SEPT are shown in Figure 7, during an upstream event close to Earth. Such events are caused by particles originated from the Earth magnetosphere or accelerated by the Earth bow shock and stream away from the Earth. The figure clearly illustrates the instruments capabilities and sensitivity.

Figure 7 Measurements by STEREO SEPT during a series of upstream events. Shown here are only the results from the instrument pointing away from the Sun and towards the Earth. While the first event is not accompanied by an electron increase the other two are. Thus the figure shows that SEPT can separate electrons from protons very well.

Major effects influencing the data quality have been investigated in the course of the SEP Server project and reported in chapter 3. They are:

- ✓ Ion contamination of the electron channels

- ✓ Electron/high energy particles contamination of the ion channels
- ✓ Transient disturbances in the low energy ion bins
- ✓ X-ray contamination
- ✓ Electronic interferences in the energy spectrum during high proton fluxes

The users need to take account of these effects, as described in the corresponding paragraphs above. However, the detailed comparative quality assesment in RD3 demonstrates the overall high quality of the SEPT, ACE/EPAM and WIND 3DP instrumentation.

SEPServer

Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report STEREO/LET Instrument description and data quality

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CHANGE LOG

Date	Issue	Rev.	Pages	Reason for change
21.11.2012	0.1			First draft
22.01.2013	1.	0		Consolidation of team inputs
11.05.2013	1.	1	Several pages	Included caveats
20.05.2013	1	2	Several pages	Several changes as a result of the checking by EV
02.10.2013	1	3	Several pages	Several changes as a result of the checking by RV

Summary

This document contains the Solar Energetic Particle Instrument Document and Data Quality Report for the SEPServer database server. Herein the following three sections are included:

1. Description the STEREO/LET instrumentation
2. Data sets delivered
3. Caveats and quality assessment.

In Section 2 a detailed description on the STEREO/LET instrumentation is provided. It includes details on LET sensor system, the dynamic threshold during SEP events, together with the directional capabilities (anisotropy measurements) provided by the instrument given its orientation onboard STA and STB. Furthermore, estimations of the yield of energetic ions recorded by Let during intense SEP events are also provided. Section 3 refers to the datasets delivered to SEPServer in terms of the format of the files and contents that currently are available through the SEPServer database. Section 4 summarises the known caveats spotted at the LET data.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document contains the Solar Energetic Particle Data Delivery Report (DDR) of the Low Energy Telescope (LET) of the STEREO mission for the SEPServer database server.

The DDR's roughly break down into the following components:

1. Description the STEREO/LET instrumentation
2. Data sets delivered
3. Caveats and quality assessment.

Each topic will be discussed in detail in a section of the document.

1.2 Applicable documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
AD1	Description of Work	EC-GA #262773, Annex I	10 Dec 2010
AD2	Data Delivery Plan	SEPSERVER-009-CAU-WP2	02 Oct 2012

1.3 Reference documents

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue
RD1	The Low-Energy Telescope (LET) and SEP Central Electronics for the STEREO Mission	Mewaldt, et al. Space Sci. Rev. 136, 285,2008	
RD2	STEREO IMPACT Investigation Goals, Measurements, and Data Products Overview	Luhmann, et al. Space Sci. Rev. 136, 117,2008	
RD3	STEREO Space Weather website	http://stereo.gsfc.nasa.gov/spaceweather/spaceweathe	

		r.shtml	
RD4	Evidence fo Remnant Flare Suprathermals in the Source Population of Solar Energetic Particles in the 2000 Bastille Day Event	Tylka et al., Astrophys. J. 558, L59 ,2001	
RD5	STEREO LET Public website	http://www.srl.caltech.edu/STEREO/Level1/LET_public.html	

1.4 Abbreviations and acronyms

CIRs	Corotating Interaction Regions
CMEs	Coronal Mass Ejections
DDP	Data Delivery Plan
DDR	Data Delivery Report
ESPs	Energetic Storm Particles
EPAM	Electron, Proton, and Alpha Monitor
FOV	Field of View
HET	High Energy Telescope
IMPACT	In situ Measurements of Particles And CME Transients
IPM	Interplanetary Medium
LET	Low Energy Telescope
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
PHA	Pulse Height Analyzed
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SEPT	Solar Electron Proton Telescope
SEPServer	Data Services and Analysis Tools for Solar Energetic Particle Events and Related Electromagnetic Emissions
SIT	Suprathermal Ion Telescope
STA	STEREO A
STB	STEREO B

SEP DDR (STEREO/LET)

STEREO Solar TERrestrial RELations Observatory
STIM The event is an internally generated calibration or livetime pulse

2 STEREO/LET description

The Low Energy Telescope (LET) on board the Solar Terrestrial Relations Observatory (STEREO) is designed to measure the elemental composition, energy spectra, angular distributions, and arrival times of H to Ni ions over the energy range from ~ 3 to ~ 30 MeV/nucleon. It will also identify the rare isotope ^3He (see **Figure 1**) and trans-iron nuclei with $30 \leq Z \leq 83$. LET onboard STEREO spacecraft has been described in [RD1] and some of its goals in [RD2]. In what follows some parts are repeated in order to better understand the limitation and quality of the data.

There are two identical LET instruments: Flight Model 1 (FM1) is flying on the STEREO Ahead spacecraft, and FM2 is on the Behind spacecraft. **Table 1** summarizes key characteristics of the LET instrument.

The primary measurement goal of LET is to measure the composition, energy spectra, and time variations of solar energetic particles ranging from H to Ni. The energy range for oxygen extends from ~ 3 to 30 MeV/nucleon (see **Figure 1**). In this range the intensities can vary by a factor of $\sim 10^6$ [RD1].

All SEP related telescopes of STEREO (e.g. SEPT, SIT, LET and HET) are being controlled by an additional unit, called SEP Central. This unit collects and transmits data from the four SEP sensors and controls the SEP bias supply, manages the interfaces to the sensors as well as the SEP interface to the instrument data processing unit. A photo of LET, HET, and SEP Central is shown in **Figure 2**.

Figure 1 Composition measurements with IMPACT/SEP onboard STEREO spacecraft. LET is denoted by blue (upper panel). The lower panel shows the LET species and energy bins identified in onboard processing [taken from RD1]

Figure 2 Photo of the LET and HET and the SEP Central housing. LET is mounted on a post so as to clear the FOV. HET is mounted on top of the SEP Central housing, with its electronics mounted inside [taken from RD1]

It is noteworthy that the four SEP instruments complement each other in addressing the scientific objectives by providing comprehensive measurements of the composition and energy spectra of energetic nuclei from H to Ni ($1 \leq Z \leq 28$) spanning the energy range from ~ 0.03 to >100 MeV/nucleon, as well as electrons from 0.03 to 6 MeV (see **Figure 1**). In addition, the SIT and LET instruments will be sensitive to trans-iron nuclei with $30 \leq Z \leq 83$, and SEPT and LET will provide information on the pitch-angle distributions of SEP events.

Table 1 Summary of LET characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Measurement objective	Composition, energy spectra, time variations of solar and interplanetary energetic particles
Measurement technique	Multiple- ΔE vs. residual energy, with corrections for trajectory
Onboard particle identification	Sixteen species from H to Fe identified within an average of 12 energy intervals
Energy interval	
H, He	1.8–15 MeV/nucleon
O	3.4–33 MeV/nucleon
Si	4.0–45 MeV/nucleon
Fe	3.8–59 MeV/nucleon
Field of view	Two 133° by 29° fans
Geometry factor¹	4.0 cm ² sr
Event yields (large SEPs)²	$>10^6$ H&He; $>10^5$ C–Si; $>10^4$ S–Fe

Most of the goals and objectives for LET instrument involve compositional and origin studies of the various particle populations that are found in the near IPM. That is to identify SEP acceleration from multi-point observations [RD2] and to facilitate the need for Space Weather services [RD3]. In particular, these goals are to explore [RD1]:

- SEP Acceleration by CME-Driven Shocks
 - Comparison of SEP and CME Kinetic Energies
- Impulsive Solar Energetic Particle Events

¹ For details see Section 2.4

² For details see Section 2.5

- Space Weather
 - Characterizing the 1-AU Radiation Environment
 - An Interplanetary SEP Network
- Acceleration by CIRs and ESP Events
 - CIRs
 - ESPs
- Anomalous Cosmic Rays

2.1 The low energy telescope (LET) sensor system

The sensor system is illustrated in cutaway views on Error! Reference source not found. and in cross-section in **Figure 4**. The active elements are all silicon solid-state detectors and include three different detector designs, designated L1, L2, and L3. **Table 2** lists the nominal characteristics of each of these detector designs. The geometry used for segmenting the detectors into multiple active elements is illustrated in **Figure 4**.

The instrument has 10 entrance apertures, each occupied by an L1 detector. Five of these are arranged along an arc of a circle that in flight lies in the ecliptic plane and is centered along the direction of the nominal Parker spiral magnetic field, generally toward the Sun. The other five are located 180° from these, centered on the same direction but facing generally away from the Sun. The central area of the instrument contains four additional detectors including two L2 and two L3 devices. Each detector is segmented into multiple active areas, as indicated in **Table 2**. This provides some position sensitivity, which is used for determining particle trajectories, as well as for reducing noise and improving instrument performance when exposed to high intensities of incident particles.

Table 2 LET detector design characteristics

Detector designation	Number in LET instrument	Thickness (μm)	Active area (cm^2)	Active segments per detector
L1	10	24	2.0	3
L2	2	50	10.2	10
L3	2	1000	15.6	2

2.2 Dynamic thresholds during SEP events

During large SEP events the single-detector count rates can increase by a factor of as much as 10^4 due mostly to low-energy protons. These elevated single-detector count rates create instrument deadtime and also lead to chance coincidence events involving two separate particles. In order to minimize these effects the LET design includes *dynamic thresholds* in which the trigger thresholds on selected PHAs are increased during periods when the count rates are high. This action reduces the count rates of selected detectors, minimizing deadtime and effectively reducing the geometry factor for H and He events with minimal effect on the geometry factor for heavy ions with $Z \geq 6$.

The dynamic thresholds are implemented in a three-stage process, as illustrated in **Figure 5**: in the first stage, the high-gain ADCs on all 20 of the L1 outer segments are disabled. The effective threshold for triggering these devices is thereby raised from ~ 0.25 MeV to the low-gain thresholds, nominally set at 5 MeV (see **Table 3**). The result is that neither H nor He ions can trigger these higher thresholds except for particles incident at very wide angles (**Figure 6**). As a result, the geometry factor for H and He is reduced by a factor of 5.

Figure 3 Two cut-away views of the LET sensor system illustrate the locations of the detectors, entrance foils, and collimators, as well as structural components [taken by RD1]

Figure 4 Panel (a) shows a cross-sectional view of the LET detector system together with the limits of the field of view. Panel (b) illustrates the sizes and segmentation of the LET detectors [taken by RD1]

Table 3 Nominal low- and high-gain thresholds and full-scale energies

Detector	Nominal high-gain threshold (MeV)	Nominal low-gain threshold (MeV)	Nominal low-gain full scale (MeV)
L1	0.174 (L1 centers) 0.205 (L1 edges)	5.4	920
L2	0.29	7	1,534
L3	1.3	18	3,989

In the second stage the high-gain ADCs are disabled on all but the center L1 centers (L1A2 and L1B2), providing a decrease in the effective geometry factor for H and He by a second factor of ~ 5 . At this point LET has reduced angular coverage for H and He ($\sim 90^\circ$ coverage instead of $\sim 130^\circ$), but the angular coverage for $Z \geq 6$ ions is not affected (except at the lowest and highest energies, where the L1 and L2 thresholds have some minor effects).

In the third stage the high-gain thresholds are disabled on all but the center two L2 segments on both the A and B sides (L2A4, L2A5, L2B4, L2B5 remain enabled), as well as the outside L3A and L3B segments. The nominal L2 and L3 low-gain thresholds are ~ 7 MeV and ~ 18 MeV, respectively, in order to be above the maximum energy loss of all but very wide-angle protons. This effectively reduces the geometry factor for H and He by an additional factor of ~ 4.5 . The monitor count rate for this process is the sum of all singles rates that are not affected by these changes (the centers of L1A2 and L1B2; L2A4, L2A5, L2B4, and L2B5; and the centers of L3A and L3B). These monitor-rate trigger levels may be changed by command.

Figure 5 Illustration of the effect of dynamic thresholds on the count rates and event readout from LET during a solar event with the composition and spectra of the July 14, 2000 (Bastille Day), SEP event. As the thresholds of various detector segments are gradually raised in response to the Monitor rate, the measured singles rate (labeled “scaled Singles”) and the H and He event rates are reduced, thereby preserving instrument livetime to record a greater sample of $Z \geq 6$ events) [taken from RD1]

Figure 6 Illustration of the effect of dynamic thresholds on the count rates and event readout from LET during a solar event with the composition and spectra of the July 14, 2000 (Bastille Day), SEP event. As the thresholds of various detector segments are gradually raised in response to the Monitor rate, the measured singles rate (labeled “scaled Singles”) and the H and He event rates are reduced, thereby preserving instrument livetime to record a greater sample of $Z \geq 6$ events) [taken from RD1]

2.3 Orientation of LET at STA & STB

The Ahead and Behind spacecraft designs are identical. However, the orientation of the IMF at 1 AU affects the location of LET and other SEP sensors. The SEP FOV are oriented at 45° to the spacecraft–Sun line so as to look along the nominal Parker spiral direction at 1 AU. The Behind spacecraft is predominantly a copy of the Ahead spacecraft rolled 180° about the spacecraft–Sun line. This points each dish antenna towards the Earth and doesn't disturb the Sun-pointing instruments, but it does mean that the SEP instruments need to be repointed to view along the nominal Parker spiral direction. In order to clear the fields of view with different pointing directions, it was necessary to have different locations for some of the telescopes, including HET and LET, on the two spacecraft. The result is illustrated in **Figure 7**.

Figure 7 The IMPACT SEP suite on the body of the Ahead (left) and Behind (right) spacecraft, including SEPT, SIT, LET, and HET. Note that the Behind spacecraft is shown upside down to indicate the placement of the SEP sensors (which are mounted on the panel facing the south ecliptic pole) [taken by RD1]

2.4 Anisotropy Measurements

STEREO is a three-axis stabilized spacecraft, which always looks at the Sun. As a result, there is no information on the arrival directions of particles except for what is provided by the sensors themselves. As discussed in RD1, the various combinations of L1 and L2 segments define a total of 300 different directions in the ecliptic plane (150 per side). These directions have been sorted into 16 sectors, 8 of which are illustrated in **Figure 8**. For sectorized count rates both the front (A-side) and rear (B-side) include particles from a $129^\circ \times 29^\circ$ FOV with the 129° fan looking along the ecliptic plane. The center of the A-side fan points at an angle that is 45° west of the Sun, along the average Parker Spiral direction at 1 AU. There are ten 16-sector rates that are read out once per minute (see **Table 4**). All of these count the particles identified by the onboard particle identification system.

Figure 8 The LET viewing directions are divided into eight sectors on the A-side and eight on the B-side. Shown here is the fraction of the geometry factor in each sector on the A-side. In this representation particles coming in a straight line from the Sun would arrive at 0° and those arriving along the average Parker Spiral angle would arrive at $\sim 45^\circ$. Note that the central six sectors are 12.5° wide and the width of the two outside sectors is 25° [taken by RD1]

Table 4 LET sectored rates

Species	Energy range	No of sectors	Geometry factor (cm ² sr)
H	4.0-6.0	16	0.039-4.0
3He	4.0-6.0	16	0.039-4.0
4He	4.0-6.0	16	0.039-4.0
	6.0-12.0	16	0.039-4.0
CNO	4.0-6.0	16	4.0
	6.0-12.0	16	4.0
NeMgSi	4.0-6.0	16	4.0
	6.0-12.0	16	4.0
Fe	4.0-6.0	16	4.0
	6.0-12.0	16	4.0

2.5 SEP Yields

In order to estimate the yield of energetic ions that would be obtained in a very large SEP event an analysis was done of the performance of LET during the July 14, 2000 (Bastille Day), event when the intensity reached its maximum (10:00–18:00 UT on July 15). Using composite spectra compiled by [RD4], the count rates of H, He, O, and Fe ions incident on the LET telescope were estimated. In addition, the singles rates of all detectors were estimated, including particles that enter through the sides of the telescope. The estimated total singles rate (summed over all detectors) is $\sim 1.6 \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$, leading to a livetime of 38% during this interval. The rate at which proton events would be analyzed [taking into account the dynamic thresholds (**Sect. 2.2**) and livetime] was estimated to be $\sim 1,200 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and the analysis rate of $Z \geq 6$ heavy ions was estimated at 14 s^{-1} . **Figure 9** shows the total number of events that would be expected during this 8-hr period (only those elements for which there is onboard analysis are tabulated). Note that the event numbers are adequate to construct energy spectra for all species.

Figure 9 Estimated yield of particle events that a LET would have measured during the eight hours when the counting rate from the Bastille Day SEP event was at its maximum. The effects of the dynamic thresholds and the instrument deadtime have been taken into account. Only those species identified by the onboard analysis system are shown [taken by RD1]

3 Data Delivery

3.1 Format of the STEREO/LET delivered data

The STEREO/LET data that have been delivered to SEPServer include omnidirectional summed intensities and counts data of H and He. Three energy bins, i.e.: 1.8-3.6 MeV, 4-6 MeV and 6-10 MeV have been delivered for hydrogen, and three energy bins, i.e. 4-6 MeV, 6-10 MeV and 10-15 MeV for helium. Omnidirectional data of heavier ions, e.g. Al, Ar, C, Ca, Fe, Mg, N, Na, Ne, Ni, O, S and Si, have also been delivered. For all the aforementioned species, both intensities and counts have been provided to SEPServer. STEREO/LET has 16 look directions or sectors, 8 per side. Both the front (A-side) and rear (B-side) include particles from a 129° x 29° FoV with the 129° fan looking along the ecliptic plane. Therefore, there are 16 sectorized intensities and 16 sectorized count rates of CNO (4-6MeV, 6-12MeV), Fe (4-6MeV, 6-12MeV), H (1.8-3.6 MeV, 4-6MeV), He3 (4-6MeV), He4 (4-6MeV, 6-12MeV), He (4-6MeV), NeMgSi (4-6MeV, 6-12MeV), which have been delivered to SEPServer. All data have been provided in ASCII files. The file format of the

STEREO/LET data delivered to SEP Server has been described in details the Data Delivery Plan (DDP) [AD2].

4 Data Caveats

Known malfunction and caveats of the LET have been reported since almost the beginning of the STEREO mission [RD5]. In what follows a summary of the known limitations and caveats of the LET data is presented (**Section 4.1**).

4.1 Summary of Limitation and Caveats of the LET data

Known limitations/caveats:

1. After March 29, 2007, (at slightly different times on each spacecraft) events identified as ^3He onboard are treated like ^4He for energy-binning (a mass-number equal to 4 is used). This allows the ^3He and ^4He boxes to be combined on the ground to obtain elemental helium (He) intensities. For data prior to the March 29, 2007 the He data are *FILL* (-9999.9). For data after the March 29, 2007, the ^3He data are also *FILL*.
2. The following species/energy-bin channels are also flagged as bad:
 - i. Protons prior to the March 29, 2007
 - ii. Protons below 4 MeV after the March 29, 2007
 - iii. All ^3He , for all time periods.
 - iv. All ^4He prior to the March 29, 2007
 - v. Fe below 5 MeV prior to the March 29, 2007
 - vi. Fe below 4 MeV after the March 29, 2007
 - vii. One or two energy-bins at the low and/or high ends for many species.
3. Unexpected changes in the LET instrument response when the instrument is in its *dynamic thresholds* (see **Section 2.2**) mode during high rate periods. During such periods, calibration shifts have been found that cause some counts for some elements to be mislabeled as the neighboring elements. At present, only ~4-10 MeV/nuc C, N, O, and Ne on the Behind spacecraft have been affected, and only during two time intervals: during the SEP events of 2-3 August 2010 (day of year 214 and 215). Rates for these elements are inaccurate by perhaps as much as a

factor of 2 from approximately 06:41 through 14:44 UT on day 214 and again from 04:29 through 09:07 UT on day 215 of 2010. As a result, a subset of the energy-bands for C, N, O, Ne, Na, Mg, AL, and Si, during high-rate periods (approximately when 1.8-3.6 MeV proton intensities exceeded ~ 150 counts/(cm² sr s MeV)) has been replaced with *FILL* data.

4. The LET instruments on Ahead and Behind have been patched to correct the instrument response when the instrument is in its *dynamic thresholds* mode during high rate periods. LET Behind was patched on October 11, 2011. LET Ahead was patched on October 14, 2011. After these dates, the energy-bands for *heavies* that were invalid during high-rate periods are now usable.
5. The geometry factors used to calculate intensities are under review. A new version of the LET data will be released at some point in the future, using new geometry factors. The resulting changes from the current version will be on the order of 5%, or less. We will make our best effort to reingest the data to SEPServer once it becomes available.
6. The total-energy calculation for particles that penetrate the instrument was found to be implemented incorrectly. The LET instruments on Ahead and Behind have been patched to correct the error. LET Ahead was patched on April 16, 2012. LET Behind was patched on April 18, 2012. Prior to these dates, the following species-energy bands are invalid.
 - i. H: 12 - 15 *
 - ii. ⁴He: 12 - 15
 - iii. C: 21 - 27 *
 - iv. C: 27 - 33 *
 - v. N: 21 - 27
 - vi. N: 27 - 33 *
 - vii. O: 27 - 33 *
 - viii. Ne: 27 - 33 *
 - ix. Ne: 33 - 40 *
 - x. Mg: 33 - 40 *
 - xi. Mg: 40 - 52 *

- xii. Si: 33 - 40
- xiii. Si: 40 - 52 *
- xiv. Fe: 40 - 52
- xv. Fe: 52 - 70 *

Note: the species-energy bands marked with "*" above were already suppressed in the data, for other reasons. So, this issue actually affects only 4 bands.

7. The 15-21 MeV/nuc Carbon bin is not valid during high-rate periods. It is therefore set to "Fill data" for these periods. The instrument thresholds are higher during these periods, and particles in this species-energy bin fall below the raised thresholds in some cases.
8. The species represented in the LET sector rates have changed on November 22, 2010.

- After Nov 22, 2010, the 16 sector rates, per species are assigned as follows:

- i. 0 - 15: H 4-6 MeV/nuc
- ii. 15 - 31: H 1.8-3.6
- iii. 32 - 47: 4He 4-6
- iv. 48 - 63: 4He 6-12
- v. 64 - 79: CNO 4-6
- vi. 80 - 95: CNO 6-12
- vii. 96 - 111: NeMgSi 4-6
- viii. 112 - 127: NeMgSi 6-12
- ix. 128 - 143: Fe 4-12
- x. 144 - 159: H 6-10

- Prior to Nov 22, 2010 the rates per species were:

- i. 0 - 15: H 4-6 MeV/nuc
- ii. 15 - 31: 3He 4-6
- iii. 32 - 47: 4He 4-6
- iv. 48 - 63: 4He 6-12
- v. 64 - 79: CNO 4-6
- vi. 80 - 95: CNO 6-12

-
- vii. 96 - 111: NeMgSi 4-6
 - viii. 112 - 127: NeMgSi 6-12
 - ix. 128 - 143: Fe 4-6
 - x. 144 - 159: Fe 6-12
9. Due to incorrect calculation of instrument livetimes in ground data processing, LET intensities at the peak of the July 23 2012 event were inaccurate. LET intensities during other periods of high particle intensities were also inaccurate to a lesser extent. The livetime calculation has been corrected on April 3 2013, and a new version of the data has been released – (Currently: Version 11).